

NOVATEUR PUBLICATION

JournalNX

A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 2

ISSN: 2581-4230

SJIF 2023: 8.075

www.journalnx.com

FEBRUARY, 2023

EMAIL

editor@journalnx.com

LOCATION

466, Sadashiv Peth, Pune, M.S.
India

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AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF LIFESTYLE, IMPACT ON SEAFARER'S HEALTH: PRECAUTIONARY MEASURES AND ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The maritime industry has long had a reputation as a "risky career," both in terms of physical and mental health. Those who make their living at sea face unique stresses in the job, such as long hours, poor working conditions, and solitude. This research aims to examine the connection between mental and psychological health at work and issues of work-life balance and healthy living. Discussions center on expanding the number of crew members, providing more training and resources, and keeping an eye on employees for signs of mental illness.

Keywords: Occupation, Safety, Health, Mariners, Control and Maritime.

INTRODUCTION

Occupational Safety and Health (OHS), a study of the literature on a variety of topics impacting marine workers across the world. Despite the fact that the current body of knowledge on seafarers OHS is disjointed and fails to paint a global picture of OHS in the maritime industry, the available studies unequivocally reveal high rates of occupational fatalities, injuries, and ill health in the maritime industry and point to the urgent need for further investigation in this area.

The majority of the research on marine health and safety originates from the Nordic and North Western European nations. In this chapter's second section, we look at the additional difficulties created by economic globalization in terms of protecting the occupational health and safety of maritime personnel. It explains how deregulation and the free flow of money and labor across borders have contributed to unsafe working conditions for maritime workers and may have harmed OHS management generally. Various responses to the negative effects of economic globalization on the marine sector, and show how the sector has implemented self-regulation to raise OHS standards.

The marine business is an exciting and rewarding field to work in for many reasons. Some people would like a less conventional work schedule, one that allows for more periods of both work and rest. You may travel the globe while earning a living by choosing a career on the high seas. The mariner's lifestyle may be quite satisfying, but it also comes with its fair share of difficulties. Due to the nature of the profession, being a mariner is taxing on all three of your body's systems. Being a mariner is an unconventional profession in that it requires significant time away from family and friends. This presents difficulties that employees in other industries may not encounter.

This book will cover the physical, mental, and emotional health concerns faced by sailors, as well as the best methods for avoiding or dealing with these dangers, all with the goal of helping mariners have happy, healthy lives while at sea. Trade across the world has relied heavily on the accessibility of rivers for transport. As a result of scientific and technological advancements, maritime transport has

changed considerably throughout time. Historically, sailing ships were the primary mode of maritime transport, traversing both inland and coastal seas to deliver goods. These ships have come a long way from the days of basic sailing boats, with current versions being large container ships that can make transoceanic journeys while still navigating inland and coastal waterways. Multinational shipping organizations, multibillion-dollar trade, and worldwide commerce have come to dominate the maritime transportation business, which was formerly controlled by individual explorers, voyagers, and merchants.

The need to facilitate international commerce has spurred the development of the marine transportation sector. As globalization and marine commerce have grown intertwined, the international maritime transport sector has expanded rapidly. The United States has its own marine transportation business, which is governed by a set of laws that differ significantly from those of other countries. The Jones Act, the Maritime Security Program, and Cargo Preference are all examples of such laws. Since many countries have not had the same opportunities for advanced development, their marine rules, laws, and regulations are not as advanced as those in the United States.

Maintaining a safe and healthy workplace is a top priority for all humans. The maximum possible level of physical, mental, and social health in the workforce across all industries is the end goal of this movement, which seeks to achieve this goal via the customization of the working environment to each individual employee. As a worldwide problem, workplace health and safety are shifting gears. The fast industrial and agricultural growth taking place in emerging nations, as well as the introduction of new goods and product processes from these regions, seem to be the key contributors to this peculiarity.

Workplace health concerns are likely to arise as many of these nations transition from manual labor to service automation in their primary productive sectors, including manufacturing, mining, and agriculture. Furthermore, these nations' unquenchable need for technological development has necessitated the importation of high-tech gear and equipment across all economic sectors, not just manufacturing. Inevitably, this has been linked to a shift in the composition of the labor force overall, with the result being more women in paid positions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Shan, Desai. (2021). The COVID-19 pandemic has altered the labour market. However, international commerce is still seen as a vital industry, and shipping is crucial to globalisation so much so that its momentum cannot be halted. More than 90% of the world's goods are transported by water, yet since the epidemic began, few nations have let seamen disembark and return home. The limits on travel due to COVID-19 have created an OHS emergency in the maritime industry. In this research, the authors draw on interviews with 29 sailors to examine the occupational health and safety (OHS) issues they encountered during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Baygi, F., et.al (2020). Interventions to improve health and safety at sea are little documented, and the available evidence is inconsistent and mixed. It is important to assess existing data from marine contexts to develop systematic knowledge in this area since land-based enterprises continue to place a premium on lifestyle and health promotion. In this study, we combed through the literature on lifestyle interventions in the maritime context by searching the databases PubMed, NLM Gateway (for MEDLINE), Institute for Scientific Information/Web of Science (ISI/WOS), and SCOPUS as recently as

January 2019. Two readers evaluated the articles and compiled the information. Research quality was evaluated using the Cochrane Risk of Bias method to ensure only high-quality studies were included. Intervention efficacy was given as a qualitative synthesis because of the substantial variation across trials. Six research were done in marine settings in the United States, three studies focused on Danish seafarers, and one study was conducted in Finland. Six studies mostly focused on educational interventions such stress management, healthy eating, anti-smoking and anti-drinking sessions, sexual behavior programmed, and counselling regarding preventative tactics. A total of four studies detailed the introduction of various treatments, including micro- Positive, if modest, effects of structural and/or educational interventions in marine contexts were reported in three investigations. All of the listed studies were of low quality. This study found that there are few trials on lifestyle treatments in a marine setting, and that those that do exist are of low quality.

Demirel, Ergun. (2022).This study advocates for a more practical approach to continuing professional development (CPD) for mariners, who, by virtue of their occupation, have extremely limited access to regular educational options. The literature review and industry survey were undertaken to get a firm grasp of the idea and applications of continuing professional development (CPD) and to identify the factors that directly impact CPD possibilities for those working in the shipping sector. To address the current shortcomings of the CPD system, we examine the available data to see how it might be improved. The paper's contribution is an argument for how to help sailors by giving them a useful CPD system that can adapt to the demands of a continually evolving industry.

Yassin AH, et.al (2022) Even when COVID-19 was in effect, U.S. sailors remained on the high seas. Limited study on workplace determinants of mental health among COVID-19 participants despite the fact that several facets of their employment may put them at risk for negative mental health outcomes. N = 1384 U.S. mariners were surveyed online between January and July 2021 about their feelings of depression, anxiety, and stress in relation to their work, their feelings about the safety of their workplace, and their experiences sailing during COVID-19. Additionally, demographic data was gathered. Anxiety and depression logistic regression models and a stress linear regression model were created. The likelihood of experiencing depression and anxiety, as well as an increase in stress, were observed to rise in tandem with the number of COVID-19 worries expressed and with the self-reported poor mental health. Having a higher number of negative on-the-job events correlates with higher levels of stress and depression among sailors.

Ibrahim, Irwan et.al (2020).Each and every worker's safety has to be taken into account. The standard of workplace safety is accountable for and directly related to the lives of the people who work there. All well-established businesses place a premium on addressing any and all safety concerns. DD & I Engineering Sdn. Bhd., a subcontractor for Malaysia Marine and Heavy Engineering Sdn. Bhd. (MMHE), a business that does maritime-focused heavy work, hosted the research. The firm has been in operation since 2001 and is headquartered in PasirGudang, Johor. The company specialises in marine engineering tasks such as blasting, painting, hydro jetting, power tooling, cleaning, mucking-out sludge, dislodging, disloping, valve, piping, main engines services, boiler, generator, cooling system, pump, navigation, underwater works, and repair, maintenance, and

services of all manner of works pertaining of marine, ship, and vessel. The purpose of this investigation is to determine how familiarity with health and safety procedures affects marine security. A total of five areas of health and safety expertise fire, manual handling, noise and vibration, safety signs, and general health and safety were selected as independent variables for this study.

RESEARCH GAP

Carcinogen effects, organic solvents and other chemicals, selenium, methylmercury, and others are all part of the potentially hazardous working environment for seafarers. The musculoskeletal, dental, auditory, and ocular health of seafarers are all put at danger by their line of work. The symptoms from such systems are widespread, and they vary depending on factors including age, number of years in the nautical profession, kind of job activities on board, weather, equipment, crew size, and experience. The health of sailors is directly related to their way of life. Smoking is quite common among fisherman and passive smoking is a serious issue for many of them. Many facets of society are driven by people's occupations. A person's occupation is a reflection of their intellect, education, personality, ambition, social standing, and way of life, among other social and psychological aspects. Jobs that involve dealing with clients or customers have numerous parallels with those that involve alcohol use or addiction. Alcohol intake rates are correlated with cirrhosis mortality rates. Such death rates are obviously higher than normal in several professions. Jobs with above-average risks are the ones to avoid at all costs. Occupational risk factors include access to alcohol on the job, peer pressure to drink, isolation from friends and family, and lack of supervision. Sleeping problems, excess weight, and emotional distress are all linked to poor health outcomes among sailors. Shipyard labour is characterized by lulls and flurrying activity. Sleep problems are associated with stress symptoms among sailors.

TRADITIONAL OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH CONCERN

High quantities of carcinogens have been found in the workspaces of mariners, according to recent research. They demonstrate an elevated risk of cancer due to exposure among mariners in contrast to the general population. Benzene was found at very high amounts in the workplaces of product tankers, according to research by Moen et al. (1995). The authors determined that the sailors were exposed to significant levels of carcinogens by monitoring air samples during cargo loading and unloading activities from the deck of eight tankers at Norwegian ports and analyzing questionnaires submitted by the seafarers exposed to such circumstances. They deduced that as a result, sailors had a higher chance of developing malignancies including lung and urogenital.

Another research analyzing the death pattern among maritime who utilized data from the economically active male Danish population between 1970 and 1985. It shown that sailors, due to their occupation, are substantially more prone to cancer than the overall population, as a result of their exposure to toxins. The authors discovered that engine room officers had a 1.9-fold higher risk of developing respiratory cancer than the overall working population in that nation, and that engine room ratings had a 2.5-fold higher risk. The authors found that the workplace was a major factor in the increased rate of cancer among professionals in the field looked at the incidence of cancer among Danish sailors from 1986 to 1999. The research included 33,340 male participants and 11,291 female participants, and it utilized the national rate's standard incidence ratio. Findings indicated that male

sailors had a 1.26-fold higher risk of developing cancer due to exposure than men in the general population. When compared to those of women sailors, the ratio was 1.07.

OCCUPATIONAL DISEASES DUE TO LIFESTYLE AND WORK-LIFE BALANCE

Lastly, a number of recent studies highlight the negative effects of seafarers' lifestyles and lack of work-life balance on their health. Long working hours, isolation and monotony aboard ships, and long-term separation from home and family to be the main cause of stress in the lives of seafarers. Sailors are more likely to develop alcoholism and mental health problems due to their working environment. Several studies have shown that sailors had a higher-than-average suicide risk due to mental health issues. For example, a study found that Polish seafarers were three times more likely to commit suicide and more prone to suffer from mental and emotional illnesses than the Polish working population on land. In maritime fatalities in the United Kingdom, if half of the "open-verbatim" involving missing seafarers are in fact suicides, it would account for fourteen percent of all maritime workers' deaths.

The authors noted that this was much greater than it was for other working groups, such as the total US population, where studies suggest that just 3% of deaths occur due to work-related suicide. Parker et al. undertook one of the most extensive studies to date on the topic of maritime workers' health on the job. The authors participated in a large-scale Australian research called FASTOH (fatigue, stress, and occupational health of seafarers), in which approximately 1800 sailors who frequented Australian beaches provided replies. The writers of this article examined the effects of work-related stress on the health and lifestyles of sailors. According to the research, sailors are more likely to report high levels of stress from all sources compared to members of the normative group. In particular, the researchers noted that the health of sailors was negatively impacted by factors such as heat, excessive humidity, and noise levels. Half or more of the participants in the research reported sleeping for six hours or less each day, highlighting the need of enough rest for good health. Sleep deprivation was a common problem among sailors for several reasons, including long working hours, short length of sleep, noise and vibration from numerous engines and equipment, and heavy rocking of the ship during inclement weather.

MENTAL HEALTH AND PSYCHOLOGICAL WELLBEING OF MARITIME PERSONNEL:

The mental and physical demands of working aboard a ship are frequently quite different from those of working in an office. As a distinct occupation, seafarers are unusually isolated due to their constant presence in the workplace, both during and outside of normal business hours. Since they spend so much time with their coworkers, it's crucial that they get along well and that their teams work well together. However, studies show that tensions arise frequently between different ranks and departments, which, when combined with extended absences from loved ones, can cause feelings of isolation and homesickness. In addition, seafarers often spend long periods of time alone in a setting that is not good for their psychological well-being: Being aboard a ship for an extended period of time may subject one to unpleasant environmental circumstances, such as loud sounds, vibration, sudden drops in temperature, spikes in temperature, and fluctuations in humidity. The most recent Seafarers Happiness Index research found that many seafarers feel forced to work excessive hours due to the long hours they are expected to work and the physical demands of their jobs. Long trips and the

resulting time zone changes may worsen the sleep deprivation and poor quality of life experienced by seafarers who operate on a 'watch system. Additionally, variables such as ship engine noise and vibration, lengthy shifts, unpredictable work hours, a rotating watch system as opposed to a constant watch cycle, night shifts, and inconsistent sleep amount are all contributors to weariness.

Extensive research has been done on the mental health of seafarers, and previous evaluations have looked at topics including stress, maritime pilots' happiness on the job, and depression and suicide. Collectively, these have identified a number of risk factors associated with poor wellbeing, such as: fatigue; high workload; long voyages; long working hours; rotating watch systems; short ship-turnaround times; little advance warning of being required to serve as a lookout; environmental stressors on board like motion, noise, and vibration; economic pressure; disturbed sleep; night shifts; variable weather; limited time for recreation.

In the first half of 2021, when this review was written, the COVID-19 pandemic presented unique difficulties for the maritime community, such as how to deal with infectious disease outbreaks at sea, how to implement quarantine and testing procedures, how to communicate with port authorities, how to handle crew rotations, and how to limit time spent ashore. The International Labour Organization's (ILO) Committee of Experts determined in December 2020 that governments had breached their duty of care to seafarers during the pandemic by failing to provide them with the minimum standards for basic rights like healthcare, repatriation, annual leave, and shore leave as required by international law. The number of calls to the ISWAN mariners' hotline reportedly tripled at the height of the epidemic. As a result, it is crucial to know what variables contribute to mental illness in maritime companies and how to help maritime workers.

MARINER HEALTH AND WELLBEING

Understanding the significance of this responsibility is the first step in making good changes to the health of your troops. After all, no business wants to waste time and resources on something that will fail. There are many good reasons to invest in your workers' health and fitness. Contributing to the health of your sailors allows you to:

- **Abide by regulations:** Regulations, such as the standards established by the Occupational Safety and Health Administration, may have been broken if your existing practices are causing major health concerns or other damage to your personnel (OSHA). The penalties for these sorts of infractions may be rather high. Making the required adjustments to guarantee compliance with all applicable health and safety regulations for workers is of the utmost importance.
- **Set employees up for success:** Business organizations should make every effort to assist workers in reaching their maximum potential. workers who take care of their health tend to be more productive. Workers whose mental or physical health is suffering may fall short of expectations, while those in good shape will be motivated and able to deliver.
- **Establish goodwill with employees:** The employer-employee relationship relies heavily on goodwill. One of the greatest ways to do this is to show genuine interest in the marines' health and happiness on all levels (physical, mental, and emotional).

- **Attract new talent:** Increasing the standard of living for sailors is likely to entice more individuals to join the maritime workforce. In the modern workplace, employees place a premium on a job's potential benefits to their overall well-being. To a mariner's eye, the benefits of working for your organization are immediately apparent, especially for those currently operating in the field.

THE PHYSICAL HEALTH CHALLENGES THAT COME WITH SEAFARING

While any vocation has the potential for accidents, sailing has a reputation for being especially risky. There are a number of physical health dangers associated with seafaring. Some are associated with a mariner's specific duties or work environment, while others are the result of more general lifestyle factors like smoking.

Some known dangers to mariners' physical health include:

- **Cardiovascular disease:** The most common cause of mortality among sailors is sudden cardiac arrest. Despite the fact that the risk of cardiovascular disease among seafarers is similar to that of the general population, it is noteworthy since many seafarers must fulfil health standards to qualify for the profession. Cardiac incidents aboard ships also have a poorer prognosis than they would on land since the person performing resuscitation is not a trained medical expert and does not respond quickly enough.
- **Fatigue:** A mariner's weariness may be brought on by the high demands of their profession, the long hours they must work, and the little number of people they have to help them. Tiredness increases a sailor's risk of injury.
- **Communicable diseases:** Malaria, cholera, yellow fever, TB, and other infectious illnesses are among those that are more likely to infect travellers than locals.
- **Cancer:** Due to their frequent exposure to harmful compounds and the sun's UV rays, mariners have an elevated risk of developing cancer on the job. As a result of their choices in life, such as alcohol use, tobacco use, and unhealthy eating habits, they may be at a higher risk of developing cancer.
- **Hand-arm vibration syndrome:** Hand-arm vibration syndrome (HAVS) is a condition that may be developed by mariners who often use power tools and can lead to temporary pain and, if left untreated, chronic incapacity.
- **Musculoskeletal Disorder:** Given that many seafarers work 12-hour shifts or 6-on, 6-off schedules, it's no surprise that some of them develop musculoskeletal diseases from lack of off-duty exercise.

STEPS TO PROTECT MARINER WELLBEING ABOARD SHIPS DURING COVID-19

Hundreds of thousands of seafarers are trapped aboard ships all over the globe, with few or no options to leave and return home. Shipping firms, trade groups, and governments must work together to ensure their safety. They also have an obligation to ensure the continued emotional and physical

wellbeing of the crew members who have been forced to stay on board beyond the completion of their scheduled tours.

The International Maritime Organization (IMO) is lobbying the United Nations (UN) for permission to classify seafarers as "keyworkers," which would facilitate crew changes and repatriations without penalty. This is crucial since current reports indicate the COVID-19 quarantine would likely last until the end of April.

Shipowners and crew managers face a tragic and sad scenario when they are unable to replace crew members or return them home. This is an insurmountable issue that no one wants to solve.

However, the vast majority of sailors have courageously accepted their new, mandatory responsibility to stay "indefinitely" on board and aid the international struggle to halt this devastating global epidemic.

Now more than ever, seafarers must manage their own stress, combat the effects of exhaustion brought on by longer shifts at sea, work together with equally nervous and worried coworkers both at sea and onshore, in makeshift home offices, and communicate with authorities both domestically and abroad. They have to deal with all of this while keeping up the same level of productivity they had before to the outbreak.

Most significantly, while stranded at sea, sailors must contend with worrying about their loved ones' safety. Each sailor's delicate mental stability is further tested by the conflicting demands of reassuring loved ones back home of their well-being while still feeling powerless to participate or help.

Cynics would point out that this is something people have done for a long time—during pandemics like SARS and H1N1 and even the 1918 flu, people kept the world's supply chain running smoothly. Perhaps such was the case in the past, but never before have we seen anything like this.

As a result of COVID19, we were all forced to deal with the 'unexpected,' 'unthought of,' situation; the meteor that landed on Earth, with few contingency plans accessible or ready to deploy, and without understanding the pandemic's global scope and devastating health, social, and economic consequences.

CONCLUSION

Historically, living on the high seas has been associated with a number of negative connotations, including a poor quality of life and a number of health problems. Regardless of the huge population of sailors and the severity of their health problems. Based on the findings of this analysis, bad lifestyle choices and occupational illnesses seem to be the most significant threats to the health of seafarers. To determine the causes of maritime workers' poor health and the steps that might be taken to improve their working circumstances, a long-term population study is necessary.

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STUDY ON INVENTORY MANAGEMENT IMPROVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The management of inventories is a complex issue area that falls within the purview of supply chain management. In order for businesses to be able to meet the demands of their customers, they need to maintain stocks in warehouses. Keeping these inventories requires companies to pay holding charges, which results in funds being frozen and making them susceptible to loss. Therefore, the aim of inventory management is to determine the number of stocked items that will satisfy the demand while minimising the likelihood of having excess inventory. This article provides a case study on inventory management for the assembly firm to demonstrate its findings. It has been suggested that using inventory management in order to cut down on stock levels and using an agent system in order to automate the activities involved in inventory management are both viable options.

Keywords: Management Improvement.

INTRODUCTION

The stock of any item or resource that is utilised in an organisation is referred to as the organization's inventory. This inventory may include any items or resources that are utilised in the organisation. This phrase is applicable to any asset or resource that is used by the organisation in any capacity. The terms "raw materials," "work in progress," and "finished products" are used to refer to the three different categories of inventory that may be found in manufacturing plants (Fig. 1). The organisational structure of the document may be broken down as follows: first, the task at hand is described; next, the current circumstance is evaluated; after that, a solution is suggested; next, the experiments are shown; and, lastly, the findings are discussed.

OBJECTIVE

1. To keep enough inventory to meet customer demand,
2. To study on Inventory Management Improvement

RESEARCH METHOD

Even though inventory management is not a new concept, some businesses still choose not to use it in their operations in order to save money on stock. Finding out how much and when to order is one of the responsibilities of inventory management.

The company's employees are the ones tasked with carrying out the research; the company's primary business is the fabrication of microchips from their component parts and the subsequent sale of these products to end users. As a consequence of this, there are warehouses stocked with stockpiles of both raw materials and completed commodities (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Different kinds of industrial stockpiles

The author discusses numerous of the reasons why it is necessary to keep inventories, including the following:

- In order to fulfil the expected level of demand;
- To meet the needs of the industrial process;
- To reduce the risk of experiencing stock-outs;
- in order to maximise the use of order cycles;
- To protect oneself against future price hikes or to take advantage of discounts offered for larger purchases;
- To provide permission for operations;
- In order to disconnect different parts of the manufacturing and distribution chain.

In the event that this does not occur, it will cause delays in manufacturing, shortages, and/or unhappy consumers. The management of inventory presents a issue in the sense that having inventory is necessary, yet having inventory is not desired due to the costs involved with managing inventory. Having inventory is required in the sense that having inventory is required. It is feasible that the expenditures associated with maintaining an inventory might pile up to a considerable sum over time. As a direct outcome of the aforementioned situation, inventory management is an integral part of supply chain management. Inventory management is a difficult problem domain that falls within the purview of supply chain management. The study was continued in this publication by adding fresh tests and predicting algorithms to the previously analysed data.

Fig. 2. putting the finishing touches on the company's stockpiles

According to the authors, just 8% of businesses have staff members who have received adequate training for inventory management. It is common practise for businesses to maintain sizable inventory reserves in order to successfully meet customer requirements.

DATA ANALYSIS

For the year 2014, the sales and inventory information for the company's warehouses and distribution centres were analysed. The data analysis of the variation in the number of microchips produced the year before revealed that there were things in stock in 2014 that did not sell. This was suggested by the fact that the variance in the number of microchips made was analysed. This was shown by the fact that there was a shift in the total quantity of microchips manufactured in the year prior to the one in question. The following is a list of the outcomes that occurred as a direct consequence of making use of these components: 16.69% of the total supplies that were kept at the warehouse (at the end of 2014) did not see any form of movement at any point over the course of the previous year; As a direct and immediate result of the passage of time, 3.95 percent of the total stocks saw a reduction in amount; and 5.13% of the total inventories that did not experience any sales during the course of 2014 saw their quantity increase as a result of the production of new ones. All of these factors contributed to the overall quantity of the inventories in the warehouse at the end of 2014. At the end of 2014, the total size of the stocks housed in the warehouse could be directly attributed to all of these various causes.

In addition, there were certain things whose combined quantity was more than the one that was sold, but at the same time there was a significant number of inventories in stock (Fig. 3). There were also goods for which the firm had a high inventory level but was simultaneously producing new ones; as a result, the amount of the company's inventory at the end of 2014 was more than the quantity of its yearly sales (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. The activities of two microchips on an annual basis

It was also discovered that the inventory level for some goods was excessively high, despite the fact that the amount sold each month was lower than the item's safety supply (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. The amounts of inventory for two different types of microchips

Additionally, it was seen that the inventory level for one item had dropped to zero, which suggested that the item was no longer available for purchase (Fig. 4). Therefore, inventory management was strongly suggested to be included into this company's operations.

ABC Classification

ABC classification, also known as ABC analysis, is a fundamental supply chain approach that is often executed by inventory controllers and materials managers. It is also the first step in the inventory management process. With the use of this categorization, managers are able to give priority to their time and money resources. The Pareto analysis, upon which the ABC analysis is founded, asserts that only 20% of the products are responsible for 80% of sales. It suggests that a limited number of goods in inventory are responsible for the highest levels of sales (Table 1). In most cases, fewer than twenty percent of the products categorised as class A are responsible for as much as eighty percent of the income. The following 15% (80%–95%) of income contribution comes from goods classified as Class B. The remaining 5% of income comes from goods and services categorised as class C.

TABLE 1 ABC CLASSIFICATION

	Number of items	Number of annual sales revenue
Class A items	About 20 %	About 80 %
Class B items	About 30 %	About 15 %
Class C items	About 50 %	About 5 %

The goods of a corporation are often divided into three categories using the ABC categorization in order to give priority in terms of inventory management.

- Items designated as Class A are the most important ones. For these goods, stringent inventory controls, regular reviews of demand predictions and use rates, extremely accurate component data, and frequent cycle counts are required to ensure the correctness of the permanent inventory balance;
- Items in the Class B category have a lower level of criticality. These goods need just rudimentary inventory management, periodic evaluations of demand projections and consumption rates, data that is relatively reliable, and cycle counting that occurs less often but on a regular basis;
- Because Class C goods have the least effect in terms of warehouse activity and financials, they are the ones that need the fewest inventory management.

The definition of class A products, which are microchips that account for the top 80% of total yearly sales, serves as the beginning point for inventory management. Class B items are those that account for the next 15% of income, while class C things make up the remaining 5%. In order to have a deeper comprehension of the mathematics required for ABC categorization, kindly refer to.

Table 2 displays the results of the ABC categorization that was performed on the analysed firm based on their total yearly revenue.

TABLE 2 PART OF THE MICROCHIP CLASSIFICATION OF THE COMPANY FRAGMENT

	Microchips	ABC classification
1	mchipcode56	B
2	mchipcode71	A
3	mchipcode139	C
4	mchipcode49	C
5	mchipcode133	C
6	mchipcode33	A
7	mchipcode264	C
8	mchipcode471	C
9	mchipcode473	C
10	mchipcode38	C
11	mchipcode39	C
12	mchipcode40	A
13	mchipcode96	C
14	mchipcode620	B
15	mchipcode674	C

It is recommended to employ a make-to-order manufacturing method for class C goods that have a demand volume that is either low or nonexistent.

Demand Forecasting Methods

The process of estimating the number of consumers who will buy a product or service in the not-too-distant future is known as demand forecasting. This may be used to predict the amount of products or services that will be Methods for predicting future demand fall into the following categories:

- Methods of qualitative prognostication;
- Methods of quantitative prediction.

When quantitative forecasting techniques cannot be performed due to a lack of accessible historical data, restricted historical data, or an absence of present relevance, qualitative forecasting methods are often used. The accuracy of the prediction is reliant on the abilities and expertise of the forecaster(s), in addition to the information that is readily accessible. This is a technique that is employed, and its application is based on how consumers and industry professionals believe or feel a product will sell. When it comes to developing company plans and estimating their revenues for the

first year, many new enterprises turn to this strategy. The following are some examples of qualitative models:

- A jury composed of senior executives;
- Sales force composite;
- Delphi method;
- Consumer market survey.

Quantitative approaches of forecasting are used to the numbers or quantities of products that were sold in the past in order to provide forecasts about the amount of product that will be sold in the near future. The vast majority of the time, this forecast will also contain quantity predictions for the next monetary year. Methods of quantitative forecasting may include things like multiplicative seasonal indices, moving averages based on the most recent period of demand, as well as basic and weighted moving averages. In each of these approaches, historical information is factored into a variety of mathematical equations to arrive at a conclusion about the quantity of a product or service that is expected to be purchased at certain periods in the foreseeable future.

In this specific circumstance, in order to anticipate future demand using historical data on demand for the year 2014, the quantitative forecasting methodologies that are used in this instance are those that are indicated below:

- A technique of predicting that is naive;
- Prediction based on the simple moving average;
- Prediction based on the weighted moving average;
- A technique of exponentially smoothing data;
- Single moving average.

The accuracy of the prediction may be evaluated based on the forecasting errors, which are understood to be the disparity between the actual demand amount and the quantity that was projected. The following is a list of some measurements of the accuracy of forecasting: Indicators of bias in predictions include The direction in which bias might take can be either positive or negative. The tracking signal establishes whether or not the prediction is within the permissible control boundaries. If the tracking signal slips beyond the control limits that have been pre-set, there is a bias issue with the technique of forecasting, and it is necessary to conduct an examination of the process by which predictions are made. The offered article provides a more in-depth description of the techniques of predicting as well as the measurements of accuracy.

Fig. 5. The real demand and forecasted demand for one microchip.

Figure 5 depicts the inventory level graph together with the results of the forecasting process for one class A microprocessor. The results of the calculations used to assess how accurately forecasts are made have yielded the forecasting algorithm that is suitable for this kind of microprocessor. All of the microchips produced by the corporation have been predicted using the procedures that were described above.

Replenishment Policies

Maintaining and exercising control over stored products is made easier with the help of an inventory system, which offers the organisational framework and operational regulations necessary for this. The system is in charge of the ordering and receiving of commodities, including the instant at which the order was placed, in addition to the maintenance of a record of what was ordered, how much of it was ordered, and from whom the order was made.

The two basic kinds of inventory management software are single-period systems and multiple-period systems respectively.

- In an inventory system with just one period, unsold products at the conclusion of the period are discarded rather than being carried over to the next period (for example, newspapers). However, there is a possibility that the unsold objects have some value as salvage.

- In an inventory system with many periods, any products that were left unsold at the conclusion of one period are made available for purchase in the next period.

In this section, we will talk about a system for managing inventory that incorporates a number of different time periods. These two categories of models each have a certain time span that they cover. When the predetermined reorder level has been achieved, an order is placed according to the fixed-order quantity model. For this model to work, it is necessary to do constant inventory checks. In contrast, in the model with a set time period, the ability to place orders is not accessible until the model's final specified time period has passed.

Fixed-order quantity models make an effort to determine not only the reorder point, which is denoted by the letter R , at which an order, denoted by the letter Q , will be placed, but also the quantity of the order, which is denoted by the number Q . This is done so that the model can more accurately predict future stock levels. When the inventory level (which includes items that are presently in stock and those that are on order) hits the reorder point R , an order Q is placed. This includes products that are now in stock as well as those that are on order. This covers both things that are now in stock and those that are waiting to be shipped out to customers. When individuals speak about "on-hand" amounts, "on-order" numbers, and "backordered" quantities being deducted from one another, they are referring to the equation that is shown in the following paragraph. When individuals refer to their "inventory position," they are referring to this concept.

Only at certain intervals, such as once a week or once a month, for example, does the inventory be tallied when a model is being used that has a preset time period attached to it. Customers may choose to combine their purchases in certain circumstances, such as when they want to combine their orders in order to save money on the shipping charges connected with those items. It is advantageous for the business to count its inventory and place orders on a frequent basis. The order quantities that are generated by models with fixed-time period intervals change from period to period based on the utilisation rates. In most cases, they need for a greater degree of safety stock than would be required by a system with fixed-order quantities. The quantity of an inventory that is carried in addition to the amount that is anticipated to be demanded is known as the safety stock.

The following are some final thoughts to consider:

In the event that there is no change in demand, the reorder point will mirror the level of demand experienced throughout the lead period.

- If there is uncertainty about the demand, the reorder point will often be set higher than the anticipated demand during the lead period.
- The reorder point is calculated as the expected demand plus the safety stock.

Following the completion of a demand projection, it is feasible to compute reorder and safety stock points for each and every microchip (see Table 3). For more information on the calculations of reorder points and safety stocks, please refer to references.

Table 3 Fragment Of Results Of Forecasts, Safety Stock And Reorder Points For Microchips

Microchips	Forecasted Demand	Safety Stock	Reorder Point
mchipcode33	1688	2081	3769
mchipcode40	12249	9096	21345
mchipcode20	1508	1603	3111
mchipcode102	537	5927	6464
mchipcode465	3625	6363	9988

EXPERIMENT 1

The proposed inventory management result check that is based on real data is particularly fascinating since it combines estimations on future demand as well as methods for replenishment. This makes the check a good resource. Because of this, the check is quite helpful. The actual numbers account for demand information for the first five months of 2015, which was collected.

The purpose of this experiment is to first compare the recommended quantities of inventories with the results of the replenishment method with real demand, and then compare the recommended quantities of inventories with the company's stocks. Both of these comparisons are intended to determine which set of data is more accurate. At the end of the day, the objective of this experiment is to determine which of these criteria yields the findings that are the most accurate (Fig. 6).

As a consequence of carrying out the experiment, one or more of the following findings could be made: In contrast to the actual data, which shows an average inventory level of 20860 pieces, the suggested inventory management system shows an average inventory level of just 11705 pieces. The number of things that are now available for purchase has been cut down. In none of these two probable scenarios did the inventory of the product at question get depleted, therefore that cannot be an excuse.

Fig. 6. Analysis of the inventory management system in comparison to actual data

The experiment that was conducted for another microprocessor revealed that safety stock was used up over the whole of the lead period. This was due to the surprisingly high level of demand for them. The demand for that particular month was 17789 pieces, which is much more than the monthly average of 9800 pieces that it had been for the previous several months. This demand will be taken into consideration as an input variable in any additional calculations that are performed about the availability of the safety stock. According to the company's actual data, the average number of products in stock is 6964, but the planned inventory management system forecasts that the average number of items in stock would be 5955.

EXPERIMENT 2

The implementation of inventory management processes and the realisation of agent systems are both necessary steps in the development of the company's condition regarding inventory management. The suggested system may get several advantages from the use of the agent system, which are as follows:

- It has the ability to draw lessons from previous histories of inventory, forecasting, and replenishment;
- If necessary, it is able to adjust the methods used for demand forecasting, the constants used for inventory management, and the rules governing replenishment;
- It is able to guarantee the monitoring and management of a significant number of SKUs;
- It has the potential to give both independence and initiative.

This article describes a portion of the current study on AEMAS, which stands for Because it is a component of the Assembling Enterprise Multi-Agent System, it has therefore been connected to the agent responsible for inventory management. The person in charge of managing the inventory should be the one to decide when and how many microchips should be manufactured, since this is a choice that should be left up to them. This is one of the responsibilities that are placed on the agent's shoulders. It includes information on the production capacity, the possible minimum reserves (often referred to as safety stock), and the strategy that is used to estimate the future demand for the

product. The feasible minimum reserves are sometimes referred to as the safety stock in certain circles. The inventory management agent has a variety of behaviours, including an ABC classification algorithm, future demand forecasting algorithms, and replenishment procedures. These behaviours are meant to prevent out-of-stock conditions while simultaneously reducing inventory levels and the costs that are associated with holding them. Additionally, these behaviours are designed to keep out of stock situations from occurring.

Fig. 7 The use of agent systems in the management of inventories as a concept

After the forecasting methods have been applied to microchips and the forecasting errors have been calculated, the Excel file will be supplied as input data to the ABC classification algorithm of the agent system. This will be done after the forecasting techniques have been applied to microchips. The facts that were gathered are being put to use to choose the method of forecasting that is going to be most suitable for each microchip that is going to be used in the not too distant future. The conclusions drawn from the exercise of forecasting are included into the computations performed by the algorithm that manages replenishment. Based on these calculations, the algorithm decides both the reorder points and the quantity of the safety stock. The agent-based inventory management system performs an analysis on this demand, and then compares the outcomes to the demand that was forecasted. This assessment is carried out in order to ensure that the true demand can be satisfied. After that, it modifies the incoming orders to create the product, if it turns out that is necessary in order to do so.

Fig. 8. Examination of the inventory management agent system in comparison with actual data
 The second experiment is designed to test the hypothesis that different replenishment strategies may be used while still fulfilling the actual demand for the product. Once again, the comparison of the amounts of the various inventory levels is provided.

The following findings have been uncovered from the experiment: When compared to the actual inventory level held by the corporation, the quantity of the first kind of microchips held in stock has been reduced. The agent system suggests an average inventory level of 11461 pieces, which is much lower than the company's actual inventory level of 20860 pieces.

CONCLUSION

Management of inventory is a vital function for every business that maintains stock. It is necessary for businesses to maintain inventory, but only up to a certain level in order to prevent both running out of stock and having too much on hand. Inventory management has the potential to improve the present situation with the firm's inventory control and reduce the expenses incurred by the organisation. The agent system, on the other hand, suggests automating this process, as well as the fact that It can support a variety of techniques to predicting and adjust to changes in the environment that it is in. The current condition of inventory management is broken down and analysed in this article, and a solution that would improve things by a factor of two is proposed as a solution to the problem. The first thing that needs to be done in order to make improvements is to implement inventory management. This should be done with the goal of reducing both the total amount of inventory held by the organisation and the costs associated with maintaining that level of inventory by removing any surplus supplies. The implementation of the agent system is the second necessary step in the process of making improvements. This will make it possible to automate the operations that are involved in inventory management, as well as respond in a timely manner to demand variances that are different from the demand that was expected by adjusting the regulations governing replenishment.

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SWOT ANALYSIS OF PAKHTAOBOD DISTRICT, MAIN MACROECONOMIC INDICATORS AND AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION VOLUME ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This article discusses the SWOT analysis of Pakhtaabad district of Andijan region and the determination of the economic efficiency of economic sectors in the district, the comparative analysis of the share of economic efficiency of economic sectors in the period of 2020-2022. Information is provided on the annual growth rates and share of the macro-economic indicators of the district and the indicators of the economic sectors of small business entities.

Keywords: SWOT analysis, macroeconomics, investment, microfinancing, leasing, insurance, consulting, marketing, gross economy, export, import.

Introduction

The national economy of our country entered a new stage during the years of independence. At the first stage of the market economy (1991-1994), laws on economic reforms were adopted, and its legal basis was created. Reforms covered all aspects of life. Since 1995, Uzbekistan has entered the second stage of social reform. This stage includes the completion of the formation of structures for the transition to market relations, comprehensive development of the country's national economy, stabilization of the national currency and the completion of privatization of state property related to ensuring its internal conversion, as well as directing the economy from the production of raw materials to the production of finished products. keeps it.

The Main Part

Pakhtaabad district borders the Kyrgyz Republic in the northeast and south, Izboskan in the west, and Jalakuduq districts in the northwest. There is 1 city, 67 neighborhoods, 25 settlements in the district. The district is considered a natural scenic area in terms of its nature and location. In particular, the territory of the district is located in the north of our region, on the flat plain of the Norin and Koradaryo oases. . Summer is hot, average temperature in July is 27°, winter is relatively cold, average temperature in January is -3°. The vegetation period is 217 days, the average annual rainfall is 200-250 mm. From the point of view of the climate, the comfortable air temperature in the summer months allows our entrepreneurs in the district not only to grow agricultural products, but also other types of business activities.

SWOT-ANALYSIS. Strengths (S) - The total land area of the district is 26 thousand hectares. Therefore, 1.5 thousand hectares of land area of the farm is specialized for growing fruits and vegetables. 199,900 people live in the district. A high percentage of the working age population, especially young people under 30 years of age;

- a large consumer market for vegetable products has been formed due to the location of the district on the border with the neighboring Kyrgyz Republic,

- favorable climatic conditions and fertile soil necessary for the cultivation of agricultural products, the average score of land credit is 59.2;

- important branches of agriculture include grain growing, cotton growing, horticulture, viticulture. The annual volume of fruit and vegetable production is 217.4 thousand tons, meat 12.6 thousand tons, milk 82.2 tons, eggs 71.6 million.

Disadvantages (W) - low wages paid to workers in the agricultural sector;

- lack of fodder for livestock (0.02 ha of fodder area per 1 conditional head of animal);

- high price of feed for livestock, necessary for the production of meat, milk and eggs;

- products were not produced to the extent that could satisfy the demand of the district population for grapes, honey and fish products;

- regardless of the fact that the lands used for farming and livestock are located in the plain, more than 2 thousand hectares of land are irrigated with water from the Kyrgyz Republic, which causes a water shortage in these fields in the summer;

- low level of utilization of industrial capacities

- low level of processing of vegetables and fruits

- insufficient development of the business environment for the activation of investment activities, weak participation of financial institutions in the implementation of investment projects;

- limited possibilities of efficient use of the railway network and highways;

- low level of use of information services.

Opportunities (O) - availability of sufficiently high-level scientific qualifications and qualified personnel; Achieving acceptable rates of population growth;

- establishment of fruit and vegetable processing enterprises, about 127,000 tons of fruit and vegetables are grown in excess of the population's needs;

- organization of fruit and vegetable products and meat products processing enterprises;

- in order to increase the incomes of the population, develop sectors of the economy with high added value, increase jobs in labor-intensive sectors of production;

- Creating jobs for the district in the framework of folk crafts, including family business

- development of fruit and vegetable processing using modern technologies and techniques;

- development of animal husbandry, fishing, beekeeping and poultry

- development of building materials industry based on effective use of local raw materials;

- Development of market services (microfinancing, leasing, insurance, consulting, marketing, etc.), tourism and recreation services, provision of information and communication services in the future;

- renewal of the region's financial resources, formation of capital, formation of industrial-production and agricultural clusters;

- there are ample opportunities to export fruits and vegetables, rice and grape products throughout the year; - intensive expansion of fisheries in artificial water bodies in the district;
- the presence of large unused opportunities in the field of food processing
- availability of favorable conditions for the establishment of a sheep wool raw material processing enterprise;

Risks (T)- constant change of exported products.

- increase in prices of fuel, lubricants, chemical fertilizers; - inflation;
- in the conditions of increasing demand, the low level of processing of agricultural products and the low conditions of storage and packaging may lead to the loss of export opportunities;
- failure to accurately analyze product composition and quality in the production of fruit, vegetables and meat products;
- when the products are fully ripe, the market prices will decrease compared to the cost of production.

Key macroeconomic indicators (* growth rate in comparative classes)

Name of indicators	2020 (billion soums)	2021 (billion soums)	Difference (+;-)	Growth rate* (%)	Share in regional index (%)
Industrial products	510,2	592,5	82,3	107,1	1,6
including regional industrial products	298,7	270,8	-27,9	106,7	3,3
Consumer goods	301	387,2	86,2	134,5	1,5
Gross agricultural products	2109	2522,8	413,8	104,2	7,9
Investments in fixed capital	278,3	325,9	47,6	76,2	2,7
Construction works	198,6	284,3	85,6	120,1	5,1
Retail turnover	557,6	695,6	138	107,4	3,9
Services	413,6	702,9	289,3	120,3	4,7
Foreign trade turnover (thousand US dollars)	22,6	18,1	- 4,5	79,7	0,6
Export (thousand US dollars)	14,4	10,8	-3,6	73,9	1,1
Import (thousand US dollars)	8,1	7,3	-0,8	90,3	0,3

The volume of agricultural products in 2020-2021

Naming	Unit of measure	The volume of the product		Growth rate (%)
			in 2021	
Total agricultural gross product volume:	tons			
1. Cotton	tons	21948	23454	106,9
- on farms	tons	21948	23454	106,9
2. Total grain crops	tons	65841	63851	97,0
- on farms	tons	63199	61675	97,6
- in peasant farms	tons	1288	1283	99,6
-in agricultural enterprises	tons	1354	893	66,0
2.1. Grain with spikes	tons	50694	47270	93,2
- on farms	tons	50219	46820	93,2
- in agricultural enterprises	tons	475	450	94,7

Conclusion

SWOT analysis of Pakhtaabad district of Andijan region, its macroeconomic indicators and the level of agricultural production, strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and risks have been explained. If the macroeconomic indicators of industrial products amounted to 510.2 billion soums in 2020, we can see that this indicator amounted to 592.5 billion soums by the end of 2021. The growth coefficient increased by 107.1%, i.e. It is increasing by 82.3 billion soums. We can see this not only in industry, but also in the gross product of agriculture. At the end of 2020, the gross product of agriculture amounted to 2 trillion 109 billion soums, by the end of 2021 2 trillion 522.8 billion soums. This indicates that the macroeconomic indicators of the district continue to rise.

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THE PLACE OF THE PENCIL DRAWING DIRECTION OF FINE ARTS IN SCHOOLS

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Abstract:

This article reveals the special place of fine art among the types of art. Starting from general secondary education, paying deep attention to the types, forms and features of fine art, the views of the pencil image, which is considered its foundation, are highlighted.

Key words: fine art, illusionism, pencil drawing, artist, picture, "Laws of painting", methods, school.

Fine art

a type of art that captures color, sculpture, graphics; it reflects what is happening in spatial forms that are easily understood and understood. Depending on its characteristics, visual art creates a sense of objectivity—size, color, phase, as well as the material shape and environment of the predecessor, movement, and changes—from the emotional specificity of the image to illusionism. Switching is considered.

Historically, it is well-known that the scientific works that many great allies have created for many centuries have come through various writings, drawings, and photographs. Rock paintings from different eras served as the foundation for the creation of the first painting.

Kalamtasvir is considered the foundation and foundation of all kinds of fine art around the world. The artist is based on a pencil, regardless of which of the types of fine art he creates. He carefully places it against the bowstring, and with flesh were covered with flesh. These condemnations in the creation of artwork

helps the artist, and serves as the foremost source.

The artist begins by drawing in a pen to create him or her card or paintings. The work is then given a color jellyfish, which gives the viewer aesthetic peace of mind. In other words, without a pencil, no artist can make his work mature.

Kalamtasvir can also be an independently completed work of art. Many of the cards created in dreams, sanginas, pastels, sauces, and pens are located at various art museums and exhibitions around the world.

In the development of hand, mind, and sensory organs, it is necessary not only for a future artist but also for people from all walks of time. Leonardo da Vinci, the great artist and scholar of the Awakening era

As he noted in his essay "The Laws of Rangtasvir," *young people need to know perfectly how to draw "Jesus, awalo, painting" if they want to test themselves in science, painting.*

Ancient Egyptians mummified the dead, with the idea that [i.e. the One who is walking on a righteous and between right and place. For example, whether you get ancient Hindu, Chinese, or Greek philosophers, medieval Figures of the Eastern and Western Awakening periods, Uzbek scholars have a wide range of relationships between the material and spiritual world in their scientific heritage. For example, theoretical views of ancient philosophers Socrates and Plato, Epicurus and Democrats, Chinese intellectual Confucius, and other scholars are known in the history of science. Teaching

methods in visual art can be seen in the development of high culture of schools in ancient Egypt, Greece, Europe, and Rome

The intermolecular entity used by Jehovah's Witnesses in your country is a brochure entitled Charitable Planning to Benefit Kingdom Service Worldwide has been prepared. Since the 17th century, visual art has been dominated by the direction of classicism, and the creation of works that reflect things in similar forms has increased. The establishment of the academic education system has ensured the development of professor art schools. The quest to withdraw from classical (classical) realistic (academic) art styles and to seek traditional styles began. 20th Century Visual Art is complex and contradictory. The emphasis on its expression, preserving the demands and styles of classical realistic art on the one hand, demonstrates the power of the desire to fill each image produced with deep major content, but rather to find new expressions and imaging tools in the style of traditional Visual Art and to create a completely new art.

Visual art in Uzbekistan is accompanied by the processes that are taking place in the world, and each artist is characterized by his desire to express his views and evenings in innovative styles and forms. This starts with teaching styles in the educational process. With a special emphasis on improving the student's skills in fine art, it is advisable for every young expert to remember the opinions of renowned artists and scholars of this field and to slogan in the workplace. It is also intended to thoroughly study the laws and regulations of fine art by a scientist and artist with advanced skills in fine art who are engaged in the theory and practice of fine art. The main task of visual art is to develop the ability of a prospective specialist to feel and describe it live in his work and to bring Uzbek and world art to the younger generation properly. The process of developing practical skills in the field of visual art is carried out through life-imaging exercises through pencils. Many scientific articles, textbooks, and brochures have been written about this. In the past, during the awakening period, artists and artists expressed their views through their world-famous works of art and methodological research. With the help of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I. Karimov, the Gallery of Fine Arts of Uzbekistan was built in Tashkent and opened in August 2004.

In a nutshell, Visual arts, along with other subjects, are also organized in general secondary schools. Teachers should teach schoolchildren much more effectively during the course, perfectly aware of the forms, types, and characteristics of fine art. Kalamtasvir is also an important process for the development of fine art. Therefore, from school, perfect teaching students the vow of fine art, such as pencil holding, understanding the harmony of white and black colors, compatibility of shapes, compatibility of colors, elegance and skill, plays a major role in the later stages of education.

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THE ROLE OF INNOVATION IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation

In this article, innovation is becoming one of the most characteristic features of economic development and is analyzed as a factor accelerating the development of the market. There are also suggestions and recommendations on how to achieve the rapid development of entrepreneurship in the modern world through the widespread use of innovation.

Keywords: Innovation, capital, innovation process, factors of production, innovative entrepreneurship.

Currently, innovation is becoming one of the most characteristic features of economic development. Not long ago, this name reminded of something exotic, unknown and not very clear even among professionals, but now the innovation itself and its concepts are rapidly conquering the world. The international capital market, which plays a significant role in the innovation process and turns innovation into a strategic resource for enterprises, is expanding, and new financial structures are helping it in this regard.

The experience of developed countries shows that innovation is often hindered by people's direct negative attitudes and attitudes. However, a paradoxical situation is developing in Uzbekistan, that is, the whole society expresses positive attitude and support to innovative processes.

In particular, it is reflected in many normative legal documents adopted in Uzbekistan and bills widely discussed in social networks. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan of July 27, 2020 on innovative activity, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Science and Scientific Activity", the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of January 22, 2018 "On the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 Presidential Decree on the State Program for the Implementation of the Strategy of Actions in the Five Priority Areas of Development in the Year of Supporting Active Entrepreneurship, Innovative Ideas and Technologies, by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Decree No. PF-5975 dated March 26, 2020, "On measures to fundamentally update the state policy on economic development and poverty reduction", "Organization of the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Alleviation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its system organizations" on" No. PQ-4653 of March 26, 2020, "Improving the system of attracting the population to entrepreneurship and developing entrepreneurship r on additional measures" Resolution No. PQ-4862 dated October 13, 2020, "On effective organization of the activities of the entrepreneurship development agency under the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Alleviation of the Republic of Uzbekistan Among them are normative documents such as the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 17, 2021. The purpose of adopting these documents is to develop business

activities, to create favorable conditions for the creation and development of new entrepreneurs, to help increase the potential and efficiency of the innovation system, and to create a regulatory, financial and informational environment favorable for innovation. It is also to increase competitiveness and productivity in the industry, to encourage the increase of the share of high-tech products, to increase production and to increase the share in the structure of production and export, to expand the use of innovative technologies and advanced management.

The aim of the research work is to help increase the potential and efficiency of the system through the innovative development of the economy and the creation of new entrepreneurs. The tasks of the research are researching the stages of increasing competitiveness and productivity in the industry and justifying its specific features; to stimulate the increase in the share of high-tech products, to increase production and increase the share in the structure of production and export, to identify the factors affecting the expansion of the use of innovative technologies and advanced management.

Analysis of Literature on the Topic

According to some authors, there is both a traditional economy and a new economy developing on a different basis. In our opinion, it is appropriate to use the positive aspects of both of these models without opposing them, because it shows that the new one is gradually developing at the base of the traditional economy. Indeed, it is true that innovation has become a factor of production in the modern world. It is known that traditionally there are three factors of production: land, labor and capital. They were first analyzed by J. B. Say.¹ Currently, these factors usually include the ability of entrepreneurs and, according to some authors, the information factor, thus emphasizing the role of information in economic development. In our opinion, it is more correct to replace the opportunities of entrepreneurs with innovations or to connect both new factors with traditional factors. Currently, by studying the factors of production, the analysis is carried out more deeply and each factor is broken down. Land or natural factors are factors that do not provide long-term competitive advantages when used as the basis of entrepreneurship. In addition, many types of natural resources are non-renewable and can be exhausted after some time. On the other hand, the innovative factor is practically inexhaustible and it creates innovations that can be introduced into production; their expansion can ensure long-term competitiveness, because it is currently based on new, especially developed factors.

In fact, such a point of view cannot be called "absolutely new". Analyzing the factors of production mentioned above, "Say" emphasizes the role of the entrepreneur, because he coordinates the following factors of production: land, capital and labor, as well as the labor factor, which he used very widely, including not only labor, but also took into account scientific conclusions and knowledge necessary for product production and organization of production.

English scientist G. A. Hobson expressed this idea more vividly and included creative abilities in production factors². Analyzing the part of the economic system where new products appear, new

¹ Гужин А.А., Гужина Г.Н. Материальные интересы в системе экономического роста// Московское научное обозрение

² Гужин А.А., Гужина Г.Н. Материальные интересы в системе экономического роста// Московское научное обозрение

markets appear, and new technologies are introduced, he called it the "progressive production sector". Now we call it the innovation economy.

Of course, in the process of studying such a phenomenon as innovation, one should not forget the names of two scientists, that is, N. Kondratiev and the Austrian J. A. Schumpeter. It was Schumpeter who first defined the concept of innovation in his "Theory of Economic Development" study³. He interpreted innovation as a scientific and organizational combination of existing production factors aimed at solving commercial problems. Schumpeter directly noticed the source of development of economic systems in innovations. Because specific content innovation is change, they point out five typical changes:

1. Provision of new technologies, new technological processes or new production markets;
2. Introduction of products with new features;
3. Use of new raw materials;
4. Changes in productive organization and material and technical support of production;
5. Emergence of new markets.

In addition, he used the concept of innovation and interpreted it as a change, the purpose of which is to introduce and use new types of consumer goods, new production and means of transport in the form of new production organization.

Not all inventions become innovations. Innovations are inventions that bring profit and satisfy market demand. In other words, thanks to science, an idea that can be implemented appears, and the next step is the commercialization of this idea, which turns the invention into an innovation, which brings income. It says: If science is the process of turning money into knowledge, innovation is the process of turning knowledge into money with added value. Kondratiev justified the idea that economic cycles (waves) have different lengths: long - 48-55 years, medium - 7-11 years and short - 3-3.5 years. His most important contribution is related to the study of long waves. To substantiate his theory, he analyzed a large amount of factual material covering the four most developed countries - Great Britain, France, Germany and the United States. The studies conducted were related to the dynamics of prices, interest rates, wages, foreign trade volume and the dynamics of basic industrial goods. The time period under analysis was extended to 140 years. Research has confirmed the existence of long waves and science, its discoveries, the uneven development of science and technology, innovations, etc. have been noted as one of the reasons (Kondratiev N. (1925))⁴. Kondratiev discovered empirical patterns associated with long waves. Before the development of the wave and at its beginning, deep changes occur in the economic life of society associated with important changes in technology (important technological discoveries and inventions took place). He considered scientific and technical innovations to be the main factor. Innovation creates excitement by changing the economic environment from its trend to an upward trend. Kondratiev also showed that innovations are unevenly distributed over time. They appear in groups or, in modern language, clusters. Therefore, in the study of Kondratiev, we can find one of the first examples of the use of the cluster approach. Currently, Kondratiev's recommendations can be used in the development of innovative

³ Иванов М.А., Гужина Г.Н. Особенности управления рисками в рыночных условиях//Вестник Российского государственного аграрного заочного университета.

⁴ Назаршоев Н.М., Гужина Г.Н., Гужин А.А., Ежкова В.Г. Стратегия развития бизнеса как инструмент управления конкурентоспособностью// Инновации и инвестиции

strategies.[4] The role of technological cycles is manifested in the development of the economy and society, which, on the one hand, increases the mass of capital production, and also increases its technological level. On the other hand, the skill level of the workforce and management will increase due to improved education and skills. Over time, with the achievement of a high technological level of production, the innovative characteristics of the labor force are the characteristics that grow the fastest, because the skilled labor force not only absorbs new technologies faster and uses them more efficiently, but also creates these technologies in production.

Schumpeter J.A. in his work "Business Cycles" (1939) he combined N. Kondratiev's long wave theory with his theory of innovation, and as a result developed the initial cyclical theory of development⁵. In his opinion, the cyclical development of the economy is mainly related to the internal mechanism of the system and it is an innovative process.

Research Methodology

The article uses methods of scientific abstraction, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction. The information of this research was obtained from official sources, and the study of innovative entrepreneurship was achieved based on the comparative analysis of the scientific-theoretical views of well-known economists on the role of innovations in the development of the economy, the generalization of foreign experiences and the results obtained on the achievements made in our country.

Analysis and Results

If we compare the innovative processes in our country with the situation in developed countries, now the developed countries of the world have been under the influence of the innovative economy and the fifth technological cycle (long wave) for more than 15 years. What should countries do that are only able to enter the fifth wave, and even beyond?

Will they reach these countries first of all by starting their scientific research in new high-tech directions? Apparently, this is very problematic. However, this is an obstacle for these countries, especially in our country, to use the technologies created by other countries and to use them in the development of their economy, to try to surpass the developed countries by creating as many conditions as possible for foreign investments to enter the country. does not Some time ago, this experiment was carried out in Japan, South Korea and other countries. In fact, the opportunities provided by innovation and the positive aspects of globalization were first of all captured by South-East Asian countries (often called "tigers"), such as South Korea, Taiwan, Hong Kong, Singapore, as well as the Celts. The "tiger" is Ireland, one of the leaders in the field of innovation. These countries can serve as a paradigm for Uzbekistan, because our country, with its small market, poor traditional resources, can only develop successfully if it chooses an innovative path using its competitive unique non-traditional resources.

The competitiveness of the country develops on the basis of the competitiveness of individual enterprises. Every business uses its own strategy to achieve competitive advantage. However, the evolution and development of successful companies will be similar in nature as companies create

⁵ Назаршоев Н.М., Гужина Г.Н., Гужин А.А., Ежкова В.Г. Стратегия развития бизнеса как инструмент управления конкурентоспособностью// Инновации и инвестиции

competitive advantages based on innovation. The reason for the weakness of innovative processes in the enterprises of our country is the influence of the following factors: The competitiveness of the country develops on the basis of the competitiveness of individual enterprises. Every business uses its own strategy to achieve competitive advantage. However, the evolution and development of successful companies will be similar in nature as companies create competitive advantages based on innovation. The reason for the weakness of innovative processes in the enterprises of our country is due to the influence of the following factors:

- the small number of scientists working in industry, as well as the low percentage of scientists and researchers in the workforce;
- not to enter the field of high technology patenting;
- weak cooperation between the production sector and universities;
- relative failure of innovation promotion and activity of entrepreneurship support mechanisms;
- complex procedures for starting a business; insufficient quality of technological education.

It is also worth noting the concept of the so-called "European innovation paradox" from the world experience - on the one hand, when assessing the share of investments in education and science in the GDP, as well as the percentage of highly educated people in the population in most countries of the European Union, the USA or even better than Japan. Europe also surpasses them in terms of indicators of scientific potential (for example, the number of Nobel laureates, SCI publications, number of scientists with doctoral degrees). Nevertheless, the productivity of the economy in the European Union is twice as low as that of the United States, and its trade balance with the United States is negative. Students from different parts of the world are trying to study in higher educational institutions of the USA. The United States itself is a very successful country in the use of innovation, commercializing knowledge created not only in its own country, but also around the world. The best specialists in the field of higher education and research (project managers, researchers, highly educated technology specialists) move to the USA. Europe is betting on training in US companies and education in higher education institutions. According to these and similar facts, the term "European innovation paradox" also appeared. From the above, we can conclude that innovation is the main driving force. Thus, innovation provides an opportunity to develop a competitive economy. In recent years, not only economists, but also politicians have understood this. In order to achieve the main goals, it is necessary to allocate 3% of the gross domestic product to research and development, increase the employment rate to 70%, reduce bureaucracy, eliminate corruption, and encourage entrepreneurship. If these problems are solved, our country's economy will achieve great success in innovative development. It is envisaged to allocate funds from state budgets for scientific research and innovation and increase the volume of its provision. In particular, three main directions are given priority:

- investment in education and formation and increase of intellectual property;
- strengthening competitiveness in industry and service sector;
- establishment of monocenters in the labor market.

It can be seen that in all the cases mentioned above, increasing competitiveness is related to innovation. It is necessary to create a coordinated and common space for conducting research and expanding knowledge for effective exchange of knowledge between countries and individual

enterprises. It is not only about supporting research and development of technologies and protection of intellectual property rights, but also about ensuring the spread and diffusion of innovations, because where innovations are introduced, the results are as expected.

Conclusions and Suggestions

In conclusion, in modern enterprises engaged in innovative entrepreneurship and using foreign experience in the production process, innovations were introduced, wages increased by 2-3 times, productivity increased by 2 times compared to traditional enterprises, especially the fact that the quality of life and well-being of working employees is ensured compared to before, shows the positive aspects of today's innovative economic reforms. But along with the progress being made, there are also problems to be solved. In particular:

- that our entrepreneurs do not have sufficient skills in business management;
- inability of employees to quickly absorb news;
- they cannot adequately assess internal and external risks, the need for innovation, and their position in the world market;
- not enough attention is paid to the development of enterprises, increase of competitiveness;
- there are many problems in the organization of the business environment and the development of the innovation promotion structure.

We consider the following proposals and recommendations to be appropriate in solving these problems:

- the role of private business in the process of funding scientific research should be increased, which will give an incentive to increase the efficiency of investments in research and development;
- it is necessary to increase the level of investments necessary for innovation and strengthen competition;
- It is necessary to support the marketing search system for developments, which is the main element of stimulating innovation and foreign patenting of scientific developments created in Uzbekistan.

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USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN CHEMISTRY EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Annotation

In this article the recommendations on the use of interactive methods in educational system. As the main factors of modernization of education innovative approaches are enlightened.

Keywords: Innovation, interactive methods, education, teaching chemistry, methods of traditional and non-traditional teaching, pedagogical innovation

INTRODUCTION

As in all fields, one of the urgent tasks is to achieve educational efficiency by introducing innovative technologies into the educational system, to further improve the quality of educational work, to train competitive personnel, and to create creativity in future specialists.

All efforts related to education are the joint mental and physical work, cooperative or independent work, activity of students, in the example of educators, educators, disseminators of knowledge, other officials, in short, students who are learning, educated, in general, students with teachers and trainers and creative thinking are multifaceted and complex processes.

Issues of increasing the efficiency of lessons and extracurricular activities are inextricably linked with the establishment of the educational process on a scientific basis and the practical application of modern pedagogical technologies. The main goal of organizing innovative activities in educational institutions, introducing innovations and new approaches to educational processes is to ensure the consistency of cooperation between teachers and students and to establish it in a goal-oriented manner on the basis of a clear plan. In this work, a careful solution of pedagogic-psychological and organizational issues is required. It should be noted that the participants of the pedagogical innovation must thoroughly acquire methodological, psychological, pedagogical, technological knowledge about the occurrence, manifestation of innovations and the laws of their management process. Otherwise, pedagogical innovations will not produce effective results.

In our opinion, the effectiveness of the innovative processes to be introduced into the educational system and the responsibility for fulfilling the requirements of the "National Personnel Training Program" depend on the conditions for the development and implementation of pedagogical innovations, on the appropriate, rational and integrated use of traditional and modern methods of education. In some cases, there are cases of abandonment of traditional methods that are effective. It is perceived as putting innovations against the teaching methodology that has been tested in experience and has been giving positive results. Therefore, it would be better if the positive experiences of the traditional education system were combined with innovations.

Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the activities of teachers and students in the pedagogical process, and require the use of interactive methods in its implementation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Interactive methods are based on the activity of each student participating in the educational process, free and independent thinking. When using these methods, learning becomes an interesting activity for the student. When interactive methods are used, students acquire the skills and abilities to work independently with the help and cooperation of the teacher. Students acquire new knowledge on the basis of scientific research, research, experiments. The principle of gaining knowledge through science is followed. Participants of the educational process work in small groups. Assignments are not given to individual students, but to all members of a small group. Each member of micro groups tries to contribute to the task. This situation forms a sense of community among students and increases their initiative.

The main form of organizing the teaching process is the lesson. Currently, various non-traditional forms of lessons are introduced. Such classes serve to develop the student's creative ability, strengthen his intellectual potential, expand his scientific worldview, and develop the skills and abilities to quickly and fully accept every new thing. The use of innovative technologies in the course of the lesson arouses interest in scientific research in students, develops creativity and creativity. As a result, acquired knowledge, skills and abilities are applied in practical activities, the quality of learning increases. For this, the teacher should be skilled and properly plan the lesson depending on the content of the topics, and achieve active and conscious work of all students during the training.

For example, when teaching the topic of Calcium and its compounds, the chemical properties of calcium are studied using the "Fish skeleton" method in the following way.

Handouts in A4 format will be distributed to small groups based on the "Fish skeleton" method. The groups work out the task within the specified time and present the group work.

Assignment to groups. Write the equation for the reaction of aluminum with the given substances and the formulas of the compounds formed on the bottom of the fish skeleton.

Pinboard (from English: pin- fixing, board - writing board) consists of adapting the methods of discussion or educational conversation with a practical method.

Students are divided into 3 groups. The teacher checks the homework with the students using the "Pinboard" method. For this purpose, cards with the name of oxide, base, acid, salt, formula and name in English are distributed to the groups. Students arrange the cards

Vodorod oksid (suv)	Hydrogen oxide (water)	H_2O
Marganes (VII) oksid	Marganese oxide	Mn_2O_7
Azot (IV) oksid	Nitrogen oxide	NO_2

The teacher shows the table with the correct answers. Groups check their work. The teacher summarizes the knowledge about the classification of complex substances.

Conceptual table It provides a comparison of two or more aspects of the phenomenon, concept, and ideas under study.

Develops the skills of systematic thinking, structuring and systematization of information

They get acquainted with the conceptual table of rules. They identify the comparable, distinguish the characteristics according to the comparisons.

They fill in the conceptual table individually or in small groups.

- Comparable in length (opinions, theories) are placed;
- Various descriptions are written for the bed comparison.

Presentation of work results

For example, when teaching the topic "Alkaline earth metals" in the course of inorganic chemistry, a new topic can be opened using the conceptual table method.

Alkaline earth metals	Meeting in nature	Taken	Physical properties	Chemical properties	Usage
Magnesium Mg					
Calcium Ca					

A modern teacher should pay special attention to the formation of students as well-rounded individuals. Therefore, it is one of the main problems to develop their oral speech, to ensure interdisciplinary communication, and to develop the ability to express their thoughts. The Cinquain method works well in solving this problem.

Cinquain is derived from French -cinquains, English -cinquain, and means 5 lines. Cinquain is a non-rhymed poem that helps to synthesize (bring together) information, in which information about the studied concept (phenomenon, event, topic) is collected and expressed by the reader's words in different versions and from different points of view. Syntax is an essential skill for expressing complex ideas, intuitions, and feelings in just a few words. The process of creating a cinquain helps to better understand the topic.

Rules for creating a cinquain:

Line 1: The topic is expressed in one word (usually a noun is chosen)

Line 2: The subject is expressed by two adjectives (2 adjectives are written)

Line 3: Three words describe the action within the topic. (write 3 verbs or adverbs)

Line 4: A four-word opinion is written that represents the attitude towards the topic (a sentence of 4 words is written)

Line 5: Write one word that repeats the essence of the topic and is close to it in meaning (write a synonym for the topic)

Examples of the following Cinquains on the subject of "Chlorine":

Chlorine – Cl₂
Yellow-green gas
It is poisonous, it dissolves, it catches.
It is used as a disinfectant.
Halogen

Chlorine – Cl₂
Oxidizing, reducing
It dissolves, poisons, evaporates.
Chlorine cannot be smelled.
Gas

Because the teacher is the main executor of the educational reform. In this case, it is important to train each teacher to learn, process and apply a large amount of information in a short period of time. The use of modern information technology, including computers, along with traditional methods of teaching, helps the teacher to solve it. The use of a computer in the lesson makes the teaching process interesting and allows an individual approach to each student.

First of all, it will be possible to convey a lot of knowledge, facts and information to students through the wide possibilities of information and communication technologies. Second, the full implementation of the teacher's innovative plans, ideas and thoughts is easy and efficient. Such processes are especially important in chemistry education.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The interactive methods mentioned above are widely used in the process of teaching chemistry in the family education system and positive results are being achieved.

Interactive methods, which are the most important structural element of interactive learning, provide a certain level of efficiency in the implementation of educational goals. Most importantly, when choosing interactive methods, educators should pay attention to the topic, problem, or problem to be solved.

CONCLUSIONS

We believe that teaching students to successfully use interactive methods in their practical activities in the future is one of the main tasks of ensuring consistency and continuity in the higher education system.

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GENESIS- BOTH DOT, END - ALSO DOT OR THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DOT IN FINE ARTS CLASSES

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Abstract

This article discusses the point, its role in life, and the processes of using it in the field of science. In visual art classes, information was given about the importance of the dot, that the dot is not only the end, but also the beginning.

Keywords; End, Genesis, Dots, Pointillism, Impressionism, Universe, Expanse, Projection, Points. Records. Playdots. Spots

The point is how much we know or understand about it. In simple words, when we say the point, the point at the end of the sentence suddenly comes to our mind. In fact, it has enough appearances to understand it in different ways, and we face it in every aspect of our life. lick

Allah created this world full of wisdom. A thinking person can take lessons from whatever he wants. Even from a point that we often overlook.

The period is one of the most widely used and oldest punctuation marks; In the 11th century, it appeared as a writing symbol in Arabic texts. Until the 19th century, its function and use was completely different from that of the present punctuation mark.

The holy book of our religion, the Holy Qur'an, was revealed in Arabic, the best of languages. Arabic writing is also distinguished from other writings by its unique forms. It's those dots that make up the letters! These dots are more numerous than all the letters in the Holy Qur'an.

In modern Uzbek spelling, the dot is used in the following places: at the end of sentences; That's why the full stop is always considered as the end. The question arises whether it really is the same... Of course, we end a whole work with a full stop, starting from a simple sentence. This is a clear thing. There are words and phrases reminding of the end, such as "put", "concentrated to one point", and even "I will put an end to your life".

Have you ever imagined the universe? Of course, we cannot imagine the infinite universe, and it is no exaggeration to say that in this universe we are actually a particle like a point. We can imagine that the universe consists of a particle, more precisely, a set of points. Then we can find a reason to say that the point is not only the end, but also the beginning. Imagine that you are in space, moving away from our beloved motherland, and you feel that it is turning into a point as it moves away from you. I have a question...why do objects, even if they are of different shapes, become points instead of other shapes as they move away?

Oh, if I knew how wide this world is?

Oh, if I knew that this world is at one point?

This thought always amazes me. It would not be wrong to say that the Creator, the great God, started everything from a point.

An example of this: be it a person, be it houses or even be it the globe, which is considered wide for us, this situation will be repeated. This process itself shows us the distance from point to point, that is, the beginning and the end. Therefore, the point is not only the completion, but also the beginning of the process. This can be seen on the scale of a simple herb or plant. In simple words, a seed the point falls there and moves, goes through a certain process and produces a seed, the seed remains and ends by itself.

The dot is interesting because it is neither a number nor a letter, nor does it have a beautiful "figure". Simple and mysterious. But if you establish a relationship with her, she will definitely show her beauty and charm.

Mathematics, the father of exact sciences, was able to give measurements and value to objects, from huge numbers, sizes and quantities to tiny particles. But even with these capabilities, we could not measure the value of the point we know! Even if it does not have the same amount as numbers, it is possible to subtract huge numbers from the existing "bisot" at the same time!

Unlike other sciences, the science that can reform the point the most is geometry and, more precisely, the science of drawing geometry.

A point is one of the basic concepts of geometry. A point is usually taken as one of the initial concepts in a consistent description of geometry. In modern mathematics, different elements that make up different spaces are called Points. (For example, in i -dimensional Euclidean space, an ordered set formed by i -th numbers is called a Point).

In geometry, a circle is defined as follows: "A set of points lying at the same distance from the center is called a circle." In fact, a circle can also be said to be larger than a point. This is a simple example of how scientists have proved that the point is the beginning. That is why the science of drawing geometry first of all starts with the analysis of the point. Projection of a point, its coordinates, distance from a point to a plane, traces of a point, perspective of a point and hakoza. You think that this analysis is enough for one point. But other sciences are starting their sciences from the same beginning..? What did the artists achieve in this regard?

Artists are able to draw imaginary impressions, not only visible to the naked eye, but also invisible to us. Currently, such "creativity" is claimed by techniques. So, what are those works of art made of? What are its bricks? Yes, surely these are not the points we consider trivial? Involuntarily, the artist who takes a pencil in his hand first puts a dot on the white paper, just like a drop of paint first the dot and then it spreads around. Dots are widely used in industrial design and art decoration. Fabrics with dot pattern are not left out of the tradition. Especially in mobile games, dots are widely used. A free mobile game produced by Betaworks and developed by American studio Playdots, Inc. It is for iOS Released on April 30, 2013 and for Android on August 15, 2013.

So, why is the point so valued? What quality makes him such a status? The only reason for this is that, like other letters, the dot didn't show off its size, it didn't take revenge on the value like numbers, it didn't disturb the world like sounds, it kept silent, it knew its place. Even though he knew that the key to all the secrets of the universe was his, he continued on his way with humility, simplicity, and modesty. It is because of this nobleness that people of creativity often turned to him, and the phrase "base point" is proof of our opinion.

Working with dots in painting was first evident in the Impressionism trend.

Release of impressionism

Impressionism in the 1860s Claude Monet, Alfred Sisley and A group of artists including Pierre-Auguste Renoir *plein air* picture together. The basis of Impressionism is painting based on impressions, and they retreated from the realistic depiction method that had existed until

that time. The movement made its official debut in 1874 Felix Nadar Demonstration at a show held by the Paris Photography Studio. This exhibition was an alternative to the salon of the Academy of Beaux-Arts in Paris, which had been the official exhibition and controller of world art standards since 1667.

American John Rand never joined their ranks as a well-known artist, but as an artist living in London in 1841 he developed a device that would revolutionize the art world: the paint in a tube. His ingenious new technology offered easily portable, premixed paint and allowed artists to take their process outdoors. Rand's technological leap gave the Impressionists' work a spontaneous and haphazard quality. Over time, other artists joined the practice and their research moved from closed studios to open cafes where they met regularly to discuss their ideas.

Pointillism is a branch of Impressionism. Pointillism, also known as neo-impressionism, was born in 1886 when Georges Seurat exhibited his "Sunday afternoon on the island of La Grande Jatte" and declared the original movement outdated. Seurat's style is small color defined by points that appear separate when viewed closely, but blend into a unified image when the viewer pulls back. Seurat developed this style with the painter Paul Signac. Camille le Pissarro, long an important figure in the movement, joined the Neo-Impressionists in his later years because of his passion for optics, but it was not well received by the public. His son Lucien spent more time as part of the Neo-Impressionists, although he was not as well known as his father.[1]

<https://www.history.com/topics/art-history/impressionism>

Neo-impressionism may not have set itself the goal of working with dots, but we can say that this turn in the creation of works revealed the secrets of working with colors in painting. If we observe the impressionist trends in the works of P. Benkov, who created at the beginning of the 20th century, we can clearly see the pointillist style in the works of artist Dilyus Mirsalimov. If we look at the work of the skilled artist Akmal Nur, we will witness that the essence of the mystery is in the dots, and the compositional solution is based on the dots. In order to achieve such perfection, the creator must be able to make a philosophical observation. Simplicity and imagination, detail, philosophy of life are very skillfully described in the following works.

The use of dots in fine art is almost given, and I think that it is a sufficient number of dots to be used effectively. In the program of the first step of preschool education, the first practical work started very correctly for the visual arts classes. But in the school fine art textbooks, only the 7th grade fine art textbook has the pointillist style. In the same 7th grade, through the subject of pointillist landscape work, we came up with the idea of how we use the initial points. Because of this, the student, who is more skilled in coloring than fine art, was able to draw a wonderful picture using points.

Why should we start the 1st grade art lesson with drawing lines?! Instead of it, we can introduce the topic of creating color spots in watercolor. Or in practical art, if point methods were used in the initial training, the efficiency of practical work would be much increased. Suppose you want to use a brush. dip it in any color of watercolor paint and mix it with water on a palette and carefully put the finished mixture on the paper; - what would you do? You can try this experiment on a beginner student or student who works with watercolors. He definitely makes a point. This protects him from making a mistake. Based on what we said at the beginning, he took a step towards the beginning. These points can easily be expanded or circled to form a straight line, which we know as the starting point. It should also be taken into account that the watercolor technique prefers to apply more color spots than the brush (line) method. If you determine the color and put it on the paper correctly, it will not damage the integrity of the paper and the cleanliness of the work.

Our goal is that in order to effectively organize visual arts classes, it is necessary to pay close attention to the way in which each type should be started. will bring. Of course, I will put a dot at the end of my words to say that I will be happy if my views of experience affect someone like a small dot... this is the end for now...

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INFLUENCE OF FEEDING IN DIFFERENT WAYS ON THE MASS OF SILKWORM AND COCOONS

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Abstract

In silkworm rearing in Uzbekistan, one of the main problems is the maintenance of a hygrothermal regime. Scientific research has been carried out to create optimal air temperature and relative humidity for rearing hybrid silkworms from the 1st instar to the 5th instar. In the experiments, the silkworms were fed in two different experiments and in the same comparative method. In silkworm rearing, the use of fabric and polyethylene film to retain humidity in a special device has been found to save mulberry leaf consumption by 15,3-18,7%, and to shorten the worm cycle by 2,7-4,0 days and due to maintaining the hygrothermal regime, a significant increase in silkworm growth and weight was observed.

Keywords: silkworm, silk, mulberry leaves, temperature, humidity, cocoon.

Аннотация

Ўзбекистон шароитида ипак қуртини боқишда гиротермик режимни сақлаш асосий муаммолардан бири бўлиб ҳисобланади. Парваришланаётган дурагай қуртларга 1-ёшдан 5-ёшгача бўлган даврда оптимал ҳаво ҳарорати ва нисбий намликни яратиш бериш борасида илмий ишлар олиб борилди. Тажрибаларда икки хил тажриба ва бир хил қиёсловчи усулда қурт боқилди. Қурт боқишда махсус мосламада намликни сақлаш учун мато ва полиэтилен плёнкадан фойдаланиш тут барги сарфини 15,3-18,7% га иқтисод қилиши, қуртлик даврини 2,7-4,0 кунга қисқартириши исботланди ва гиротермик режимни доимий сақлаш ҳисобига, қуртларни ўсиб ривожланишида ва қурт вазнида сезиларли даражада ўсиш кузатилди.

Калит сўзлар: тут ипак қурти, ипак, тут барги, ҳарорат, намлик, пилла.

Аннотация

В шелководстве Узбекистана одной из основных проблем является поддержание влаготермического режима. Проведены научные исследования по созданию оптимальной температуры воздуха и относительной влажности для выращивания гибридных тутовых шелкопрядов с 1-го по 5-й возраст. В опытах шелковичных червей кормили в двух разных опытах и одним и тем же сравнительным методом. Установлено, что при выращивании тутового шелкопряда использование ткани и полиэтиленовой пленки для сохранения влажности в специальном устройстве позволяет сэкономить расход листьев тутового дерева

на 15,3-18,7%, сократить цикл червей на 2,7-4,0 дня и за счет поддержания влаготермического режима. , наблюдалось значительное увеличение роста и массы тутового шелкопряда.

Ключевые слова: тутовый шелкопряд, шелк, тутовый лист, температура, влажность, кокон

Introduction

Certain successes have been achieved in the production and processing of cocoons in our republic, the creation of high-yielding varieties and industrial hybrids adapted to our different regions, as well as highly nutritious mulberry varieties. However, the development and scientific justification of methods for the proper storage of domestic and foreign silk ribbons, providing them with a constant and relative humidity in the specific dry climate of Uzbekistan is given little attention.

Currently, more than 20 countries of the world are engaged in the processing of silk and the production of finished silk fabrics, the main share of cultivated cocoon raw materials belongs to the People's Republic of China. Demand for cocoon raw materials, which is a source of natural silk, is increasing on the world silk market. The main demand of the leading industrial complexes for the production of products from silk is focused on thin silk carpets. In the period of modern market relations, the competitiveness of products for export on the world market is a priority for any industry. In the silk industry, the high quality of silk is directly related to the quality of the cocoon and its technological features. To improve the quality of raw silk, in first of all, it is necessary to create breeds and hybrids that produce high-quality silk, and then, of course, it is necessary to use innovative technologies that have a scientific basis.

While scientists in the field of sericulture have done a lot of research on shortening silkworm rearing period and producing abundant and quality cocoons, the advanced cocoon producers have also introduced a number of innovations into silkworm rearing processes in their practical experiments. As a result, several methods have been developed in silkworm rearing, such as simple method, intensive method and the method of silkworm breeding at changeable temperature, as well as an improved method. Today, an improved intensive method is being used widely. For this, it is required the temperature to be 26-27 0C and relative humidity to be 65-75% in the 1st, 2nd and 3rd instars of silkworm, in the 4th instar to be 25-26 0C, in the 5th instar 24-25 0C, while in cocooning stage 25 0C, with humidity 60-65 percent (Akhmedov, 2014). In the result of rearing silkworm under this improved intensive rearing method, larva stage of reared silkworms reduced by 1-1,5 days, cocoon yield, mean weight of cocoon and silk-fiber yield increased by 4-5 percent.

In this regard, in countries with developed cocoons, manual labor is gradually being abandoned. The role of innovative technologies in the era of silkworm care is of great importance. Based on this, the mechanization of sericulture and the use of innovative techniques and technologies during the fattening period of worms make it possible to grow high-quality raw materials under production conditions and silk fibre.

The amount of the food given to the silkworm, eaten and digested by the worm body depends on the amount of water in the leaf, the moisture and freshness of the leaf. In cocoonery where the silkworms are reared, when the temperature is 25-270C, the mulberry leaves lose freshness within 1,5 hours and get dried. Young larva of silkworm consume the leaves slower than the larva of older instar. In the rearing of young larva, the care under polyethylene film is much more effective. As a result of this, if

the larva are fed at regular intervals, i.e 3 times a day with chopped leaves, the growth of worms is accelerated and the freshness of mulberry leaves remains more, getting less dried. The most part of the given feed, that is mulberry leaves are saved to be wasted. It was found that when a mulberry silkworm is fed in a simple way, 100-1200 kgs of leaves are consumed per box of worms, and when fed under film, an average of 750-800 kgs of food is consumed per box of worms (Khomidy et al. 2004).

When silkworms are reared under ordinary conditions, the moisture of the mulberry leaf quickly decreases and begins to dry out. By considering the worm's need for humidity, it has been suggested that young larva can be fed 4-5 times a day instead of 9-10 times a day if they are fed under a damp sheet/blanket cover or polyethylene film (Akhmedov, 2014).

Mulberry silkworms need to be fed on special shelves to protect them from pests and floor (ground) moisture. Folding shelves and permanent stillages (racks) are used to rear the silkworm of all instars. They can be installed vertically in 2,3,4 and 8-10 layers (Akhmedov, 2014).

In the method that is used in India, it is recommended to rear mulberry silkworm larvae in young and adult instars in special boxes measuring 2 x 3 m (Bharat and Satish, 2014). In the rearing process of the silkworm in these stillages the work can be accelerated and get easier. For feeding and thinning the silkworm larva, it has been noted that the time is saved by 23 percent to 60 percent. Furthermore, the damage that can be caused to larva reared in these stillages while changing their place, or transferring somewhere has been found to be decreased.

At the stage of cocooning of silkworm, the quality of cocoon, its calibre, i.e large or small sizes, shape, weight, shell mass, silkiness, cocoon hardness and technological indicators not only depend on silkworm breed, but also on cocooning condition too (Akhmedov and Murodov, 2004; Akhmedov, 2014). The authors reported that the temperature, humidity and light in cocooning condition, as well as the amount and quality of mulberry leaves may affect considerably to cocooning.

The cost of growing mulberry silkworm and producing cocoon products is increasing. This is due to the fact that as a result of the decline in the quality of the cocoons grown, the fineness of the silk fiber is not at the level required by world standards. That is, non-recommended materials for silkworm rearing are used in the production process. It leads to defective formation of cocoons which are double, spotted and have a rack trace. The use of the proposed artificial trays of polyethylene, cardboard and other materials has been proven to improve the quality and technological performance of cocoons (Lavrentyev, 1973; Mirzakhodjaev et al., 2009).

Research materials and methods

Many factors influence the growth and development of the silkworm and the production of high-quality cocoons. These include the quantity and quality of feed, hydrothermal conditions, and agricultural practices. All activities and techniques are aimed at providing the worms with a sufficient amount of high-quality, moist mulberry leaves. It is also important to maintain a constant temperature air and the level of relative humidity. Many scientists have conducted a number of scientific studies on the effect of temperature and humidity levels, the quantity and quality of food on the silkworm. The results of the studies provide scientifically sound recommendations. However, in the theory and practice of sericulture, the development of methods for maintaining a constant optimal hygrothermal regime and its scientific justification is a topical issue.

Research Results and their Discussion

At the next stage of our research work, the effect of feeding worms under wet cloth and film on the growth of worms, the mass of worms and the amount of gana produced during the feeding period was studied. Tables 3.5.1-3.5.4 indicate the number of worms, the number of worms remaining in the worm (stunted) and the weight of 100 worms and 1 worm on the 7 th day of V-age by 5 different ways of feeding the worms.

Table-1 Litter and caterpillar weights for different rearing methods (2018 y.)

Nº	Feeding method	Manure quantity gr	Number of caterpillar under	Weight of 100 of caterpillar on the 7th day of age V, gr	Weight of 1 caterpillar on the 7th day of age V, gr
1	With the sheet open	1103	26	364,38	3,64
2	With the film open	976	19	367,41	3,67
3	With the sheet closed	1218	23	378,35	3,78
4	With the film closed	1004	21	391,89	3,91
5	In a simple way (comparator)	1361	27	323,76	3,23

Table-2 Litter and caterpillar weights for different rearing methods (2019 y.)

Nº	Feeding method	Manure quantity gr	Number of caterpillar under	Weight of 100 of caterpillar on the 7th day of age V, gr	Weight of 1 caterpillar on the 7th day of age V, gr
1	With the sheet open	1171	31	362,21	3,62
2	With the film open	1005	27	371,38	3,71
3	With the sheet closed	1108	29	381,12	3,81
4	With the film closed	1226	27	396,43	3,96
5	In a simple way (comparator)	1415	38	323,76	3,23

Table-3 Litter and caterpillar weights for different rearing methods (2020 y.)

Nº	Feeding method	Manure quantity gr	Number of caterpillar under	Weight of 100 of caterpillar on the 7th day of age V, gr	Weight of 1 caterpillar on the 7th day of age V, gr
1	With the sheet open	972	28	386,21	3,86
2	With the film open	1072	15	393,61	3,98
3	With the sheet closed	1000	23	429,12	4,29
4	With the film closed	986	31	438,91	4,38
5	In a simple way (comparator)	1634	38	364,3	3,64

**Table-4 Litter and caterpillar weights for different rearing methods
(average indicators for 2018-2020)**

Nº	Feeding method	Manure quantity gr	Number of caterpillar under	Weight of 100 of caterpillar on the 7th day of age V, gr	Weight of 1 caterpillar on the 7th day of age V, gr
1	With the sheet open	1082*±58,4	28,3±1,45	370,9±7,66	3,71±0,08
2	With the film open	1017,6±28,4	20,3±3,53	377,5±8,15	3,79±0,10
3	With the sheet closed	1108,7±62,9	25,0±2,0	396,2±16,5	3,96±0,17
4	With the film closed	1072±77,2	26,3±2,91	409,1±14,9	4,09±0,15
5	In a simple way (comparator)	1470±83,5	34,3±3,67	337,3±13,5	3,37±0,14

From the figures in tables 1-4 it can be seen that all indicators are higher when feeding worms under cloth and film.).Next, you can specify the method of keeping the worms in the closed state of the film and the methods of feeding the beds in the open state (1072 g; 1082 g). For comparison, with a simple method, 1470 g was obtained, that is, the largest residue.

The effectiveness of the method of feeding worms can also be assessed by the number of worms remaining in the seeds (lagging behind in development). The more correctly agrotechnical measures are selected and applied, the more uniform the growth and development of worms, the less the number of worms lagging behind in development. In our experiments, the number of worms was determined remaining in the ganache. According to the results, the smallest number of worms in the grain was observed with the film method of feeding (20.3 pcs.), while in other variants of the experiment it was found that 25.0-28.3 worms remained in development. .The number of remaining helminths was significantly higher (34.3 units) with normal care.

The weight of the silkworm is a key factor in the production of a high-quality, heavy cocoon. Only when worms are provided with sufficient and nutritious nutrition, the mass of worms and, accordingly, the biosynthesis of a sufficient amount of silk fluid in the silk gland increases. Therefore, we determined the mass of worms with different feeding methods at the last stage of the 5th century .On the 7th day, out of 100 worms, the heaviest worms by weight were obtained with a closed version of feeding under a film (409.12 g). In other options, this figure was 370.9-396.2 g. significantly less (337.3 g). Based on the individual weight of the worms, it was observed that in the closed state under the film, the worms gained 0.72 g in weight compared to the control.

The results discussed above show that the method of feeding worms under full film and wet cloth is effective and can be recommended for production.

The mass of the cocoon is the most important indicator in determining the yield of a cocoon from 1 box of silkworm. The mass of the cocoon depends primarily on the breed and hybrid of the silkworm, and then on the quantity and quality of the feed. Here, the amount of natural moisture in the feed and how much it is retained, is also one of the factors on the basis of which we analyzed the mass of cocoons, mass of the shell, silkiness and productivity of cocoons obtained in the course of our experiments.

Table-5
Cocoon performance in different methods and sets (average for 2018-2020)

№	Method of feeding and type of bunch	Percentage of cocoon $\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}, \%$	Weight of cocoon $\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}, \text{r}$	Weight of shell $\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}, \text{r}$	Neto weight of cocoons $\bar{X} \pm S\bar{x}, \text{r}$
1	Accumulative bunches placed on caterpillar raised under sheets at a young age (Mulberry shoot)	87,7 ± 0,67	1,51 ± 0,12	0,331 ± 0,03	914,6 ± 184,01
2	Bunches with yachts placed, on caterpillar fed under a film (Mulberry shoot)	87,7 ± 0,90	1,54 ± 0,16	0,329 ± 0,03	934,7 ± 0,82
3	Folded bunches, placed in caterpillar, which are fed under sheet in their young and older years (cardboard)	86,7 ± 0,88	1,50 ± 0,11	0,330 ± 0,03	937,2 ± 147,34
4	Under a film placed on caterpillar fed In their young and older years, bunches with yachts, (cardboard)	87,7 ± 0,33	1,55 ± 0,16	0,334 ± 0,04	968,7 ± 194,63
5	Straw bunches placed on caterpillar fed in a simple way (comparator)	82,3 ± 1,20	1,37 ± 0,12	0,287 ± 0,04	818,8 ± 166,33

Before presenting the numerical analysis data in tablitsia 5 it should be noted that in this experiment, along with the method of feeding the worms, in each variant, grouping and bundles of cells of mulberry varieties were used. Straw bales were used in the comparative variant.

A careful study of the three-year results shows that the cocoonness of worms grown under sheets and films was almost the same in all experiments and amounted to 86.7-87.7%. In the comparative variant, this figure was 82.3 percent.

The same trend was observed with an average cocoon weight of 1.50-1.54 g compared to 1.37 g for the comparison. A significant difference in the weight of the cocoon between the control and experimental options is visible (0.329-0.334 g; 0.287 g). The highest level of net the mass of cocoons obtained by the variants was determined by feeding the worms 5 times under a film at a young age and placing a bunch of mulberry cells on them (968.7 g). The same indicator was equal to 818.8 g in the comparative variant, and the cocoon yield was 95.8-149.9 g less than in the experimental variants. All these given details definitely prove the advantage of the method of feeding worms under sheets and film in special hatches

Conclusions

If we consider climatic conditions of Uzbekistan, a sharp change is noted in air temperature and humidity in silkworm rearing seasons. Under such conditions, it is required to create an optimal hygrothermal regime for silkworms in order to grow the maximum cocoon yield. Otherwise, it will not be possible to take full advantage of the genetic potential of industrial hybrids. In this research, mulberry silkworms were reared in three different methods, and the method of rearing silkworm

under a damp cloth and polyethylene film was recommended for optimal silkworm rearing. The data obtained proved that the leaf needed to care for the silkworm could be significantly saved and the temperature and humidity could be kept at a level normal for silkworms by shortening the larva period.

The following conclusions can be drawn from our research for 2018-2020:

- mulberry leaf consumption can be saved by 15,3-18,7% when silkworms are reared under cloth and film;
- as a result of the use of cloth and polyethylene film to retain high humidity, the number of feedings the larva with leaves at 1-5 instars decreased by 81,4-90,0, and the larva period was reduced to 2,7-4,0 days;
- most importantly, as a result of rearing silkworms under the fabric and film, a significant increase in the growth and weight of larva was observed due to the constant maintenance of the hygrothermal regime;
- in the conditions of Uzbekistan in silkworm-breeding farms, it is recommended to rear silkworms under cloth and polyethylene film.

Acknowledgements

This research work of the author was completed in the range of practical project named "Creation of folding cocoon rack and silkworm lifter and the equipments adapted in farms to make them" with number F-A-2018-019 in the sponsorship of the Ministry of Innovative development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

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THE STRATEGY OF FORMING THE FIGHT AGAINST SPIRITUAL THREATS OF THE YOUTH IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN AND THE PROSPECTS OF ITS DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation

The article analyzes socio-philosophical views aimed at protecting the younger generation from various spiritual threats in the development of new Uzbekistan in connection with the education system. The spiritual significance of the reforms in the formation of the worldview of young people, aspects of the fight against spiritual threats associated with the national idea are revealed.

Keywords: spiritual threat, youth, national idea, ideology, strategy, knowledge, faith, legal culture, worldliness, ideological education, information, humanism, culture.

Аннотация

В статье анализируются социально-философские взгляды, направленные на защиту молодого поколения от различных духовных угроз в развитии нового Узбекистана в связи с системой образования. Раскрывается духовное значение реформ по формированию мировоззрения молодежи, аспекты борьбы с духовными угрозами, связанными с национальной идеей.

Ключевые слова: духовная угроза, молодежь, национальная идея, идеология, стратегия, знание, вера, правовая культура, мировоззрение, идеологическое воспитание, информация, гуманизм, культура.

Аннотация

Мақолада янги Ўзбекистоннинг тараққиётида ёш авлодни турли маънавий таҳдидлардан сақлашга қаратилган ижтимоий-фалсафий қарашлар таълим-тарбия тизими билан боғлиқ равишда таҳлил қилинган. Унда ёшлар дунёқарашини шакллантиришга доир ислохотларнинг маънавий аҳамияти, маънавий таҳдидларга қраш курашишнинг миллий ғоя билан боғлиқ жиҳатлари очиб берилган.

Калит сўзлар: маънавий таҳдид, ёшлар, миллий ғоя, мафкура, стратегия, билим, эътиқод, ҳуқуқий маданият, дунёқараш, ғоявий тарбия, ахборот, инсонпарварлик, маданият.

The material and moral condition of pedagogues in the field of education has been radically improved in our country in recent years, and modern technologies for improving the quality of education are being introduced.

Education and training cannot be separated from each other, these two stages are harmonious, organized on a continuous basis, polite, highly spiritual with moral qualities, at the same time knowledgeable, intelligent, mentally and physically healthy, with a broad outlook and thinking, a modern profession. He cultivates patriotic young people who own –craft.

Scientific- technological-reformation of youth education in Uzbekistan is carried out on a modern basis, based on scientific- based basic competencies. requires formation on the basis of qualities.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his greeting to our people on the occasion of the 28th anniversary of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, emphasized the following: “New Uzbekistan begins at the school threshold”, unprecedented attention is being paid to the fundamental reform of the national education system. A lot of work is being done to develop the fields of science, culture and art, literature, and sports, to increase the efficiency of spiritual and educational activities, and to realize the talents and abilities of young people, especially girls. All this serves to create the foundations of the new era of the Third Renaissance National Development in our country¹.

Today, we must constantly inculcate this idea in the hearts and minds of the population, especially young people. It is known that even in the most developed countries, about 15-20% of the population is educated. In the framework of this system, young people are also instilled with knowledge in the field of ideology. However, this does not eliminate the conclusion that this system occupies an important place in the education of ideas and ideology.

A worldview formed on the basis of a certain idea is a set of knowledge, imagination and perception about it, which is organized and transformed into a coherent conscious system, which helps a person to occupy a worthy place in life and society. The years of youth and adolescence are extremely important in the formation of such a worldview and the strengthening of faith. This period is favorable not only for the formation of worldviews, but also for changing them, if there is a certain system of views. Therefore, it is natural that many ideological influences are mainly aimed at the youth, their hearts and minds. Today, the development of spirituality is becoming more and more important both in the world and in our country. Its development is of practical importance not only for enriching the spiritual and moral potential of our youth in accordance with the requirements of today's rapidly changing times, but also for the economic, socio- philosophical and spiritual-educational development of our country.

“Educational institutions” serve the priorities of the independent development strategy of Uzbekistan, the goals and objectives of the Uzbek people to build a great state, and inculcate the national ideal in the hearts and minds of young people. Therefore, during the years of independence, education and training, science, profession great attention was paid to the fundamental reform of the education systems.

One of the goals of ideological education is to form the character of living with **a sense of responsibility** in young people. Responsibility is the ability of a person to understand what he can do for himself and others, his duty, fully imagining the result of each work and activity. A person who feels civic responsibility, first of all, thinks about the development of the community where he works or the school where he is studying, his neighborhood and the country.

In this regard, **the growth of socio- philosophical and legal culture is of great importance**. This is the direction deepening democratic reforms in our country, serves to develop civil society. With their activities, they serve the realization of the idea of building a democratic society based on the diversity of opinions.

¹Note.: <https://kun.uz/96804041>”We will continue on the path of openness and transparency” - the President congratulated the Uzbek people on the Constitution Day. 07.12.2020.

Increasing the level of knowledge of young people strengthens the scientific- theoretical foundations of ideological education. "The concept of the development of the higher education system until 2030" approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 of October 8, 2019² is a historical document aimed at improving the knowledge and skills of young people. Setting priorities for the systematic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, modern knowledge and high moral Such a concept was adopted in order to raise the process of training highly qualified personnel with moral qualities and independent thinking to a new level in terms of quality, modernization of higher education, development of social sphere and economic networks based on advanced educational technologies. As written in the 2nd chapter of the concept: "Current qualification requirements, curriculum and programs are not focused on the formation of practical skills of graduates in terms of content, the share of non- specialist subjects in curricula remains high; work on personnel training in mutual cooperation with higher education institutions and personnel customers is not effectively established, the participation of employers in the formation of the content of higher education is insufficient; the skills of critical thinking, independent search and analysis of information have not been formed in young people; practical training in production enterprises is not effectively organized, the qualification level of trained specialists does not sufficiently meet the modern requirements of the labor market; Due to the low level of mastery of information and communication technologies of foreign languages and the requirements of their professional skills, van Shishevoi dosviy. Due to the low level of education, personal skills are lagging behind today's requirements.

There is a need to further develop work on respect for values, humanitarianism and high moral ideals, to educate them in the spirit of patriotism, to strengthen their immunity against foreign ideas and ideologies. In order to educate young people in the spirit of patriotism on the basis of humanism and high moral ideas, new modern management methods will be adopted. At this point, we would like to make some suggestions: first, organize additional courses for young people, regardless of their specialty, to acquire new knowledge and learn a trade; secondly, teaching to master information technologies and create skills; thirdly, it is appropriate to conduct interesting educational events and book quizzes in the hostels to meaningfully spend the free time of young people.

Today, in order to modernize the higher education system, a group of experts from foreign countries has developed various recommendations and proposed them for practice. Taking these recommendations into account is of great importance in improving the quality of training of highly educated specialists, and by further expanding the participation of economic sectors and industries, it serves to train highly qualified competitive personnel in the higher education system of the republic. This is based on the prospects and needs of the country's socio- economic development, radical improvement based on the modern achievements of science, culture, technique and technology, establishing close cooperation relations with the world's leading scientific and educational institutions in the field of higher education, advanced educational process introduction of foreign experiences, especially work related to internships and training of promising pedagogues and scientific personnel in leading scientific and educational institutions abroad serves to bring to a higher level. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 20, 2017 PQ-2909 "On

²Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030"<http://lex.uz/docs/4545884>

measures to further develop the higher education system” regarding the modern reform of the higher education system and increasing its efficiency by implementing this task, Uzbekistan from the ears of source. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 27, 2017 No. PQ-3151 “On measures to further and expand the participation of sectors of the economy in improving the quality of training of highly educated specialists”, Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3775 dated June 5, 2018 “Education in higher educational institutions “Decision on additional measures to increase the quality and ensure their active participation in comprehensive reforms implemented in the country” and other important legal documents were adopted. In recent years, the development of the science of modernization of the system of higher and secondary special education in Uzbekistan large- scale work is being carried out on the modernization of the education system, the development of science, and the introduction of modern forms and technologies of teaching. transition to the credit- module system, the task of implementing the work that cannot be delayed was put before the managers of the field in the optimization of social and humanitarian sciences in higher education.

First of all, the provision of increasing the efficiency of the higher education system on the basis of these normative and legal documents depends directly on the professors and young people who are participants of higher education. Young people are taught by professors in various subjects. Social and humanitarian sciences can easily be included among such subjects. Because the widespread involvement of all young people in the teaching of social and humanities in the higher education system serves as a factor in the fight against spiritual threats. Through these subjects, young people will have sufficient knowledge about serious problems specific to society and ways to solve them, history, culture, economy, and the acquired knowledge will be further strengthened. Because social sciences are a set of disciplines related to society and human behavior, including philosophy, economics, linguistics, political science, sociology, history, law, psychology, and cultural studies. By studying these subjects, people have social and personal relations, conditions for their development in a certain place, spiritual threats immunity to fight will appear, personal development skills will appear in young people, ideological foundations and skills will be improved for the realization of the concept “from national recovery to national growth”.

We can cite obstacles such as one- sided development of education, problems in optimizing higher education itself, closedness of state policy as the problems that have arisen in the performance of social humanities during the last quarter of a century. But if a deeper analysis is connected to the specialty, optimization of subjects not in higher education cannot be considered as a solution to the problem. Because it is necessary to improve the specialized subjects of the educational areas in accordance with the requirements of the time. For this, it is important to strengthen research aimed at the development of media education integrated with social humanities at all levels of education. In the world experience, research in this field began in the 60s and 70s of the last century, and a unique direction in science, media education, appeared. It is expected that the new direction will help young people to adapt to the world of media culture, to master the language of mass media, to be able to analyze media texts.

According to the recommendation of YUNESKO, media education is being introduced in many developed countries of the world. The goal is to build media literacy. Currently, the nature, purpose and tasks of media education are being studied on a large scale and significant results are being

achieved. In Wikipedia, media studies are the study of the press, television, radio, cinematography, and the Internet. The knowledge in this regard serves not only for the supply of personnel for the industry, but also for the formation of the ability to analyze, evaluate and create media texts in every person who uses information technologies.

Today, invisible socio- philosophical methods and technologies are being used that lead to the long- term dehumanization of other peoples through some of the information disseminated in the media system. We see this in the following:

- messages distributed on the internet and other media that may negatively affect the security and development of society;
- in media systems among information, young people;
- nonsense that has a negative effect on spirituality and morals;
- resources, information, descriptions, films, clips, books;
- the presence of texts, songs, reports and others;
- based on the content of information distributed in media systems;
- not necessarily useful, just meant to pass the time.

therefore, the presence of games, information that attracts everyone; that due to copying of literature, textbooks, training manuals, abstracts, prepared course works available in the media system, the enthusiasm of the young generation to study and research is decreasing, and because of this, a hopeless process is taking place, such as the weakening of the ability to think.

The media system, which lures young people whose worldview is not fully formed, as well as people who do not have a firm opinion, the presence of currents with religious and magical power; in some media systems religious extremism, racism.

aggressive nationalism, fascist ideas are promoted;

large media, famous people, artists

personal life, household lifestyle, water, discrediting him

or messages that create a false reputation that are actually defamatory spread. As a result of the influence of the Internet, the increasing access to information and the increase in the possibilities of diversity in the print and information space, the formation of a multicultural (different cultures) information space in the information space, some subjects and special courses related to information security and information attacks have been developed and included in the educational process. In particular, some compulsory subjects in higher education institutions can be included among them. Important events published in the media will be discussed with the young people, comments will be made on the transmitted information, and today's the news appearance of the day is observed. In order to overcome the current crisis in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to strengthen the positive impact of the information age and eliminate its negative impact integration of non- professional media education with social humanitarian sciences, which serves the purpose of education, is considered promising.

In a word, the introduction of media education not only contributes to the formation of mature specialists for the field of mass communication, but also serves the formation of a healthy information environment in society and the formation of information culture among young people.

Based on our analysis, we suggest implementing the following measures to increase the effectiveness of teaching social and humanities in the higher education system:

- development of evaluation criteria aimed at increasing the effectiveness of teaching social and humanities in educational institutions and its implementation;
- organization of spiritual and educational circles on social and humanitarian subjects and ensuring active participation of young people in them during their free time;
- to strengthen the work of holding various events, evenings and round talks related to the study of social and humanitarian sciences;
- among young people in social and humanitarian sciences sociological surveys aimed at determining their interests to carry out
- organization of professors- teachers giving important news to young people in social and humanitarian field for a short period of time during class sessions;
- to create a society of social and humanitarian councils with voluntary composition of young people and to discuss the existing problems in the field.

By implementing measures in these directions, in the future, it will be possible to increase the effectiveness of teaching social and humanitarian subjects in educational institutions, increase the interest of young people in these subjects, expand the scope of young people's worldview and independent thinking.

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INUMBER OF INFLUENCERS AND THEIR FOLLOWERS

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ABSTRACT

Every day, consumers have many choices about what to buy. This purchase choice is the culmination of extensive consideration of wants, needs, and other factors. In addition to these, friends, relatives and coworkers all play a role in shaping consumer preferences. In recent years, it has become clear that social media influencers can sway the purchasing decisions of their followers. The objective of this study is to discover number of influencer that followers know on the given social media platforms. Data was gathered from primary as well as secondary sources such as questionnaire, Google forms, journals, magazines, internet etc. 100 respondents from the Rohtak region were used in survey. Non probability sampling technique used to select sample. The findings demonstrated that on Youtube and Instagram maximum numbers of influencers are followed and on Twitter least number of influencers is followed.

Keywords: Social Media, Social Media Influencer, Consumer buying behavior.

INTRODUCTION

Today, marketing has evolved into an art form that involves sharing experiences with customers rather than just offering them products. It is no longer necessary to make individual efforts to promote your product; instead, one can now use the expertise of some well-known individuals (Influencers) to target mass consumers through the use of social media channels like TV, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and other sites where individual reach is not feasible. At present, the number of internet users is expanded when compared with past and now a noteworthy piece of the population is investing their energy on the social networking sites. So to thrive in the market, role of influencer marketing through social media have expanded. It is generally agreed upon that each person is responsible for the choices that influence his or her daily life. Everyone's access to news has shifted since the rise of social media platforms. Companies have found that social media is the most effective medium for reaching their target audience and spreading news about their products and services. Before the widespread availability of social media platforms, customers received information about the product from the company through more traditional channels, and they simply accepted the message without question. However, now that customers can actively participate in the conversation by sharing their opinions on a variety of products through review sites, it's more important than ever for brands to deliver high-quality goods and services. More than half the world's population is now active on at least one social media site, making it simple for businesses to spread the word about their

wares.

Influencer marketing is social media advertising that focuses on employing influencers to spread a brand's message to a larger audience. An influencer is a social media user who is less well-known and popular than the world's celebrities, but who nonetheless has impact. They are sort of opinion leaders, but they aren't exactly "regular people" or well-known figures. What makes certain persons more influential than others? Is it because of their rank or a duty related to their employment? How integrated into social or commercial systems are they? Their character? The insightful subject matter? Or was it simply a matter of timing and location? There isn't a set formula that must be followed, thus it might be a combination. These influencers collaborate with organizations and are compensated for their work by receiving cash payments, gifts, or other benefits in exchange for spreading the word. In essence, they are promoting the brand's goods or services on their platform(s), either overtly (by posting it as an advertisement) or covertly (by, for example, leaving a product on a table). Although influencers use a variety of social media sites, the most effective ones include blogs, Facebook, Youtube, Instagram, and Twitter. Brands have been interacting with the influencers of their interests for years, but more recently, new businesses have emerged as a result of changes in online life advertising practises and consumer demand for more services. These businesses create databases where they compile influential people from numerous industries. Companies can use this method to search databases and identify influencers who are appropriate for their brand, product, or service. Therefore, by taking use of these services, organizations may streamline their social media marketing by following the best relevant influencers while also saving time by skipping over the reasonable ones. Influencer marketing involves a third party who, though they may never be accountable for it, fundamentally impacts the customer's purchasing choice.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A number of descriptive studies on this topic have been conducted by researchers, various institutions and agencies. An attempt is made to review the available literature on the subject under study.

Ertemel and Ammoura (2016) researchers looked on how paid social media advertising affected consumers' purchasing decisions in the retail fashion sector. The study also identifies variations in brand names and consumer demographic characteristics. For this study, electronic questionnaires were created for consumers who reside in Istanbul, Turkey. The consumer buying behavior model with five phases was applied. These processes were Identification of Need, Information Search, Post-Purchase Evaluation, Buying Decision, and Alternative Evaluation. Results showed there are no relationship with information search and only a weak relationship between social media advertising and customer need recognition. Strong correlation with alternative evaluation was discovered. The survey also showed that there is no correlation between consumer education level and age.

Biaudet (2017) Customers are getting more competent at using media and more sensitive of company communications as a result of digitalization. Because it is so difficult for firms to stand out from the sea of other advertisements, many turn to influencer marketing. It represents a novel marketing strategy for those individuals at the forefront of the consumer buying process because it is virtually hard for a business to develop customer trust alone. This study aims to understand why

businesses should utilize influencer marketing as a tool for marketing and how to run an influencer marketing campaign on Instagram. . The study also collected qualitative data through a semi-structured interview with the Finnish social media influencer marketing firm Monochrome in addition to the literature review. One individual, the CEO and co-founder of Monochrome, was the subject of the interview. The interview began with background questions about the business and moved on to topics like influencer marketing in general and the steps involved in developing an influencer marketing campaign. With closing and follow-up questions, the interview was concluded. The findings suggest that Instagram influencer marketing is a methodical procedure. Influencer marketing incorporated a level of reader and influencer trust. A brand cannot develop a relationship with the consumer on its own, which is why a business should employ influencer marketing as a marketing tactic.

De Veirman, Cauberghe and Hudders (2017) studied the effect of brand attitude on the number of followers and product difference. The main aim of the study was to find out whether the number of followers has an impact on the relationship between followers and influencers' likeability. There were two sections to the investigation. In the first section, relationships between followers and influencers were discovered by making phone influencer Instagram accounts. The Likert scale has five points. M. Turk recruited 117 Instagram users who took part in the study. The study's second component looked at the quantity of followers and product divergence. From M. Turk, 118 female participants were selected. It was discovered that having more followers makes one more likeable. When a lot of people are interested in a product, the assumption spreads that it will not be unique.

Gashi (2017) with the power of information sharing shifting from businesses to consumers, social media is bringing people from all over the world together. Companies now find it incredibly challenging to reach customers. Customers' purchasing decisions are influenced by social media influencers, which help businesses, solve this issue and generate sales. Consumers' purchasing decisions are allegedly influenced by social media influencers, but little is actually known about the influence at each stage of the purchasing process. The purchase decision process is a set of processes that the buyer must go through before making a choice to buy anything. The main aim of the study was to find out how consumers view the influence of social media influencers at various points in the purchasing process. A qualitative study was carried out to examine members' opinions and experiences in order to collect consumer understanding of the influence of social media influencers. The results of this study demonstrate that social media influencers are important in every phase of the buying process for consumers due to their capacity to give content, attractiveness, knowledge, social identity, and trust. The study's original contribution was in recognizing how social media influencers have an impact at every stage of the purchasing decision-making process.

Nandagiri and Philip (2018) the goal of the study is to determine whether an influencer's work supporting or evaluating a product has a beneficial impact on their audience. For this sample size, 100 people who were between the ages of 18 and 21 were selected and given a survey. 111 people completed the online survey, which had 20 questions. The majority of respondents are female, and they follow prominent YouTube and Instagram influencers. They watched videos and photographs of

the influencers discussing and promoting the products, respectively. The findings demonstrated that the sample preferred product reviews to advertisements, making it more effective in its own right. It was found that the viewer was more likely to relate to and understand the product the way the influencer had.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this research is to discover number of influencer that followers know on the given social media platforms. In this research descriptive and exploratory methods used to fulfill the objectives of this research. The sample size for this study will be 100 customers who use social media for making their opinion for purchasing of various goods like mobile phones, apparels, consumer electronic items, cosmetic products etc. The researcher collected samples from Rohtak for the purpose of the current investigation. Primary data as well as secondary data was collected for this survey such as questionnaire, articles, journals, magazines etc. Researcher made personal contact with the students at their individual schools and locations in order to get the desired high response rate.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

A total of 100 respondents completed the 7-question survey online. Most of the responders were women, and the bulk of them were in the 18 to 25 age range. The majority of respondents watch popular influencers' videos on YouTube and Instagram.

Age of respondents

Maximum number of respondent's lie in age group 18-25 and minimum lies in the group 30-35 i.e.10 respondents.

Table 1: Age of respondents

AGE	Respondents
18-25	62
25-30	38
30-35	10
Total	100

Figure 1: Age of respondents

Gender of Respondents

There are more female respondents i.e. 55 and remaining 45 respondents are male.

Table 2: Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	45	45.0	45.0
Female	55	55.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

Figure 2: Gender of Respondents

Respondents were asked to fill the number of influencers they know and follow on different social media platforms.

Table 3: Facebook influencers you follow and are familiar with

Facebook	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 2	57	57.0	57.0
2 to 5	14	14.0	71.0
5 to 10	3	3.0	74.0
Not Applicable	26	26.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

From this table we can see that the maximum respondents who follow on Facebook are following less than 2 influencers i.e. 57 respondents, 14 respondents follow 2 to 5 influencers, 3 respondents follow 5 to 10 respondents and rest of them are non-applicable.

Figure 3: Facebook influencers you follow and are familiar with

Table 4: Youtube influencers you follow and are familiar with

YouTube	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 2	43	43.0	43.0
2 to 5	14	14.0	57.0
5 to 10	5	5.0	62.0
More than 10	20	20.0	82.0
Not Applicable	18	18.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

From this table we can see that the maximum respondents who follow on YouTube are following less than 2 influencers i.e. 43 respondents, 14 respondents follow 2 to 5 influencers, 5 respondents follow 5 to 10 in and rest of them are non-applicable. Below graph presents proportionate frequency of the above figures.

Figure 4: Youtube influencers you follow and are familiar with

Table 5: Instagram influencers you follow and are familiar with

Instagram	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 2	46	46.0	46.0
2 to 5	14	14.0	60.0
5 to 10	10	10.0	70.0
More than 10	11	11.0	81.0
Not Applicable	19	19.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

From this table we can see that the maximum respondents who follow on Instagram are following less than 2 influencers i.e. 46 respondents, 14 respondents follow 2 to 5 influencers, 10 respondents follow 5 to 10 influencers, 11 respondents follow more than 10 influencers and rest of them are non-applicable. Below graph presents proportionate frequency of the above figures.

Figure 5: Instagram influencers you follow and are familiar with

Table 6: Twitter influencers you follow and are familiar with

Twitter	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 2	45	45.0	45.0
2 to 5	10	10.0	55.0
More than 10	4	4.0	59.0
Not Applicable	41	41.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

From this table we can see that the maximum respondents who follow on Twitter are following less than 2 influencers i.e. 45 respondents, 10 respondents follow 2 to 5 influencers, 4 respondents follow more than 10 influencers and rest of them are non-applicable. Below graph presents proportionate frequency of the above figures.

Figure 6: Twitter influencers you follow and are familiar with

Table 7: Snapchat influencers you follow and are familiar with

Snapchat	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 2	50	50.0	50.0
2 to 5	14	14.0	64.0
5 to 10	1	1.0	65.0
More than 10	3	3.0	68.0
Not Applicable	32	32.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

From this table we can see that the maximum respondents who follow on Snapchat are following less than 2 influencers i.e. 50 respondents, 14 respondents follow 2 to 5 influencers, 1 respondents follow 5 to 10 influencers, 3 respondents follow more than 10 influencers and rest of them are non-applicable. Below graph presents proportionate frequency of the above figures.

Figure 7: Snapchat influencers you follow and are familiar with

CONCLUSION

This conclusion can be drawn as a direct consequence of the findings presented above. Youtube and Instagram are the most followed platforms from the point of view of influencers. On Twitter least number of influencers is followed. Although the effect is thought to be relatively minor, there is evidence that it has a beneficial impact on shoppers' intentions to make a purchase. The result of running analysis shows that if the source is more known to the consumer, then it will have a considerable effect on the consumer's intention to make a purchase. Buyers are greatly impacted by online content and, now even more, through social relationships whenever it relates to purchasing. Further research is necessary to identify social impact metrics that accurately reflect users' direct control.

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PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN SPEECH ACTS

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the stages of speech acts. In this process, speech acts in English and Uzbek works using phraseological units are selected. The locutionary, illocutionary and perlocutionary acts of these speech acts are analyzed.

Keywords: phraseological unit, pragmatics, speech act, locutionary act, illocutionary act, perlocutionary act.

INTRODUCTION

The words used in our speech are the sources that play an important role in expressing our thoughts. Phraseological units are used to increase the meaning of the words and it is necessary to understand the content of the speech in order to be clear to the listener. This is considered one of the topical issues studied in the field of linguistics, so phraseology and pragmatics are important fields in the study of this problem.

A.V.Kunin notes that the outstanding professor E.D.Polivanov raised the issue of phraseology as a linguistic discipline for the first time, in addition, E.D.Polivanov repeatedly returned to this issue and emphasized that the dictionary studies the individual lexical meanings of words, morphology studies the formal meanings of words and syntax studies the formal meanings of phrases, “and now corresponding to the syntax, there is a need for a special section that deals with the individual meanings of these individual expressions, not the general types but at the same time as the dictionary is concerned with the individual (lexical) meanings of individual words. This field of linguistics, as well as the generality of the phenomena studied in it, I give the name of phraseology (I note that another term has been proposed for this meaning - idiomatic)” [10, 7].

According to Sh.Rakhmatullayev, this language unit consists of at least two lexemes [6, 6], two and more lexemes are semantically-syntactically connected, generalization occurs when a figurative meaning is discovered [7, 420].

Sh.Safarov emphasizes that pragmatics is a special field of linguistics, the scope of its research includes the selection of linguistic units in the communication process, their using and the influence of the units in this usage on the participants of the communication [8, 76].

METHODS

According to M.Buzrukova, a speech act is one of the main concepts of pragmatics, a purposeful communicative action performed in accordance with the rules of language movement [2, 108]. Sh.Safarov acknowledges that the speech act theory as a complete doctrine was formed in the works of the English logician J.Austin, the American psychologist J.Searle and others [8, 77]. Arso Setyaji notes that Austin classifies speech acts into three: locutionary act, illocutionary act, and perlocutionary act [1, 18]. R. Choerunnisa points out that the idea is also proposed by Yule who states that locutionary act is the act of producing meaningful utterances. [3, 8]. Arso Setyaji defines that illocutionary acts – the act

of intending are the acts that contain an intention [1, 18]. According to Sh.Safarov, perlocutionary act is the influencing stage of speech activity, perlocution is an act of influencing the mind, feelings and behavior of the listener [8, 82]. The theory of these speech acts is described through English and Uzbek speech acts using phraseological units.

RESULTS

The description of speech acts was selected and analyzed from the following English and Uzbek works where phraseological units were used:

“Don’t make fun of it” from the novel “The Little Nugget” by P.G. Wodehouse [9, 45];

“You’re joking!” from the novel “The Little Nugget” by P.G. Wodehouse [9, 45];

“Shoira o’ninchi sinfni bitiray deb turganda, shu yigit silab-siypab turib bir chang soldi-da, Shoirani baxti qaro qilib qo’ydi” from the novel “Nur borki, soya bor” (There is light, there is a shadow) by O.Khoshimov [5, 156];

“– Omadingiz keldi! – injener iyagini cho’zib qiya eshik tomonga imo qildi” from the novel “Nur borki, soya bor” (There is light, there is a shadow) by O.Khoshimov [5, 181].

The results show that these speech acts are described through the stages of locutionary act, illocutionary act and perlocutionary act. The analysis of these acts includes the process of conveying the speaker’s opinion and its content to the listener.

DISCUSSION

There is a speech act “Don’t make fun of it” from the novel “The little nugget” by P.G.Wodehouse [9, 45]. The phraseological unit “make fun of somebody/something” is used, the general meaning of the words in it and it means figuratively “to laugh at somebody/something or make other people laugh at them, usually in an unkind way” [4, 630]. According to the stages of speech acts, the locutionary act is “Don’t make fun of him”, the illocutionary act is “to encourage you not laugh rudely at him” and there is the command in an illocutionary force.

The perlocutionary act is “do not laugh at him rudely”.

There is a speech act “You’re joking!” from the novel “The little nugget” by P.G.Wodehouse [9, 45]. In this speech act there is a phraseological unit “You’re joking!” that is “used to show that you are very surprised at what somebody has just said” [4, 837]. According to the analysis based on the stages of speech acts, the locutionary act is “You’re joking”, the illocutionary act is “showing surprise” and there is an illocutionary force with emotion. The perlocutionary act is “he knows that he is surprised”.

There is a speech act “Shoira o’ninchi sinfni bitiray deb turganda, shu yigit silab-siypab turib bir chang soldi-da, Shoirani baxti qaro qilib qo’ydi” from the novel “Nur borki, soya bor” (There is light, there is a shadow) by O.Khoshimov [5, 156]. In this speech act, the phraseological unit “baxti qaro” which means “there is not good time from marriage; unhappy” is used. According to the stages of speech act, the locutionary act is “when Shoira was about to graduate from the tenth grade, this young man attacked while being kind to her and made her unhappy”, illocutionary act is “to report that this young man made Shoira unhappy by attacking while being kind to her when she was about to graduate from the tenth grade” and the illocutionary force of reporting is expressed. The perlocutionary act is “to know that this young man made Shoira unhappy by attacking while being kind to her when she was about to graduate from the tenth grade”.

There is a speech act “– Omadingiz keldi! – injener iyagini cho‘zib qiya eshik tomonga imo qildi” from the novel “Nur borki, soya bor” (There is light, there is a shadow) by O.Khoshimov [5, 181]. The phraseological unit “omadi kelmoq” which means “to succeed in one’s work, to be lucky” is used in this speech act.

Based on the stages of the process of speech acts, the locutionary act is “You are lucky!” - the engineer extended his chin and gestured towards the slanted door”, then there is the illocutionary force of informing in the delivery of information and the illocutionary is “to inform that the engineer who said that he was lucky that his job has succeed and gestured towards the slanted door with his chin”. A perlocutionary act is “an action is performed as a result of the engineer who said that he was lucky that his job has succeed and gestured towards the slanted door with his chin”.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the listener’s comprehension of the sentences used by the speaker in the process of communication, the meaning of the phraseological units which involved in them are studied in linguistics by dividing into stages and this shows that speech acts are important in understanding and clarifying the content of the speaker’s speech.

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IMPORTANCE OF TRANSPORT IN UZBEKISTAN'S INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

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Abstract

In this article, information on the main transport networks used in Uzbekistan and their periods from their creation to the present development, as well as the importance of these means of transport and their effective use, and suggestions are given.

Keywords. Transport, production, railway transport, interstate communications, air transport, road transport,

Introduction

It is well known that no country can have a perfect economic and social activity without establishing relations with other countries around it. The beginning of the production of goods led to the formation of international trade relations. The development of production forces at first sharply increased the volume of production in all regions, and then created the basis for further strengthening of the economic relations of the states. After independence, Uzbekistan has been very active in international economic relations and has been carrying out trade and export-import processes through the transport networks of the country.

Uzbekistan is one of the prominent countries in the world, it occupies one of the important places among more than 180 countries of the world with many raw material resources, natural resources, production, and services provided. In particular, to date, Uzbekistan stands out among other countries in the extraction and processing of several strategically important minerals.

The territory of Uzbekistan is rich in a number of minerals, and the territory of our country corresponds to 1.5% of the irrigated land in the world, and agricultural crops are grown by farmers on these fertile lands.

In recent years, thanks to the many production sectors, new sectors such as technology, pharmaceutical, automotive, petrochemical, electronics industries are developing rapidly in Uzbekistan. Many products are produced and exported to foreign countries.

The Main Part

Uzbekistan is one of the two countries in the world far from the ocean (the other being Liechtenstein). Uzbekistan uses land (railroad, automobile), air, pipeline transport and partially water transport (Amu Darya, Syrdarya).

Railway transport. Regardless of the weather conditions and the season of the year, this transport network continues to operate. Its speed is quite high and the cost of transportation is very low (compared to road transport). Highways for the railway can be built in different directions. But high steep mountains and regions where earthquakes occur relatively often are excluded. The total length of this railway transport in our country is more than 7 thousand km.(2019)

Length of public railways in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions (km)

№		1980	1985	1990	1995	2000	2005	2015	2018	2019
	Province									
1	Qoraqalpog'iston.Res	458,0	475	475	504,0	503,5	844,3	844,3	921,0	885,3
2	Andijon	159	159	159	156,6	155,8	155,8	155,8	155,8	158,8
3	Buxoro	655	654	609	210	324,9	270,6	270,0	493,5	499,2
4	Jizzax	216	216	217	217,8	217,8	280,5	274,1	274,1	274,5
5	Qashqadaryo	355	382	376	380,1	380,1	381,7	492,7	492,7	492,7
6	Navoiy				390,7	276,7	469,3	469,3	469,3	512,4
7	Namangan	138	138	138	140,0	140,0	144,6	224,8	228,1	226,7
8	Samarqand	263	263	277	277,0	279,0	283,8	282,9	282,9	282,9
9	Surxondaryo	296	315		314,0	301	300,0	368,7	368,7	425,6
10	Sirdaryo	166	166	172	171,6	171,6	157,8	167,5	161,5	160,9
11	Toshkent	348	353	363	363,8	363,8	358,5	364,6	391,0	390,9
12	Farg'ona	228	228	228	227,8	228,6	228,6	228,6	228,6	228,6
13	Xorazm	133	133	133	128,7	128,7	138,7	138,7	174,7	199,6
14	Toshkent				-	-	-	-	-	-
	All republic	3415	3482	3462	3482,7	3471,5	4014,2	4237,5	4641,9	4735,1

- Car transport. It is the most widely used transport network in our country, it is easy and affordable to transport goods and passengers. We use this transport network every day and on every front. It is advisable to use it mainly for short distances of 100 km and in areas with poor railway access. The total length of highways in our country is 184,000 km
- 42,695 km of public roads
- 14,100 km of international importance
- 24,614 km of local significance
- The streets in our republic are inter-farm roads, rural streets, urban-type rural streets 116,560 km

Length of public highways by region in 2019.

№	Province	All	According to the importance of roads		
			International	State	Local
1	Qoraqalpog'iston. Res	4213	664	992	2557
2	Andijon	2463	103	800	1560
3	Buxoro	4101	540	1155	2406
4	Jizzax	2601	168	1431	1002
5	Qashqadaryo	3427	425	890	2112
6	Navoiy	3917	302	2490	1125
7	Namangan	3377	69	1048	2260
8	Samarqand	4097	385	979	2733
9	Surxondaryo	2843	351	990	1502
10	Sirdaryo	1450	259	505	686
11	Toshkent	3965	400	1241	2324
12	Farg'ona	4031	202	873	2956
13	Xorazm	2210	113	706	1391
14	Toshkent				
	All republic	42 695	3981	14100	24614

Air transport. Air transport is the fastest mode of transport today. It is faster than other types of transport (automobile and railway) and it is convenient to carry and transport perishable goods and long-distance goods. In addition, it can be said that using this type of transport, it is possible to quickly evacuate from one country to another. Air transport in Uzbekistan developed rapidly after independence. After gaining independence, on January 28, 1992, by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the National Airlines of Uzbekistan Airways was established on the basis of the Civil Aviation Administration of Uzbekistan, which was under the control of the former Union Civil Aviation. Air transport is one of the most important sectors in the economy of our country and other countries

- cultural
- diplomatic,
- economic,
- is causing the development of trade relations.

First in Uzbekistan, in Kokand in 1947, in Samarkand in 1948, New in Karysh in 1955, in Bukhara in 1963, in Tashkent in 1961 airports were built. By 1980, the length of Uzbekistan's air transport routes was more than 155,000 km. Including the length of local air routes is 60.1 thousand km. Tashkent airport is the largest international airport in the Central Asian region. Pilots, technical service personnel, and ground service personnel for the air transport of our republic are trained at the Tashkent Aviation Institute, which was established on May 15, 1943, by the flight training center of the national airline company "Uzbekiston Havoyollari".

Analysis of Literature on the Topic

If we consider the literature on this topic; Z. Abdalova and Z. Tajiyeva in their work entitled "Economic Geography" "The role of infrastructure in continuous production important. Therefore, the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is territorial it is of particular importance to study whether it is provided with production infrastructure in the formation of systems. 1, and as a logical continuation of this opinion, describing the importance of transport in the deployment of production forces, "The role of transport in the development and deployment of production forces is incomparable. Transport production in any region is an important part of the infrastructure. Any scale it is impossible to develop the area effectively and rationally without transport.

Production and consumer in industry and agriculture transport takes an active part in delivery. Economic district and specialization in zones is carried out by transport. Transportation development of production forces and technical progress depends on the level of development. 1990-2010 in transport infrastructure in 2015, from railways to highways (109.8%). (122.1%) there was an increase in the total length of use. in 2013 transport in the republic's gross domestic product production share was 11.9 percent, in this respect it is industrial and rural. It is the third most important industry after agriculture. 2 - he said.

Analysis and Results

During the analysis of the above points, the following results were obtained; in order to further increase the importance of transport, first of all, removing many requirements placed on it, construction of new easy-to-use and efficient transport routes for the development of transport networks, to improve relations between countries and thereby open safe roads for transport, includes such results.

Conclusions and Suggestions

Our country is one of the Central Asian countries with a well-equipped transport system. Due to its distance from the oceans, sea and river transport is not sufficiently developed, but despite this, relations with other countries are effectively carried out by other types of transport. From the information given above, it is known that the development of transport and its effective use will develop the country's economy.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF USING FAIRY TALE THERAPY IN THE PRIMARY CLASSES OF A SPECIAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

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Annotation:

The article highlights the effective method of using fairy tale therapy in the primary classes of children of a special educational institution. The benefits of using fairy tale therapy are described. Information about the types of fairy tales used in fairy tale therapy is provided.

Keywords: special education, cognitive, therapy, hyperactive, competence, individual, anomaly, compensation.

The concept of modernization of education requires a new approach to the educational functions of the general education school and, of course, the improvement of the educational process. focused on the development of his personality, knowledge and creative abilities. The general education school should form a comprehensive system of universal knowledge, abilities, skills, as well as the experience of independent activity and personal responsibility of students, that is, the basic competencies that determine the modern quality of educational content. So, what about special education?

One of the main trends in the field of modern education is the creation of special conditions for development, education and upbringing, and at the same time, the percentage of children who need special education - severe and complex disabilities - is increasing. How to help them?

The development of such a child occurs in a unique way. The approach to education and upbringing of such "needs of special education" children should also be special, non-traditional, based on the individual characteristics of each child, due to the nature of the disorders in their physical and mental development, education should be adapted to their needs. should be

One such non-traditional approach is the use of fairy-tale therapy as an accompanying element of the main educational process in an educational institution where children with disabilities study.

Children with disabilities are a complex and unique contingent of students with physical or mental disabilities that present varying degrees of learning difficulties. This category includes children with various developmental disorders:

- hearing,
- to see
- speech,
- musculoskeletal system,
- intelligence,
- with developmental delays and complex disorders,
- children with severe emotional and behavioral disorders. In corrective-pedagogical work with children with various developmental disabilities, a special place is given to fairy tale therapy - it is an innovative educational technology that has already proven its effectiveness.

Story therapy is one of the most effective ways to work with disabled children who have physical, emotional or behavioral difficulties. This method is convenient for children to understand in all types

of education. The method of fairy tale therapy allows solving problems of behavior, emotional-will control. He introduces children to books, introduces them to literature, and encourages children to be creative by writing fairy tales together.

Fairy tale therapy develops a child's personality through a multifaceted effect. It develops leadership qualities, speech, imagination, thinking, and also helps to eliminate undesirable qualities found in children: indecisiveness, fear, aggression, etc. Thanks to immersion in a fairy tale, the child opens up, experiences vivid feelings and emotions.

At primary school age, the child actively develops the mechanism of identification, therefore, fairy tale therapy is the most effective method during this period. The child fully gets used to the role of the hero, fully experiences all the events that happen to his character, imposes his personal qualities and relationships on him. Fairy tale images teach the child how to act in this or that difficult life situation, observing the norms of morality and ethics.

A fairy tale serves as an intermediary between reality and the inner world for a child. A fairy tale is perceived and understood (as a rule, at the subconscious level) solves some psychological problems, or, more precisely, provides a person with access to social relations. Any fairy tale is aimed at socio-pedagogical effect: it teaches, educates, encourages activity and even heals. Fairytale images are emotionally rich, colorful and unusual, but at the same time simple and understandable for children. Therefore, fairy tales and their characters are one of the main sources of knowledge of reality (events, behavior, character of people) for a child. It is in the form of a fairy tale that a child encounters complex events and feelings: love and hatred, anger and compassion, betrayal and lies.

Children with disabilities are a complex, unique contingent. In them, underdevelopment of cognitive activity is observed as the main symptom, a symptom of mental weakness, and some features of the emotional-will sphere are lagging behind in development. The feelings of children who need special education are unstable and changeable. They may react differently to the same recurring event. Therefore, before telling a fairy tale, it is necessary to create a positive emotional mood, calm the child, introduce him to the "magic state", interest him in seeing and hearing unusual things.

A fairy tale plays a big role in correcting the emotional sphere of children who need special education. The emotional background created by the teacher while reading the fairy tale, the change in the voice of the characters, the reflection of the emotional state of the characters of the fairy tale on the teacher's face - all this helps to read the fairy tale. The child unconsciously begins to "reflect" on his face the feelings he experienced while listening to the story.

Fairy tale therapy is one of the least "traumatic" and painless methods of psychotherapy. A fairy tale not only teaches children to experience, rejoice, sympathize, but also encourages them to communicate verbally. Its meaning extends to the concept of "social adaptation", that is, correction and compensation of gross anomalies in early development, playing an important role in preparing children with special needs for life and work.

Fairy tales help the child to adapt to life: by solving fairy tale conflicts, the child alleviates internal psychological stress, develops self-confidence and a sense of security. The child does not like instructions, and the fairy tale does not teach him directly, offers interesting images, and vital information is absorbed spontaneously, imperceptibly. Through a fairy tale, it is easy to explain to a child the first moral concepts - what is good and what is bad. The characters are vividly expressed in their images, they are strengthened in real life and in relationships with loved ones.

"Journeys" through fairy tales awaken children's imagination and imaginative thinking, get rid of patterns and patterns. Sketches, which are constantly used to express and manifest various emotions, improve and activate expressive tools - plasticity, facial expressions and speech. For the comprehensive development of a child, it is very important to nourish his emotional sphere, to develop his feelings, and a fairy tale is one of the most convenient means of developing the feelings of a child.

Our main goals in working with disabled children are the development of the emotional sphere, social and aesthetic relations, education of the sense of collectivism, development of thinking, attention, speech, memory and fine motor skills. Through fairy tales, we try to form children's love for nature, modesty, kindness, national decency, responsibility and many other qualities of universal human values. Fairytale therapy is a psychotherapeutic approach, with the help of which the child overcomes his fears, negative personality traits, and also educates, develops his personality and, if necessary, corrects his behavior. . It is the most ancient method of upbringing and education, fairy tale therapy has a valuable value in human civilization and its origin goes back more than a thousand years. Fairy tales and stories have been used for teaching and healing purposes since ancient times. M. Erikson, N. Pezeshkian, B. Bettelheims began to use metaphors, fairy tales and parables as a means of psychotherapeutic intervention. N. Pezeshkian considered parables and proverbs as examples of a vivid image of speech, which suggested that they help resolve intrapsychic conflicts and remove emotional stress[1].

However, fairy-tale therapy has a very young age in the scientific world, and the official establishment date of the institute of fairy-tale therapy is considered to be 1998 in St. Petersburg.

Fairytale therapy is very popular today and is actively used in working with children with severe intellectual disabilities. Using a fairy tale in teaching, you can correct the negative aspects of the child's behavior.

Types of fairy tales used in fairy tale therapy:

Didactic fairy tale - created to tell children about new concepts (home, nature, family, rules of behavior in society, etc.). Tasks in such fairy tales give the child the opportunity to immediately apply the acquired knowledge in practice. A didactic story can be told in any convenient form (story, cartoon or just a game). This is a didactic tale that can arouse interest in a child and enliven a regular lesson.

A psychological fairy tale is designed to guide and enrich the child's personal development.

Fairy tale - introduces children to the aesthetic principles and traditions of humanity.

Diagnostic fairy tale - helps to determine the child's character and reveals his attitude to the world.

A meditative fairy tale is a special type of fairy tale that communicates with the listener's subconscious by creating vivid visual images in his imagination.

Fairy tale therapy for hyperactive children.

When working with children with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, the method of fairy tale therapy is often used, which allows reducing excessive activity and normalizing the child's emotional state. Through a fairy tale, a hyperactive child learns to control his behavior, becomes calmer.

Fairy tale therapy in speech therapy work with children.

The method of fairy tale therapy is also widely used to teach children with severe speech disorders. This method is very effective for developing the child's cognitive abilities, as well as speech function in an unobtrusive, simple and convenient game. Fairy tale therapy helps to form cause-effect relationships and learn social norms accepted in society.

Fairy tale therapy for children with severe mental retardation.

All training using fairy tale therapy is conducted in the form of a game. This method allows the child to develop creative thinking, oral speech, imaginative thinking, the ability to establish cause-and-effect relationships, and develop a sense of humor. Fine and gross motor skills, mood background, self-care skills, modeling, drawing and writing are improved with the help of story therapy.

Listening to the fairy tale, the child plunges into a magical world full of secrets and adventures. It helps to form a strong feeling for the hero of the fairy tale in the child. Fairy tale therapy helps to teach, develop and teach children to communicate with other people, as well as to develop speech, higher mental functions: thinking, memory, imagination.

In the process of correction and education, fairy tale therapy occupies a special place, because with the help of fairy tales, children learn the norms of behavior shown by the main characters of fairy tales in the easiest and simplest way.

The method of fairy tale therapy in classes with children who need special education is not only educational, but also correction and development aimed at increasing the personal and creative potential of the child. Fairy tale therapy awakens children's love for reading, it is interesting for children not only to play fairy tales together with a specialist, but also to analyze other fairy tales and read them independently.

Fairy tale therapy is one of the main genres of folklore, a prose work of an epic, mostly magical, adventurous or domestic character. It is one of the types and methods of emotional-psychological, pedagogical influence, social and moral formation in socio-cultural activity. [2]

Writing and reading fairy tales are used in game psychotherapy to offer the child new opportunities and behaviors, to attract his attention, to stimulate the manifestation of hidden abilities, as well as to strengthen optimism and hope in the child. Gives him a chance to achieve a positive result.

T. D. Zinkevich divides fairy tale therapy into the following types:

1. Writing fairy tales - interpretation; rewriting fairy tales; write new tales and stories;
2. Staging fairy tales - a fairy tale in the sand; theatrical games; therapeutic puppet shows;
3. Telling a story - a) Group - to invent "in the circle"; tell a well-known fairy tale "in a circle"; b) Individual - from the 1st person; From the 3rd person [3].

Thus, we can conclude that fairy tale therapy is an effective way of working with children who need special education. Because this method allows solving problems of emotional-will control of behavior. He introduces children to books, introduces them to literature, and encourages children to be creative by writing fairy tales together. Fairy tale therapy develops a child's personality through a multifaceted effect. It develops leadership qualities, speech, imagination, thinking, and also helps to eliminate undesirable qualities: indecisiveness, fear, aggression, etc.

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GLOBAL INTERPRETATION: PHILOSOPHY OF LITERATURE

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Abstract

In this article, it is noted that a relatively new direction in our literary criticism is the essence of the philosophy of literature as a product of world-class scientific and literary interpretation. Analysis of selected works of both classic and modern new literature. Also, the philosophy of literature is a set of high and great global meanings that are covered and seen with the eyes of the heart and the eyes of the pure mind.

Keywords: global interpretation, philosophy, image, plot, art, word, classic novel.

Introduction

Literary philosophy is not the science of nature, society, and the development of thought, the general laws that we are aware of, that is, it is not philosophy, or part of it. Even it is not applying these principles to literary works, it is not searching and finding philosophical categories from their content. It is possible to say that there is such a way which will not provide sufficient scientific and practical results. Because such coercive philosophical rules do not absorb into a work of art, on the contrary, they will harm it. Literature does not disclose the heart of the work of art; it does not like foreign ideas and rules forced into it. It wants to see itself in itself.

Discussion and Methods

The Philosophy of Literature is the Word; it is the philosophy of small and large worlds existing in its front and back and in its depths.

If to look upon it through the eyesight of literary philosophy, a simple, unobtrusive sentence in a particular work, a description made regarding the character, can carry a great meaning, and like a magic stick it may present a new look to the work of art. In our classic novel "Kutlugh Qon" ("Memorial Blood"), Father Shakir's words that "a small courtyard in the shape of a talesman" or on behalf of this character of the novel about the leading character of the novel in the language of this hero, "Well, Yulchiboy, the Brave's son, was brave, he was from another world" encourages to look upon the whole novel and upon the leading Character, Yulichi's image with a different scholarly eye, it opens the way to it. At the heart of this description there is the meaning that Yulchi is not a man of this world, and it is interesting that the same sentence does not exist at all in the Russian translation of the novel. The translator might have realized the power of this statement; he could display the "vigilance." In Chingiz Aitmatov's famous story "Jamila", one of the leading characters describes Doniyor in Russian, "Stranniy chelovek, ne ot mira chego" (a strange man, not from this world)¹ (in the Uzbek

¹ Чингиз Айтматов, Повести гор и степей, Изд. "Худ. лит", М., 1971, С. 21.

translation the next sentence is not reflected) which restores his image mixed with divinity like that of Yulchi.

The fact is that the description given to the two literary characters is based on the words of Prophet Jesus in the Bible. Jesus says of himself and his people: "Since I am not from this world they are also not from this world" (John, 17:16)². Again he said, "Are you the King of the Jews?" the Roman ruler Pontius Pilate, who asked, replied, "My kingdom is not of this world" (John, 18:36)³.

It is no coincidence that the two literary heroes, Yulchi and Doniyor, are described as Jesus, who is also revered in our Islamic religion. And such a connection (a great connection!) Brings both heroes to a new, higher axis. Is it not because Doniyor is not from this world, his heart is in tune with the waves of distant worlds, that Louis Aragon, who made the story of Jamila famous, was called "the most beautiful love story in the world"? What if it was the same power that captivated a woman as wild and proud as Jamila?

As for as the our great novel "The Memorial Blood" is concerned, this description which leads the leading character of the work to Jesus alayhissalom, in our view, is an esoteric code embedded in the novel by the great writer, without doubt. This code is so skillfully placed among the words of Shakir ota that it is absolutely invisible at first glance. During my school years, I used to read the work several times, but it seemed to me that this sentence drew my attention only in the early 90s of the previous century.

What is the service function, the literary energy of this esoteric code? First of all, it gives a new dimension, a special wisdom to the image of Yulchi. Yulchi is a potentially great personality; he has a natural keen mind. Even not to mention his human superiority, he is intellectually superior to all the rich and educated jadid like that of Abdushukur described in the novel. Doesn't his demeanor, his spiritual purity, his standing on the side of truth and justice in spite of all dangers, indicate that he is an extraordinary human being, a person from another world? Read and re-read the novel in the light of Jesus, and rethink of every action, every effort, then you will surely believe in the great rise of both Yulchi and the novel itself. I'm sure of it.

Every work of art has its own secret place, that is, the fetus. It is impossible to unravel the literary mystery and magic in it to the end, moreover, the revealed mystery is not a mystery. Such mystery and magic is the first factor that makes a work of art known not only to the people of the period in which it was created, but also to future generations. While the embodiment of a true work of art is pleasing, the discovery of a person who travels in his inner world and decides to reveal his secrets must be pleasing, that is, the discoverer of mysteries, and he is destined.

Analysis and music. The ostrich looks like an event that is too far apart. But if we look at the matter in depth, it becomes clear that the original work of art is born from the music that the Creator places in the heart of the creator (if you want to call it inspiration), and this music moves to the work of words and melody. It is impossible to fully analyze a work of art without entering it into the body of musician to some extent and listening to it. It is not surprising that in such an analysis, analytical music is created from the music of an literary word.

Comprehensive analysis is one of the hallmarks of global scientific and literary analysis.

² Инжил, Туркия мукаддас китоб жамияти, 1995, 263-бет.

³ Ibid, p. 267.

Talking about the modernization of the poet's work, sometimes they add the poem "Time" to this stream. If modernization means to act and create in accordance with the requirements of the time, then the poem "Time" stands much higher than such modernization. In general, such works cannot be approached with a simple criterion, nor can such criteria be applied to poems such as Time. Those who include the poem in the list of modernization works may be distracted by the fact that it mentions contemporary events and personalities. But try to put yourself in the shoes of a creator and perceive whether it is possible not to mention the events of that time while writing about that same time. Time gets an example from time, but not from anything else. That's why it is necessary to distinguish between modernization and modernity. "Time" is characterized by high modernity, that is, it is consistent with time, so it breaths together with the moment, it means breathing harmoniously with the moment. There arises a question: is it breathing with the time, colonial time when Dictator Stalin used to be a ruler, or with the period of independence when we are analyzing the poem now? An literary work which has accomplished a certain literary level is considered modern for all periods; it is contemporaneous with all times. As for the poem "Time", it is about a continuous, absolute time, and time is a part of this time, if to look upon it with the view of eternity, it is only a moment of absolute time. That's why to include the poem "Time" in the list of modernization works is nothing but a lack of understanding of its essence. Naturally, "Time" is a simple on the surface, but difficult to understand in depth. The lines seem simple on the surface; their deep meaning cannot be perceived at once. As long as the meaning is not perceived, the poetic image is not formed in the mind. In some types of poems, the image is vividly seen, so the image and the meaning reveal themselves almost simultaneously, while in the "Time" it is necessary to digest the meaning of the word and the line first, and only then the figurative imagination begins to function. The poem "Time" is the property of an intellectual reader who has passed the obstacles of distracting simplicity, who has attempted to understand the deep hidden meanings in its background, and who can enjoy such attempts. Reading the "Time" superficially means to spend time in vain.

It is no wondered that globalization is a great test sent to mankind by its Creator. In this, humanity is subjected either to failure or to victory. We want and hope that it will come out victoriously.

Indeed, globalization can also be an opportunity for humanity to rise to a new level of consciousness. One of the great esoteric scholars of the modern world, Durunvalo Melchise, writes in his book "The Ancient Mystery of the Flower of Life": "Teachers who looked at the invisible realized that we, the Earth, would achieve the spiritual unity and rise to a higher level of consciousness"⁴.

So, global scientific and literary interpretations are worthy of the period of globalization. If the above interpretations partially meet such a requirement, we would consider ourselves lucky.

In the poet's work, poetry and prose, time presents the status of an literary and philosophical concept. In the poem "Time" the philosophy of time reveals itself in the form of the philosophy of the moment. Consequently, the philosophy of the moment can be said to be a special manifestation of the philosophy of the entire time.

⁴ Мельхеседек Д. Древняя тайна Цветка Жизни. М.: ООО Изд. "София", 2012. С.395.

Time dimension in poetry has a global scale, a philosophical-esoteric essence, and a quantum physical basis. These factors being synthesized would turn the poem "Time" into a timeless phenomenon, that is, it turns into an immortal literary phenomenon.

Conclusion

The philosophy of literature is the alchemy of words. As alchemy is the conversion of ordinary metals into gold and silver, so is the creation of miracles from a simple word, a "miracle status" (Navoi), is the alchemy of words.

In the global scientific and literary interpretation, a subjective factor, that is, the prestige of the researcher increases, the participation becomes active. But this objective factor does not diminish the importance of the literary text in the slightest degree. The original literary text will always remain as a basis for global scientific-literary interpretation. For a full-pledged global scientific-literary interpretation to take place, the two factors - the subjective, i.e. the researcher, and the objective, i.e. the text must be of the highest degree. If the researcher cannot handle the text or the analysis of the text is weak (actually there is no weak text, if it is weak, it is not text, and we use the word "text" because there is no other term) no matter how skilled the researcher is, he cannot go far. The expected result will not be achieved.

Since ancient times the global scientific and literary interpretation has long been known and existed as a concept, that is, a way of thinking and understanding, but it is of particular importance and actuality in the current globalization time of mankind.

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STUDY OF NUCLEAR STRUCTURE OF $^{45,47}\text{Ti}$ ISOTOPES BY USING OXBASH CODE

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Abstract

Titanium $^{47,45}_{22}\text{Ti}$ has 26 isotopes from ^{38}Ti to ^{71}Ti five of these isotopes stable like ^{46}Ti , ^{47}Ti , ^{48}Ti , ^{49}Ti , ^{50}Ti . titanium isotopes ^{45}Ti , ^{47}Ti have neutrons (N=23,25) with 5 to 7 nucleons outside of closed shell, shell model is utilized to determine the energy levels and B (E2) with use of the shell model code OXBASH for windows and the effective interactions F7MBZ and F742, with the spin-parity of the valence nucleons taken into account. The calculated energy levels and B(E2) values mostly agreed with the available experimental data.

Keywords: Energy levels , Shell model , OXBASH code , B (E2) .

1. Introduction

The nuclear shell model is just one of many that have been created to explain the nucleus [1], as well as certain additional characteristics like the spins, parities, and B(E2) . It provides the theoretical foundation for a microscopic description of nuclear properties that is primarily dependent on the utilization of effective interactions [2], There are a number of "standard" effective interactions, including the USD and Cohen-Kurath interactions for the p and SD shells [3]. in order to determine the nuclear structural characteristics of both ground and excitations according to the nuclear shell concept. Those states' wave functions are required , To obtain these wave functions, the shell-model program OXBASH is used. Titanium's nucleus structure was calculated using the Windows program OXBASH. with using the f_7 with (F7MBZ & F742) effective interactions [4] . Similarities exist between this model and the atomic shell model of electrons. Similar to how valence electrons outside of a closed shell can characterize atomic behavior and qualities, the value nucleons (protons or neutrons) situated in close-proximity shells with magic numbers (2,8,20,28,50,82, and 126) dictate the nuclear attributes of a nucleus. Highly stable nuclei with magic numbers have unique properties. Atomic behavior and attributes can be defined by the valence electrons that exist in an open shell. Highly stable nuclei with magic numbers have unique properties [5] . This work's goal is to investigate the decreased transition probabilities and level schemes for ^{45}Ti , ^{47}Ti , and odd isotopes use the most recent OXBASH for Windows version the energy levels of some ^{45}Ti states and ^{47}Ti Compared to the most recent data, the figures calculated in this paper show [6].

2. Theory

Traditional calculations using the shell model ,Typically, one would determine the energy levels using related to a closed shell as opposed to the system's overall energy, as well as for a solitary nucleon outside the doubly miraculous core. In this instance, it is assumed that energy is an eigenvalue of the

Hamiltonian H_0 . when the whole Hamiltonian is represented as and there are many nucleons beyond the core [7].

$$H = \sum_{k=1} H^o + \sum_{k \leq l} V_{kl} \quad \dots \dots (1)$$

Where $\sum_{k \leq l} V_{kl}$ is residual two-body interactions [8], Generally, a quantum mechanics solution to the Schrödinger steps to an equation have been essential [9]. so that Schrödinger equation can be expressed in writing.

$$H = |\psi_n \rangle = E_n |\psi_n \rangle \quad \dots \dots (2)$$

Where

$$H = H_o + H_1 \quad \dots \dots (3)$$

$$H_o = \sum_{i=1}^A (T_o + U_i) \quad \dots \dots (4)$$

$$H_o = \sum_{i < j}^{i=1}^{A-1} (V_{ij}^{NN} - \sum_{i=1}^A U_i) \quad \dots \dots (5)$$

To disentangle [10] the nuclear Hamiltonian one-body potentials have been proposed as the integral of one-body terms. Which characterizes the nucleons' free-moving nature plus the interaction H_1 [11]. The Schrödinger equation can be solved using the mean field potential to obtain the single-particle wave functions in the extreme single-particle shell model, and the resulting quantum numbers (n, l, j) for the energy levels of the particles. The quantum number (n) denotes the quantity of nodes in the radial wave function. The orbital angular momentum is denoted by the symbol l . Where j is the overall angular momentum brought about by the coupling of the intrinsic nucleon spin = $\frac{1}{2}$. The two options to the orbital angular momentum $\square = \pm 1/2$ [12].

3. Calculations and Discussion

The calculations were performed in the nuclear shell model f7 with the windows program OXBASH. An m-scheme Slater determinant Basis is used in the code. A projection approach is used to create wave functions with good angular momentum J and isospin T [13]. Shell model calculation of $^{45,47}Ti$ isotopes were carried out for the space model $(1d3/2, \text{ and } 1F7/2)$, for the aforementioned isotopes, with neutrons $(N=23 \text{ and } 25)$ above the near ^{40}Ca core In addition to 5 nucleons outside core for ^{45}Ti and 7 nucleons outside core for ^{47}Ti [14], and effective interactions F7MBZ, F742.

3.1 Levels of energy

The purpose of this investigation is to Determine the nuclei that are in close proximity to ^{45}Ti because of the significant role that these nuclei play in recent developments in astrophysical applications. The determined energy levels and presented low-lying state experimental results for odd-odd nuclei. However, On the left, you can see the results of our calculations and right-hand experimental info for any band [9].

3.1.1 Energy levels of ^{45}Ti

For ^{45}Ti isotope using (F7MBZ) interactions is shown in the table1. When measured against the experimental data that is presented, Through our theoretical calculations, the energy value of the ground level was obtained as 0, and its angular momentum was $(5/2^-)$ while the momentum was $(7/2^-)$ in the available practical results, but in our theoretical calculations we obtained a value of (0.274) MeV

with the same angular momentum ($7/2^-$). A good agreement was obtained for the values of the practical energies (1.35349, 1.46824, 3.01537, 4.3449) MeV corresponding to the angular momentum ($9/2^-$, $11/2^-$, $15/2^-$, $19/2^-$,) when compared with the calculated theoretical values, The total momentum and parity of the unconfirmed practical energies (1.5217, 2.0147, 2.500, 4.723, 5.1800, 10.1535) MeV was confirmed for the angular momentum ($3/2^-$, $3/2^-$, $7/2^-$, $7/2^-$, $3/2^-$, $25/2^-$) are confirmed when compared with the calculated theoretical values, And The experimental energy value (2.5314, 4.8552, 5.2399, 7.3420) MeV was confirmed for angular momentum ($5/2^+$, $17/2^+$, $17/2^+$, $23/2^+$) with negative parity In our calculations, We found the values of energies for a specific angular momentum close to the values of the practical energies (3.200, 5.540, 6.0067, 7.8307, 9.6435) that have no specific angular momentum, and thus we expect that its angular momentum is the theoretically calculated momentum ($9/2^-$, $15/2^-$, $15/2^-$, $15/2^-$, $11/2^-$). Through our calculations, we noticed that there are sixty two levels with total angular momentum and parity that were not matched by any available practical value.

Table(1): Excitation energy predicted by (F7MBZ) interactions and observed excitation energies for the ^{45}Ti nucleus are compared.

Theoretical values for F7MBZ		Experimental values		Theoretical values for F7MBZ		Experimental values	
J^π	E (MeV)	E (MeV)	J^π	J^π	E (MeV)	E (MeV)	J^π
5/2 ₁ ⁻	0	0.000	7/2 ₁ ⁻	23/2 ₁ ⁻	6.912	7.3420	(23/2 ₁ ⁺)
7/2 ₁ ⁻	0.274	-----	-----	9/2 ₆ ⁻	6.973	-----	-----
9/2 ₁ ⁻	1.705	1.35359	9/2 ₁ ⁻	15/2 ₄ ⁻	7.06	-----	-----
11/2 ₁ ⁻	1.763	1.46824	11/2 ₁ ⁻	17/2 ₃ ⁻	7.289	-----	-----
3/2 ₁ ⁻	1.966	1.5217	5/2 ₁ ⁻ to 9/2 ₁ ⁻	11/2 ₆ ⁻	7.333	-----	-----
3/2 ₂ ⁻	2.658	2.0147	5/2 ₁ ⁻ to 9/2 ₁ ⁻	17/2 ₄ ⁻	7.343	-----	-----
7/2 ₂ ⁻	2.769	2.500	5/2 ₁ ⁻ , 7/2 ₁ ⁻	5/2 ₆ ⁻	7.395	-----	-----
5/2 ₂ ⁻	3.223	2.5314	1/2 ₁ ⁻ , 3/2 ₁ ⁻ , 5/2 ₁ ⁺	9/2 ₇ ⁻	7.450	-----	-----
15/2 ₁ ⁻	3.561	3.01537	15/2 ₁ ⁻	13/2 ₆ ⁻	7.549	-----	-----
9/2 ₂ ⁻	3.748	3.200	-----	11/2 ₇ ⁻	7.662	-----	-----
7/2 ₃ ⁻	3.871	-----	-----	15/2 ₅ ⁻	7.664	-----	-----
13/2 ₁ ⁻	3.943	-----	-----	19/2 ₃ ⁻	7.726	-----	-----
1/2 ₁ ⁻	3.957	-----	-----	15/2 ₆ ⁻	7.892	7.8307	-----
17/2 ₁ ⁻	3.982	4.8552	(17/2 ⁺)	13/2 ₇ ⁻	7.918	-----	-----
9/2 ₃ ⁻	4.385	-----	-----	11/2 ₈ ⁻	8.135	-----	-----
11/2 ₂ ⁻	4.426	-----	-----	21/2 ₂ ⁻	8.162	-----	-----
5/2 ₃ ⁻	4.612	-----	-----	27/2 ₁ ⁻	8.232	-----	-----
19/2 ₁ ⁻	4.628	4.3449	19/2 ⁻	7/2 ₈ ⁻	8.401	-----	-----
13/2 ₂ ⁻	4.716	-----	-----	9/2 ₈ ⁻	8.576	-----	-----
7/2 ₄ ⁻	4.745	4.723	(7/2 ⁻)	17/2 ₅ ⁻	8.600	-----	-----
11/2 ₃ ⁻	4.909	-----	-----	9/2 ₉ ⁻	8.783	-----	-----
9/2 ₄ ⁻	5.483	-----	-----	13/2 ₈ ⁻	8.826	-----	-----
15/2 ₂ ⁻	5.532	5.540	-----	23/2 ₂ ⁻	8.828	-----	-----
11/2 ₄ ⁻	5.549	-----	-----	19/2 ₄ ⁻	8.837	-----	-----
3/2 ₃ ⁻	5.636	5.180	1/2 ⁻ , 3/2 ⁻	15/2 ₇ ⁻	8.962	-----	-----
13/2 ₃ ⁻	5.837	-----	-----	17/2 ₆ ⁻	9.124	-----	-----
17/2 ₂ ⁻	5.925	5.2399	(17/2 ⁺)	5/2 ₇ ⁻	9.216	-----	-----
9/2 ₅ ⁻	5.951	-----	-----	1/2 ₃ ⁻	9.238	-----	-----
15/2 ₃ ⁻	6.000	6.0067	-----	3/2 ₅ ⁻	9.242	-----	-----
11/2 ₅ ⁻	6.037	-----	-----	25/2 ₁ ⁻	9.276	10.1535	(25/2 ₁ ⁻)
5/2 ₄ ⁻	6.074	-----	-----	11/2 ₉ ⁻	9.644	9.6435	-----
7/2 ₅ ⁻	6.159	-----	-----	3/2 ₆ ⁻	9.786	-----	-----
5/2 ₅ ⁻	6.313	-----	-----	7/2 ₉ ⁻	9.944	-----	-----
13/2 ₄ ⁻	6.399	-----	-----	15/2 ₈ ⁻	10.069	-----	-----
19/2 ₂ ⁻	6.433	-----	-----	13/2 ₉ ⁻	10.116	-----	-----
7/2 ₆ ⁻	6.676	-----	-----	21/2 ₃ ⁻	10.169	-----	-----
3/2 ₄ ⁻	6.722	-----	-----	9/2 ₁₀ ⁻	10.245	-----	-----
1/2 ₂ ⁻	6.764	-----	-----	5/2 ₈ ⁻	10.413	-----	-----
21/2 ₁ ⁻	6.814	-----	-----	11/2 ₁₀ ⁻	19/2 ₅ ⁻	10.806	-----
13/2 ₅ ⁻	6.882	-----	-----	17/2 ₁ ⁻	7/2 ₁₀ ⁻	10.985	-----
7/2 ₇ ⁻	6.899	-----	-----	5/2 ₂ ⁻	11.147	-----	-----

For ⁴⁵Ti isotope using (F742) interactions is shown in the table2 . When measured against the experimental data that is presented ,Through our theoretical calculations, the energy value of the ground level was obtained as 0, and its angular momentum was ((5/2-) while the momentum was (7/2-)) in the available practical results, but in our theoretical calculations we obtained a value of (0.093) MeV with the same angular momentum (7/2-). A good agreement was obtained for the values of the practical energies (0.03653, 1.35349, 1.46824 , 3.01537 ,4.3449 ,6.1630 ,7.1434) MeV corresponding to the angular momentum (3/2-1 , 9/2-1, 11/2-1, 15/2-1, 19/2-1 , 23/2-1 , 27/2-1) when compared with

the calculated theoretical values , The total momentum and parity of the unconfirmed practical energies (2.0147,2.500 , 4.723 , 5.180) MeV was confirmed for the angular momentum ($3/2_{-2}$, $7/2_{-2}$, $7/2_{-5}$, $1/2_{-2}$)are confirmed when compared with the calculated theoretical values , And The experimental energy value(2.5314, 2.8494 ,2.9329, 3.9376 ,5.030 ,6.7579, 7.3420 ,8.2892) MeV was confirmed for angular momentum ($5/2_{+2}$, $1/2_{+1}$, $13/2_{+1}$, $11/2_{+2}$, $5/2_{+5}$, $21/2_{+2}$, $23/2_{+2}$, $25/2_{+2}$) with negative parity In our calculations, The total angular momentum has been determined for the values of the practical energies for which parity (2.8494 , 3.9376) has not been determined corresponding to the angular momentum ($1/2_1$, $11/2_2$) when compared with the available practical values, We found the values of energies for a specific angular momentum close to the values of the practical energies (3.156, 3.200 ,5.540 , 6.0067 ,7.8307 ,9.6435) that have no specific angular momentum, and thus we expect that its angular momentum is the theoretically calculated momentum ($9/2_{-2}$, $7/2_{-2}$, $3/2_{-4}$, $5/2_{-6}$, $7/2_{-9}$, $19/2_{-5}$). Through our calculations, we noticed that there are fifty five levels with total angular momentum and parity that were not matched by any available practical value. Table(1): Excitation energy predicted by (F742) interactions and observed excitation energies for the ^{45}Ti nucleus are compared .

Theoretical values for F742		Experimental values		Theoretical values for F742		Experimental values	
J^π	E (MeV)	E (MeV)	J^π	J^π	E (MeV)	E (MeV)	J^π
$5/2_1$	0	0.000	$7/2_{1^-}$	$5/2_6$	6.010	6.0067	$(23/2_{1^+})$
$7/2_1$	0.093	-----	-----	$15/2_4$	6.137	-----	-----
$3/2_1$	1.526	0.03653	$3/2_{1^-}$	$9/2_7$	6.137	-----	-----
$9/2_1$	1.529	1.35349	$9/2_{1^-}$	$11/2_6$	6.253	-----	-----
$11/2_1$	1.571	1.46824	$11/2_{1^-}$	$21/2_1$	6.338	-----	-----
$3/2_2$	2.231	2.0147	$3/2_{1^-}$ to $9/2_{1^-}$	$13/2_6$	6.415	-----	-----
$7/2_2$	2.365	2.500	$5/2_{1^-}$, $7/2_{1^-}$	$11/2_7$	6.432	-----	-----
$5/2_2$	2.772	2.5314	$1/2^-$, $3/2^-$, $5/2$ (+)	$17/2_3$	6.478	-----	-----
$9/2_2$	3.136	3.1560	-----	$17/2_4$	6.505	-----	-----
$7/2_3$	3.229	3.200	-----	$23/2_1$	6.522	6.1630	$23/2^-$
$15/2_1$	3.236	3.01537	$15/2^-$	$13/2_7$	6.635	-----	-----
$1/2_1$	3.290	2.8494	$1/2^-$, $3/2^-$, $5/2$ (+)	$15/2_5$	6.644	-----	-----
$13/2_1$	3.490	2.9329	$(13/2^+)$	$11/2_8$	6.73	-----	-----
$11/2_2$	3.594	3.9376	$(11/2$ to $15/2)$	$15/2_6$	6.778	-----	-----
$9/2_3$	3.626	-----	-----	$7/2_8$	6.842	-----	-----
$17/2_1$	3.720	-----	-----	$19/2_3$	6.927	-----	-----

5/2 ₃	3.752	-----	-----	9/2 ₈	7.054	-----	-----
7/2 ₄	3.998	-----	-----	9/2 ₉	7.173	-----	-----
13/2 ₂	4.113	-----	-----	17/2 ₅	7.309	-----	-----
11/2 ₃	4.194	-----	-----	1/2 ₃	7.329	-----	-----
19/2 ₁	4.222	4.3449	-----	3/2 ₅	7.341	-----	-----
15/2 ₄	4.551	-----	-----	5/2 ₇	7.393	-----	-----
3/2 ₃	4.657	-----	-----	21/2 ₂	7.403	6.7579	(21/2 ⁺)
11/2 ₄	4.684	-----	-----	13/2 ₈	7.425	-----	-----
9/2 ₄	4.694	-----	-----	15/2 ₇	7.526	-----	-----
5/2 ₄	4.844	-----	-----	19/2 ₄	7.695	-----	-----
9/2 ₅	4.916	-----	-----	3/2 ₆	7.809	-----	-----
7/2 ₅	5.096	4.723	(7/2 ₁) ⁻	11/2 ₉	7.826	-----	-----
5/2 ₅	5.111	5.030	(3/2 ⁺ , 5/2 ⁺)	17/2 ₆	7.857	-----	-----
13/2 ₃	5.148	-----	-----	27/2 ₁	7.874	7.1434	27/2 ₁ ⁻
11/2 ₅	5.223	-----	-----	7/2 ₉	7.933	7.8307	-----
1/2 ₂	5.252	5.180	1/2 ⁻ , 3/2 ⁻	23/2 ₂	8.037	7.3420	(23/2 ⁺)
15/2 ₃	5.269	-----	-----	9/2 ₁₀	8.185	-----	-----
17/2 ₂	5.316	-----	-----	5/2 ₈	8.259	-----	-----
13/2 ₄	5.366	-----	-----	13/2 ₉	8.282	-----	-----
7/2 ₆	5.389	-----	-----	15/2 ₈	8.380	-----	-----
3/2 ₄	5.521	5.540	-----	25/2 ₁	8.453	8.2892	(25/2 ⁺)
7/2 ₇	5.742	-----	-----	7/2 ₁₀	8.707	-----	-----
9/2 ₆	5.846	-----	-----	21/2 ₃	8.845	-----	-----
19/2 ₂	5.861	-----	-----	11/2 ₁₀	8.992	10.985	-----
13/2 ₅	5.862	-----	-----	19/2 ₂	9.153	9.6435	-----

3.1.2 Energy levels of ⁴⁷Ti

For ⁴⁷Ti isotope using (F7MBZ) interactions is shown in the table3 . When measured against the experimental data that is presented, Through our theoretical calculations, the energy value of the ground level was obtained as 0, and its angular momentum was (7/2⁻) while the momentum was (5/2⁻) in the available practical results, but in our theoretical calculations we obtained a value of (0.002) MeV with the same angular momentum (5/2⁻). A good agreement was obtained for the values of the practical energies (1.54965, 1.44425, 1.79380 ,2.1632 ,2.6194, 2.74887,2.5482 , 3.99394 , 4.49411, 3.8271, 4.67290 , 8.0051) MeV corresponding to the angular momentum (3/2⁻¹, 11/2⁻¹, 1/2⁻¹, 3/2⁻², 7/2⁻², 15/2⁻², 3/2⁻³,15/2⁻², 19/2⁻¹, 7/2⁻⁵, 17/2⁻², 27/2⁻¹) when compared with the calculated theoretical values , The total momentum and parity of the unconfirmed practical energies (2.4062, 2.7576, 2.6823 , 2.8095, 3.7271 ,3.780, 4.095, 5.433, 6.067, 6.3664) MeV was confirmed for the angular momentum (9/2⁻², 7/2⁻³,11/2⁻³, 5/2⁻³, 13/2⁻², 9/2⁻⁴,1/2⁻², 3/2⁻⁵, 1/2⁻³, 21/2⁻¹) are confirmed when compared with the calculated theoretical values , The total angular momentum has been determined for the values of the practical energies for which parity (3.7018) has not been determined corresponding to the angular momentum (7/2₄) when compared with the available practical values. , We found the values of energies for a specific angular momentum close to the values of the practical

energies (1.67, 2.695, 2.8002, 3.724, 4.04, 3.961, 4.112, 4.243, 4.264, 4.303, 4.518, 4.541, 4.553, 4.708, 4.898, 5.102, 5.125, 5.195, 5.301, 5.372, 5.451, 5.478, 5.635, 5.702, 5.774, 6.095, 6.129, 6.195, 6.209, 6.234, 6.265, 6.304, 6.364, 6.402, 6.449, 6.474, 6.514, 6.554, 6.624, 6.645, 6.823, 6.854, 6.882, 6.903, 6.917, 6.002, 7.038, 7.123, 7.205, 7.225, 7.4806) that have no specific angular momentum, and thus we expect that its angular momentum is the theoretically calculated momentum ($5/2^-$, $11/2^-$, $9/2^-$, $17/2^-$, $1, 5/2^-$, $15/2^-$, $11/2^-$, $9/2^-$, $3/2^-$, $13/2^-$, $13/2^-$, $11/2^-$, $5/2^-$, $15/2^-$, $9/2^-$, $13/2^-$, $19/2^-$, $11/2^-$, $9/2^-$, $5/2^-$, $7/2^-$, $7/2^-$, $9/2^-$, $15/2^-$, $11/2^-$, $13/2^-$, $19/2^-$, $7/2^-$, $5/2^-$, $17/2^-$, $23/2^-$, $11/2^-$, $15/2^-$, $9/2^-$, $7/2^-$, $11/2^-$, $3/2^-$, $15/2^-$, $13/2^-$, $9/2^-$, $5/2^-$, $15/2^-$, $17/2^-$, $13/2^-$, $5/2^-$, $11/2^-$, $19/2^-$, $17/2^-$, $13/2^-$, $5/2^-$, $23/2^-$). Through our calculations, we noticed that there are nineteen levels with total angular momentum and parity that were not matched by any available practical value.

Table(3): Excitation energy predicted by (F7MBZ) interactions and observed excitation energies for the ^{47}Ti nucleus are compared.

Theoretical values for F7MBZ		Experimental values		Theoretical values for F7MBZ		Experimental values	
J^π	E (MeV)	E (MeV)	J^π	J^π	E (MeV)	E (MeV)	J^π
$7/2_1$	0	0	$5/2^-$	$3/2_5$	5.798	5.433	$1/2^-$, $3/2^-$
$5/2_1$	0.002	-----	-----	$21/2_1$	5.833	5.19744	$21/2^-$
$3/2_1$	0.801	1.54965	$3/2^-$	$1/2_3$	5.903	6.067	$(1/2^-, 3/2^-)$
$11/2_1$	1.213	1.44425	$11/2^-$	$13/2_6$	6.006	6.095	-----
$1/2_1$	1.447	1.79380	$11/2_1^-$	$19/2_3$	6.058	6.129	-----
$5/2_2$	1.548	1.670	-----	$7/2_8$	6.106	6.195	-----
$9/2_1$	1.582	-----	-----	$5/2_7$	6.261	6.209	-----
$9/2_2$	2.131	2.4062	$(9/2^-)$	$17/2_3$	6.277	6.234	-----
$3/2_2$	2.41	2.1632	$3/2^-$	$23/2_1$	6.285	6.265	-----
$7/2_2$	2.495	2.6194	$7/2^-$	$11/2_8$	6.319	6.304	-----
$15/2_1$	2.577	2.74887	$15/2^-$	$15/2_6$	6.388	6.364	-----
$11/2_2$	2.604	2.6950	-----	$9/2_9$	6.442	6.402	-----
$9/2_3$	2.805	2.8002	-----	$7/2_9$	6.458	6.449	-----
$7/2_3$	2.872	2.7576	$7/2$ to $13/2^-$	$11/2_9$	6.459	6.474	-----
$3/2_3$	2.98	2.9800	$3/2^-$	$3/2_6$	6.55	6.514	-----
$11/2_3$	3.172	2.68230	$11/2(-)$	$15/2_7$	6.774	6.554	-----
$5/2_3$	3.209	2.8095	$5/2^-, 7/2^-, 9/2^-$	$13/2_7$	6.835	6.624	-----
$13/2_1$	3.365	-----	-----	$9/2_{10}$	6.844	6.645	-----
$15/2_2$	3.547	3.99394	$15/2^-$	$5/2_8$	6.85	6.823	-----
$13/2_2$	3.577	3.7271	$(13/2^-)$	$15/2_8$	6.869	6.854	-----

17/2 ₁	3.643	3.724	-----		17/2 ₄	6.886	6.882	-----	For
9/2 ₄	3.804	3.7800	3/2(-) to 9/2-		13/2 ₈	6.893	6.903	-----	
5/2 ₄	4.021	4.040	-----		21/2 ₂	6.949	6.3664	(21/2-)	
15/2 ₃	4.082	3.961	-----		5/2 ₉	6.967	6.9170	-----	
7/2 ₄	4.129	3.7018	7/2,9/2, 3/2,5/2-		11/2 ₁₀	7.037	7.002	-----	
11/2 ₄	4.138	4.112	-----		19/2 ₄	7.194	7.038	-----	
9/2 ₅	4.242	4.243	-----		17/2 ₅	7.224	7.123	-----	
3/2 ₄	4.279	4.264	-----		13/2 ₉	7.242	7.205	-----	
1/2 ₁	4.29	4.095	1/2-, 3/2-		5/2 ₁₀	7.293	7.225	-----	
13/2 ₃	4.321	4.303	-----		17/2 ₆	7.488	-----	-----	
19/2 ₁	4.336	4.49411	19/2-		3/2 ₇	7.501	-----	-----	
13/2 ₄	4.410	4.518	1/2-, 3/2-		21/2 ₃	7.582	-----	-----	
7/2 ₅	4.538	3.8271	7/2-		7/2 ₁₀	7.637	-----	-----	
11/2 ₅	4.595	4.541	-----		15/2 ₉	7.659	-----	-----	
5/2 ₅	4.61	4.553	-----		19/2 ₅	7.833	-----	-----	
15/2 ₄	4.967	4.708	-----		23/2 ₂	7.867	-----	-----	
9/2 ₆	4.984	4.898	-----		23/2 ₃	8.101	7.4806	-----	
13/2 ₅	5.123	5.102	-----		25/2 ₁	8.169	-----	-----	
19/2 ₂	5.147	5.125	-----		17/2 ₇	8.211	-----	-----	
11/2 ₆	5.206	5.195	-----		15/2 ₁₀	8.224	-----	-----	
9/2 ₇	5.297	5.301	-----		1/2 ₄	8.269	-----	-----	
5/2 ₆	5.335	5.372	-----		13/2 ₁₀	8.334	-----	-----	
17/2 ₂	5.46	4.6729	-----		19/2 ₆	8.523	-----	-----	
7/2 ₆	5.462	5.451	-----		27/2 ₁	8.703	8.0051	27/2-	
7/2 ₇	5.506	5.478	-----		3/2 ₈	8.713	-----	-----	
9/2 ₈	5.637	5.635	-----		21/2 ₄	9.578	-----	-----	
15/2 ₅	5.746	5.702	-----		17/2 ₈	10.135	-----	-----	
11/2 ₇	5.768	5.774	-----		3/2 ₉	11.911	-----	-----	

⁴⁷Ti isotope using (F742) interactions is shown in the table3 . When measured against the experimental data that is presented , Through our theoretical calculations, the energy value of the ground level was obtained as 0, and its angular momentum was (7/2-) while the momentum was (5/2-) in the available practical results, but in our theoretical calculations we obtained a value of (0.126)MeV with the same angular momentum (5/2-). A good agreement was obtained for the values of the practical energies (1.44425, 1.79380 ,1.25209 ,2.1632 , 2.74887, 2.5482 , 3.28773 ,3.99394 , 4.49411, 4.67290 ,5.19744 , 6.0886 , 8.0051) MeV corresponding to the angular momentum (11/2-₁, 1/2-₁, 9/2-₁, 3/2-₂, 15/2-₁, 3/2-₃,13/2-₁, 15/2-₂, 19/2-₁, 17/2-₂, 21/2-₁, 23/2-₁ , 27/2-₁) when compared with the calculated theoretical values , The total momentum and parity of the unconfirmed practical energies (1.2507 , 2.4062, 2.2971 ,2.5482 , 2.7576 , 2.8463 , 2.8095 , 3.780 , 3.4845, 5.433, 5.013, 5.540, 6.3664, 5.615 , 6.3664 , 6.333) MeV was confirmed for the angular momentum (3/2-₁, 9/2-₂,7/2-₂, 3/2-₃, 7/2-₃ , 11/2-₃,5/2₃- ,5/2-₄, 11/2-₄,3/2-₄, 3/2₅- , 1/2-₃, 3/2-₆ , 3/2-₇, 21/2-₂,3/2-₈) are confirmed

when compared with the calculated theoretical values , The total angular momentum has been determined for the values of the practical energies for which parity (2.668 ,3.3689 ,3.4005) has not been determined corresponding to the angular momentum (9/2₃, 9/2₄, 13/2₂) when compared with the available practical values , We found the values of energies for a specific angular momentum close to the values of the practical energies (1.67 ,3.654 ,3.724 , 3.839 ,3.961 ,3.889 ,3.961 ,4.303 , 4.518 , 4.541 ,4.553 ,4.605 ,4.670 ,4.708 ,4.811, 4.876 ,4.898 ,5.043 ,5.102 ,5.195 ,5.301 , 5.372 ,5.451, 5.478 ,5.635, 5.67 ,5.702 ,5.746 , 5.755 , 5.774 ,5.836 ,5.872 ,5.937 ,6.013 ,6.095 ,6.129 , 6.195 ,6.206 , 6.234 ,6.265 ,6.304 , 6.364, 6.387 ,6.402 ,6.449 , 6.514 ,6.787 ,7.018 ,7.038 ,7.095 , 7.123 ,7.141 ,7.205 ,7.225) that have no specific angular momentum, and thus we expect that its angular momentum is the theoretically calculated momentum (5/2₂, 17/2₁, 15/2₃, 9/2₅, 13/2₃, 13/2₄, 11/2₅, 9/2₆, 13/2₅, 15/2₄, 11/2₆ , 5/2₆, 9/2₇, 7/2₆ , 7/2₇ , 9/2₈ , 19/2₂ , 11/2₇, 7/2₈ ,15/2₅, 5/2₇ , 13/2₆ , 9/2₉ , 7/2₉ , 11/2₈ , 11/2₉, 5/2₈, 19/2₃ , 15/2₆, 17/2₃, 5/2₉ , 9/2₁₀ , 15/2₇, 13/2₇, 5/2₁₀ , 15/2₁₀, 11/2₁₀ , 13/2₈ , 17/2₄ ,7/2₁₀ , 13/2₉ , 17/2₅, 17/2₆ , 19/2₄, 15/2₉ ,1/2₄ , 21/2₃, 13/2₁₀ , 19/2₅ , 15/2₁₀, 17/2₇, 23/2₂, 19/2₆, 23/2₃). Through our calculations, we noticed that there are nine levels with total angular momentum and parity that were not matched by any available practical value.

Table(4): Excitation energy predicted by (F742) interactions and observed excitation energies for the ⁴⁷Ti nucleus are compared.

Theoretical values for F742		Experimental values		Theoretical values for F742		Experimental values	
J^π	E (MeV)	E (MeV)	J^π	J^π	E (MeV)	E (MeV)	J^π
7/2 ₁	0	0	5/2 ⁻	7/2 ₈	5.143	5.102	1/2 ⁻ , 3/2 ⁻
5/2 ₁	0.126	-----	-----	17/2 ₂	5.148	4.6729	17/2 ⁻
3/2 ₁	0.826	1.2507	(1/2 ⁻ , 3/2 ⁻)	15/2 ₅	5.223	5.195	(1/2 ⁻ , 3/2 ⁻)
11/2 ₁	1.276	1.44425	11/2 ⁻	5/2 ₇	5.374	5.301	-----
5/2 ₂	1.428	1.670	-----	13/2 ₆	5.391	5.372	-----
1/2 ₁	1.517	1.7938	1/2 ⁻	9/2 ₉	5.415	5.451	-----
9/2 ₁	1.636	1.25209	9/2 ⁻	3/2 ₆	5.427	5.540	1/2 ⁻ , 3/2 ⁻
3/2 ₂	2	2.1632	3/2 ⁻	7/2 ₉	5.479	5.478	-----
9/2 ₂	2.016	2.4062	(9/2 ⁻)	11/2 ₈	5.48	5.635	-----
7/2 ₂	2.284	2.2971	5/2 ⁻ ,7/2 ⁻	11/2 ₉	5.603	5.670	-----
11/2 ₂	2.349	2.6823	11/2 ⁻ (-)	5/2 ₈	5.607	5.702	-----
15/2 ₁	2.546	2.74887	15/2 ⁻	21/2 ₁	5.687	5.19744	21/2 ⁻
3/2 ₃	2.547	2.5482	3/2 ⁻	19/2 ₃	5.753	5.746	-----
9/2 ₃	2.549	2.668	9/2 ⁻ , 13/2 ⁻	15/2 ₆	5.758	5.755	-----
7/2 ₃	2.62	2.7576	7/2 ⁻ to 13/2 ⁻	17/2 ₃	5.759	5.774	-----
11/2 ₃	2.921	2.8463	5/2 ⁻ to 11/2 ⁻	5/2 ₉	5.766	5.836	-----
5/2 ₃	2.926	2.8095	5/2 ⁻ , 7/2 ⁻ , 9/2 ⁻	9/2 ₁₀	5.892	5.872	-----

13/2 ₁	3.219	3.28773	13/2 ⁻		15/2 ₇	5.933	5.937	-----	3.2
9/2 ₄	3.261	3.3689	7/2 ⁻ , 9/2 ⁻ , 11/2 ⁻		13/2 ₇	6.019	6.013	-----	
15/2 ₂	3.351	3.99394	15/2 ⁻		5/2 ₁₀	6.031	6.095	-----	
13/2 ₂	3.389	3.4005	7/2 ⁻ to 13/2 ⁻		15/2 ₈	6.054	6.129	-----	
5/2 ₄	3.405	3.780	3/2 ⁽⁻⁾ to 9/2 ⁻		11/2 ₁₀	6.076	6.195	-----	
17/2 ₁	3.562	3.654	-----		13/2 ₈	6.136	6.209	-----	
1/2 ₂	3.595	-----	-----		23/2 ₁	6.14	6.0886	23/2 ⁻	
11/2 ₄	3.646	3.7018	7/2 ⁻ , 9/2 ⁻ , 3/2 ⁻ , 5/2 ⁻		3/2 ₇	6.234	5.615	1/2 ⁻ , 3/2 ⁻	
15/2 ₃	3.713	3.724	-----		17/2 ₄	6.237	6.234	-----	
3/2 ₄	3.714	3.4845	(3/2 ⁻)		7/2 ₁₀	6.289	6.265	-----	
9/2 ₅	3.738	3.839	-----		13/2 ₉	6.296	6.304	-----	
7/2 ₄	3.738	-----	-----		17/2 ₅	6.452	6.364	-----	
5/2 ₅	3.943	-----	-----		21/2 ₂	6.554	6.3664	(21/2 ⁻)	
13/2 ₃	3.969	3.961	-----		17/2 ₆	6.64	6.397	-----	
7/2 ₅	3.982	-----	-----		19/2 ₄	6.667	6.402	-----	
13/2 ₄	4.115	3.889	-----		15/2 ₉	6.769	6.449	-----	
11/2 ₅	4.149	3.961	-----		1/2 ₄	6.819	6.514	-----	
19/2 ₁	4.2	4.49411	19/2 ⁻		3/2 ₈	6.999	6.333	1/2 ⁻ , 3/2 ⁻	
9/2 ₆	4.478	4.303	-----		21/2 ₃	7.011	6.787	-----	
13/2 ₅	4.567	4.518	-----		13/2 ₁₀	7.088	7.018	-----	
15/2 ₄	4.573	4.541	-----		19/2 ₅	7.133	7.038	-----	
11/2 ₆	4.588	4.553	-----		17/2 ₁₀	7.19	7.095	-----	
5/2 ₆	4.611	4.605	-----		17/2 ₇	7.275	7.123	-----	
9/2 ₇	4.647	4.670	-----		23/2 ₂	7.326	7.141	-----	
7/2 ₆	4.684	4.708	-----		19/2 ₆	7.596	7.205	-----	
7/2 ₇	4.818	4.811	-----		23/2 ₃	7.622	7.225	-----	
3/2 ₅	4.858	5.433	1/2 ⁻ , 3/2 ⁻		25/2 ₁	7.83	-----	-----	
9/2 ₈	4.927	4.876	-----		27/2 ₁	8.386	8.0051	27/2 ⁻	
19/2 ₂	4.929	4.898	-----		21/2 ₄	8.55	-----	-----	
1/2 ₃	4.961	5.013	1/2 ⁻ , 3/2 ⁻		17/2 ₈	8.673	-----	-----	
11/2 ₇	5.133	5.043	-----		3/2 ₉	9.461	-----	-----	

B(E2) Calculations :

3.2.1 B(E2) for ⁴⁵Ti

Within the nuclear shell model, (F7MBZ & F742) projected that the chance of an electric quadruple transition B (E2) for ⁴⁵Ti would be lower. The transition probability was determined for each in-band transition assuming a pure E2 transition by using the harmonic oscillator potential (HO, b), Where $b < 0$. Core polarization effects have been taken into account by selecting the effective charges for the proton ($e_p = 1.5e$) and the neutron ($e_n = 1.5e$). Table 5 ⁴⁵Ti was calculated with the help of the efficient interactions of F7MBZ and F742. Over all, there appears to be a fair amount of concordance between the computed results and the available experimental data.

Table 5 : the B (E2) values for ^{44}Ti ground-state band. They use e^2fm^4 units, which match the experimental results.

J_i^-	\rightarrow	J_f^-	Theory B(E2) ($\text{e}^2 \text{fm}^4$)		Exp. B(E2) ($\text{e}^2 \text{fm}^4$) $e_p = 1.5e$, $e_n = 1.5e$ $b = 2.266 \text{ fm}$
			F7MBZ	F742	
3/2	\rightarrow	7/2	285.7	301.9	285.227
9/2	\rightarrow	5/2	226.7	216.4	101.731
9/2	\rightarrow	7/2	410	395.6	152.121
11/2	\rightarrow	7/2	475.7	479.6	171.136
15/2	\rightarrow	11/2	552.5	537.2	95.076
17/2	\rightarrow	13/2	3.365	21.99	96.977
19/2	\rightarrow	15/2	248.3	222.5	18.064
23/2	\rightarrow	19/2	197.8	185.4	81.765
27/2	\rightarrow	23/2	154.6	155.8	59.898

3.2.2 B(E2) for ^{47}Ti

Within the nuclear shell model, (F7MBZ & F742) projected that the chance of an electric quadruple transition B (E2) for ^{47}Ti would be lower. The transition probability was determined for each in-band transition assuming a pure E2 transition by using the harmonic oscillator potential (HO, b), Where $b < 0$. Core polarization effects have been taken into account by selecting the effective charges for the proton ($e_p = 1.5e$) and the neutron ($e_n = 0.816e$). Table 6 ^{47}Ti was calculated with the help of the efficient interactions of F7MBZ and F742. Over all, there appears to be a fair amount of concordance between the computed results and the available experimental data.

Table 6 : the B (E2) values for ^{47}Ti ground-state band. They use e^2fm^4 units, which match the experimental results.

J_i^-	\rightarrow	J_f^-	Theory B(E2) ($\text{e}^2 \text{fm}^4$)		Exp. B(E2) ($\text{e}^2 \text{fm}^4$) $e_p = 1.5e$, $e_n = 0.816e$ $b = 2.171 \text{ fm}$
			F7MBZ	F742	
7/2	\rightarrow	5/2	244.2	240.4	244.758
9/2	\rightarrow	7/2	66.64	87.21	186.016
9/2	\rightarrow	5/2	221.6	197.7	68.532
11/2	\rightarrow	9/2	78.83	80.56	393.710
11/2	\rightarrow	7/2	311.1	302	166.435
3/2	\rightarrow	7/2	277.4	258.8	38.182
3/2	\rightarrow	5/2	254.5	239.8	3.231
1/2	\rightarrow	3/2	119.8	107.5	9790.320
1/2	\rightarrow	5/2	199.6	177.6	11.748
3/2 ₂	\rightarrow	7/2	61.38	66.62	35.245

(9/2)	→	5/2	221.6	197.7	26.434
15/2	→	11/2	268.9	254.5	127.274
7/2 ₄	→	11/2	162.2	19.28	283.919
13/2	→	9/2	4.450	0.9131	2.154
(3/2)	→	7/2	277.4	258.8	45.035
17/2	→	15/2	63.88	67.58	587.419
7/2	→	11/2	466.6	453	420.984
15/2 ₂	→	11/2	22.26	25.78	5.874
19/2	→	17/2	54.96	62.47	16.644
19/2	→	15/2	149.7	117.5	27.413
17/2	→	13/2	109.6	115	195.806
21/2	→	17/2	53.18	51.1	489.516
23/2	→	21/2	49.90	47.05	196.785
23/2	→	19/2	113.7	93.73	43.077
27/2	→	23/2	66.13	66.13	186.016

4. Conclusions

All figures show , success in reaching an agreement nearly all energy levels of the isotopes of Titanium, and a proper reproduction of the level arrangement is made . We can evaluate practically any calculations in relation to (F7MBZ & F742) data . Met with some success in replicating the level structure exhibited. Generally speaking , the greatest and most thorough results possess the biggest model space while performing calculations in the infinite sphere . In OXBASH, the model space is described based on the nucleon valence orbits that are now excited together with the outcomes of our calculations are often in agreement with experimental findings

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PLACE OF NOMINATIVE SENTENCES IN A LANGUAGE SYSTEM

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Annotation:

Language illustrates the nation's entire sphere from history to future. Sentence is the main part of a language. The place of nominative sentence is main object of the following article. Furthermore, the article is devoted to define the linguistic essence of nominative sentences in a language system.

Key words and expressions: nominative sentence, language system, ellipsis, one-member sentence.

In world linguistics, there are more than 300 definitions of the linguistic reality called a sentence. Of course, among these, there are nominative sentences as well as simple, compound, complex, subordinate clauses. Unfortunately, sentences distinguished by predicativeness, modality, tone and other features do not have functional, differential signs that are common, universally considered for all full-fledged languages. This is, firstly, a significant problem in syntax, and secondly, a problem related to language structure, that is, sentence construction. Until recently, neither the definition nor the place of nominative clauses in the language system, which includes the set of signs specific to them, has not been resolved.

Taking into account the above circumstances, in this article we will give the definition of nominative sentences and try to determine their place in the language system.

Linguistic literature testifies that nominative sentences have several definitions. These definitions are based on the goals of the researchers. That's probably why there are few that reveal the essence of nominative sentences. Our task, then, seems to be to develop principles of nominative clauses that differ from the definitions given to other clause categories. For this we refer to some of the definitions given so far.

Professor I. Rasulov defines nominative sentences as follows: Nominative sentence is the main type of indefinite sentences divided according to the nature of the main clause. This type of sentences is called the name of an object or event, and this object is expressed by affirming the existence of the event." [1] G'. According to Abdurahmanov, "Sentences indicating the existence of a certain object or events are called nominative sentences" [2]. A group of Russian linguists, thinking about nominative sentences, say that this category of sentences belongs to the group of compound one-syllable sentences formed by the combination of a noun or a quantifier with a noun that confirms the existence of an object or event, can be complicated by the meanings of emotional assessment, command, desire. [3] So, nominative sentences can consist of one word and can be expanded with determiners. For example; University. The golden period of my youth passed here. At first glance, nominative sentences are thought of as sentences consisting only of the possessor without a participle. In fact, if we put these sentences into a paradigm according to tenses, the following view is formed:

1. Wide desert - It was a wide desert.
2. Night - It was night.
3. Spring - Like spring has come.

"Such units equal to the names of events are called nominative sentences," says Sh. Rahmatullaev [4]. The above-mentioned words name the reality almost, none of the grammatical categories that form the clause (sentence) are included in its structure. For

example; Late autumn. It is the season of full harvest. As can be seen from the definitions given above, there is no similarity between Russian and Uzbek linguists in defining the essence of nominative sentences. Therefore, we focus on the sources of Indo-European languages. English grammarians view nominative clauses as a variant of monosyllabic structures. The main or main component of such structures consists of nouns or nouns. (gerund, number, etc.). The function of nominative sentences in the communication process is to realize a dynamic image of the event. A group of sentences expresses the time of the action or event, its place, the conditions of the event, and the participants of the communication process. For example; London. Fog everywhere. Nasty November weather - London, fog everywhere. If we explain the pragmatic features of the meanings of the given examples; these sentences appear as follows both in terms of structure and communication. We bring to mind the capital of Great Britain, the Tower, the bridge, Trafalgar Square, the British Museum, the Houses of Parliament and, of course, the River Thames; Fog in Cabbage - You can't imagine the capital of Great Britain without fog in autumn; Crow tax November air. The weather in the UK will be mostly sunless in late autumn. The

examples given from the English language and their pragmatic explanation indicate that in the development of languages, nominative sentences were also sentences with two or more clauses. Absence of necessary components in nominative sentences can also explain their inclusion in the category of elliptical sentences. In fact, to be an elliptical sentence, the absence of any of the main clauses is taken as a basis. In most cases, nominative sentences must have one of the main clauses. So, what features do nominative sentences differ from elliptical sentences? In our opinion, there is no modality in nominative sentences, even if there is a tone, just as there is no predicativeness, but I.I. According to Meshaninov, predicativeness may be hidden. Nominative clauses are used as noun clauses, nominative clauses, and monosyllabic clauses at all stages of linguistics, including syntax, as evidenced by linguistic literature. Now the term nominative clause has been completely retired by all linguists and researchers.

Cognitive features of nominative sentences are clearly visible. For example, if we take the concept of "love", this word derives from the meanings of words like "who is not affected by the pain of love", loved-unloved or Russian words like "не любимых женщин нет, ест невстреченне".

Some German scholars claim that the function of nominative sentences (function) is to confirm the presence of the possessor in one-syllabic sentences, or to bring the reader to the place where the event or action is taking place. For example; Malay camp. The row of streets crossing another row of streets. Mostly narrow streets. Mostly dirty streets. Mostly dark streets. (P.A). If the structure of sentences is taken seriously, it brings the reader to all the features of the place where the story takes place, including the appearance of the place and the attitude of the character participating in the story to the place. So, if we agree with the opinion of most linguists about nominative sentences, then this category of sentences will be included in one-syllabic structures and will consist only of noun group words. From both semantic and communicative point of view, it is an independent syntactic device that determines the existence, place, and time of an event, event, or a natural phenomenon. As for isolated sentences, they never belong to the group of monosyllabic sentences, because such sentences

rely on the context to perform a certain semantic task, which is why they are called ellipsis sentences. Therefore, nominative sentences are one-syllabic sentences that indicate the existence of an object, event, event at the time of speech (may be outside of the speech function) are called nominative sentences. They can be expressed by one word or by several interconnected words. For example: Subhidam. The sun rose from his bed; Winter. It is the coldest season of the year; Tashkent. It was once a city of bread during the war years. It is now a city of peace. Nominative sentences are present participle sentences. For example; magic tone. Classic songs. Makes hearts flutter.

We will not limit ourselves to this article, which is aimed at highlighting the place of nominative sentences in the language system. Researching the linguopragmatic, linguostylistic and cognitive features of this category of sentences is one of our main goals.

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THE PHENOMENON OF PERIPHRAISIS IN MODERN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

The article is devoted to periphrases, which are one of the interesting and complex phenomena of linguistics. Periphrases belong to the category of tropes - stable combinations of artistic speech, used semantically indivisibly and everywhere. The article discusses the features of the semantics and grammatical design of descriptive phrases - periphrase.

Keywords: linguistics, modern Russian language, periphrase, denotation, expressiveness of the text, fiction, journalism, structural unity, periphrasing.

The functional and communicative aspect of the language and the language of the speaking subjects finds its embodiment in modern linguistics and involves the study of the features of the implementation and functioning of language units of different levels.

A special type of stable combinations (periphrases) has long attracted the attention of language researchers. In modern linguistics, there are several views on this linguistic phenomenon of language. One point of view presupposes a broad understanding of periphrasis, when this term is used for almost any descriptive turn that calls something a second time. Proponents of a narrow approach limit the composition of the periphrases, bringing to the fore any leading distinguishing feature of these turns.

"Periphrastic combinations have been known since biblical times, and their description is already found in the works of ancient theorists of language and style (Aristotle, Quintilian). In antiquity, periphrasis was attributed to figures or tropes, contributed to the creation of the effect of sublimity of speech, and was also used to replace aesthetically unacceptable words and expressions" [4].

According to some researchers, the term periphrase (periphrasis) is borrowed from the French language.

Thus, D. E. Rosenthal and M. A. Telenkova define periphrase as a descriptive turn, namely: "An expression that is a descriptive transfer of the meaning of another expression or word" [7]. A. P. Kvyatkovsky defines periphrase as: "a stylistic device consisting in replacing a word or phrase with a descriptive turn of speech" [3].

The term "periphrase" combines phenomena of different linguistic nature: descriptive characteristics (a cunning beast – a fox), assessments (old age – the evening of life), verbal pairs (to be perplexed – to be perplexed), poetic lines in the volume of a whole sentence ("Sad time! The enchantment of the eyes is about autumn (Pushkin).

The Russian language has enormous possibilities of descriptive transmission of meaning using various lexical and phraseological means. But it would be wrong to consider any turnover with a substitutive function as a periphrase, as well as to narrow the volume of periphrases, guided by only one distinctive feature, and not their totality.

Periphrasis is one of the interesting and complex phenomena of linguistics. It is used in various fields of scientific knowledge, namely: literary studies, logic, stylistics, rhetoric, psycholinguistics, sociolinguistics, etc. All this makes it possible to consider periphrasis not only within the framework of linguistic analysis.

"Periphrases as modeled units, representing in terms of semantics typed expressive modifications of lexical meanings of words, carrying a variety of pragmatic information, constituting a special type of linguistic meaning - periphrastic, and in terms of nomination acting as actual nominative formations, are integrative facts of language and as such should be included in the circle of objects of communicative linguistics" [1].

The peculiarities of the semantics and grammatical design of the descriptive turnover depend primarily on which area of extra-linguistic reality is called a second time: subject, action, feature. That is why periphrases are expressions that describe the object or phenomenon of reality for the second time.

The nature of the descriptive turnover also depends on the purpose for which the turnover is created, and this is largely determined by its belonging to a particular functional style of speech.

The periphrase can have several meanings. They are polysemous if they denote the primary image of phenomena, are connected by generic relations. So, for example, the periphrase "heavenly body" can be used in two meanings: like a star and like the sun.

In other cases, periphrases are considered as homonyms if they denote several primary images. So, the periphrase of the "northern lemon" is called cranberries and kohlrabi, although the first is a berry, and the second is cabbage.

If earlier periphrases were more common in fiction (especially poetry of the XIX century), recently they have been used more often in journalism.

There is still a tendency among linguists to take linguistic material from fiction, so the periphrases of the Russian language, which find their expression in the journalistic style of speech, were not the subject of a special lexicographic description. Therefore, the question of the distinctive features of the periphrasis in the language of newspapers is currently relevant.

Periphrases are secondary nominations. The semantic techniques of secondary nomination of objects and phenomena used in periphrasis are not so diverse. The primary image (denotation) is replaced by a new peripheral one (doctors are people in white coats). In periphrases, two methods of constructing a new image are mainly used: transferring the concept to another sphere metaphor or metonymy (the supporting component of the periphrase is used figuratively: green pharmacy medicinal plants) and expanding the scope of the concept of denotation (the supporting component of the periphrase is used in the direct meaning - this is a generic word in relation to the denotation: white grain - rice).

"The elementary cell of the semantics system is the unity of 3 elements, the so-called "semantic triangle": the external element of a verbal sign (a sequence of sounds or graphic signs) – the signifier is connected, firstly, with the denoted object of reality - the denotation (as well as the referent), secondly, with the reflection of this object in consciousness a person is signified. The signified is the result of social cognition of reality and is usually identical to a concept, sometimes a representation. The triple connection "signifier – denote – signified" constitutes the category of meaning, the basic cell of semantics. Semantic relations consist in the fact that these cells are likened to each other by any of

their three elements - by the signified (synonymy), by the signifier (homonymy), by denotation and referent (periphrase)" [5].

A distinctive feature of the periphrasis is their structural unity - it is mainly the construction of "adjective + noun" (blue planet, green wealth), "noun + noun" (queen of fields, son of Heaven), "numeral + noun" (third hunt). Periphrastic denotations of objects and phenomena of the external world are expressed by nouns, therefore, the supporting component of the periphrasis, which contains the grammatical properties of the descriptive turnover, in the vast majority of cases is a noun.

"Periphrases can be moderated and unmoderated. The structural and semantic models according to which the periphrases are constructed belong to the language system, for example, "city + noun in R. P.": the city of sin (Las Vegas), the city of love (Paris), the city of millionaires (Baden-Baden), the city of metallurgists (Vologda), the city of bridges (St. Petersburg) and others. Speech implementations of peripheral models either remain single neoplasms within the same context, or acquire the properties of reproducibility and stability (are usualized) and enter the corpus of language"[4].

Not every substantive combination is a secondary nomination. It is necessary to take into account the syntactic position. Since the concepts denoted by nouns are mainly paraphrased, to the extent that the periphrases in a sentence usually perform syntactic functions characteristic of a noun, i.e. it is a subject, complement or circumstance. A sign of the stability of these linguistic units is very important for the lexicographic description of periphrases. The occurrence of periphrase is occasional, but its first use is a potential opportunity to acquire stability.

It is quite difficult to fix the moment when the secondary nomination turns from an occasional one into a linguistic unit of periphrasis. Of great importance for the acquisition of stability by the secondary turnover is the character of the trait, which determines the subject correlation of the periphrase with the denotation. For example, if we compare such descriptive phrases as the steel bogatyr - dump truck and the red-haired traveler - cat, then we can notice a different dependence of these secondary nominations on the context. In the first case, the context specifies a feature that can be applied to various denotations in various plots, in the second it deciphers a feature that is relevant only in a specific plot. The reproducibility of periphrasis is due to the relevance of peripheral denotations.

"Consideration of the periphrase as an object of a system description, and not an occasional speech phenomenon, allowed us to discover that in the periphrase there is a communicative actualization of the semantics of the nominate word according to certain semantic and syntactic rules: a) the use of thematic relations between the members of the periphrase, based on the iteration of the seme of the nominate word in the supporting component of the periphrastic combination; b) the use of words of certain selective classes according to the communicative function of each of the components of the periphrastic combination; c) the use of the mechanism of figurative valence, based on the actualization of expressively promising semes of the supporting component of the periphrastic combination, generating the phenomenon of semantic formants in the periphrastic word; d) the use of a "semantic filter" that determines the presence of a direct nominative meaning in one of (or both) members of the combination as a "pledge" of its periphrasticity; e) the use of appositive relations for the paratactic expression of the semantic correlation of the parts of the periphrasis" [1].

Although most of the topics in the newspaper are constant, the specific material in them is often updated. Sometimes denotations are relevant for a short time, but during this period they are actively paraphrased, and then disappear forever from newspaper materials. Some secondary nominations have appeared nowadays and are not frequent, but their denotations may become relevant later, and then these paraphrases have a chance to become reproducible and stable. Paraphrases include both traditional paraphrases that have been used in the press more than once (white gold - cotton), and the most frequent paraphrases that have emerged in the last decade, simultaneously with the realities that they denote (the second literacy is knowledge of the basics of computer science).

«The linguistic and stylistic features of the press are the result of the generality of information of global importance. This is the reason for the convergence of the style of utterance, intensive borrowing of terminology, some stylistic techniques, types of headings, manner of presentation of content»[8].

In the language of the newspaper, mainly paraphrases born within the framework of the journalistic style are used (such paraphrases denote denotations that occur exclusively or predominantly in newspaper materials). However, in newspaper journalism, one can also find paraphrases "borrowed" from the language of fiction [despicable metal is gold, a friend of life is a wife, etc.]. Most literary paraphrases are recorded in explanatory dictionaries of the Russian language. The use of newspaper paraphrases is also not limited to the limits of the journalistic style of speech; paraphrases, frequent in the newspaper, are found both in fiction and in popular science texts, performing there, of course, somewhat different stylistic functions than in the language of the newspaper.

There are also paraphrases of famous people. Russian poet Alexander Pushkin is often called the "Sun of Russian poetry", Georgy Zhukov – "Marshal of Victory", Konstantin Tsiolkovsky – "Father of Russian Cosmonautics", Johann Strauss – "King of Waltz", Margaret Thatcher – "Iron Lady", Louis XIV – "King of the Sun", Elvis Presley – "King of Rock -n-roll."

Arguments against the lexicographic development of paraphrases often boil down to the fact that most of the periphrastic turns can be easily understood from the context and does not need a special dictionary interpretation. However, this "disadvantage" of paraphrases entirely stems from the functional features of the journalistic style - too encrypted paraphrases simply would not take root in a newspaper that should carry information in the most accessible form for the mass reader.

At the same time, although many paraphrases easily correlate with the denotation, the periphrastic image can not always be understood without information about the denotation, which goes beyond ordinary ideas. With regard to the lexicographic description of the periphrasis, the issues of speech culture become particularly relevant due to the well-established attitude to periphrastic turns as costs of the journalistic style of speech, as newspaper cliches that should be avoided. They not only help to avoid repetitions, but also in a compact form express an assessment of an object or phenomenon of reality. In the newspaper language, the new, original is dialectically interconnected with the standard, stereotypical. Every linguistic discovery in the press is inevitably put "on stream" and quickly turns into its opposite - a speech stamp. Therefore, the frequent repetition of once-created images in the newspaper is not a cost, but a pattern of journalistic style. Unfortunately, quite often there is an inappropriate use of paraphrases, when they do not agree with the context, are perceived as linguistic excesses.

Thus, periphrases serve as means of enhancing the expressiveness of the text, in many respects remain traditional phrases that developed in the previous century, but they are influenced by the new time with new realities, the reflection of which we are currently seeing with the birth of new periphrastic units.

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THE FIRST BALL OF NATASHA ROSTOVA

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Annotation

In this article, the author analyzes the image of one of the main characters of the epic novel "War and Peace", considering it in an episode describing Natasha Rostova's first entry into secular society. A comparative analysis of the image of Natasha with her antipode Helen Bezukhova is carried out.

Key words: adjutant manager, ball, adjutant dancer, secular society, first waltz, favorite heroine of the writer

The episode depicting the first ball of Natasha Rostova is one of the main ones in the novel: it is important for revealing the inner world and character of the main character. In this fragment, we are presented with a Petersburg ball from beginning to end, with music, flowers, dances, the sovereign, "ladies in white, blue, pink dresses, with diamonds and pearls on their open hands and necks."

The appearance of the ball itself is all about Peronskaya, with her assessments and remarks, the sovereign, "the queen of St. Petersburg Countess Bezukhova", "the adjutant dancer who started the ball" - everything "mixed into one brilliant procession." But this is not just an ordinary Petersburg ball - this is the first ball of Natasha Rostova, where we meet all the main characters of the novel at once: Natasha, with her sparkling eyes, Prince Andrei and the gloomy, absent-minded Pierre. This event can be called a turning point in Natasha's life. The ball is very important for her future life. She, having visited this ball, parted with her childhood and passes into adulthood. It is this ball that becomes decisive in the relationship between Natasha and Prince Andrei, whose life paths subsequently cross more than once.

Prince Andrei will play an important role in the fate of Natasha. The ball is one of the links in the chain of events that tells about the Rostov family. The picture of the ball is preceded by an episode of the arrival of Boris Drubetskoy - Natasha's first hobby. Tender feelings flare up again between young people, but Natasha no longer perceives Boris as her fiancé. After a conversation with the Countess, Boris stopped visiting the Rostovs.

There is some symbolism in this: Natasha, rejecting Boris, at the same time leaves her childhood in the past. The episode of the ball should be considered as a transitional one. The author in every possible way emphasized Natasha's still childish excited state, more than once using the word "girl" in her description and depicting her with a "grateful childish smile." It was this state that "most of all went to her," and it was precisely this Natasha, "with her surprise, joy and timidity, and even with mistakes in the French language," that Prince Andrei fell in love with.

The author gives us the opportunity to compare the main character "with the Queen of St. Petersburg" - Helen Bezukhova, against whose background Natasha, with her "thin arms and shoulders",

"indefinite breasts", not only does not lose, but also attracts the attention of guests, because in it was something that "did not have a common secular imprint on itself." But we see Natasha as a "girl" not only externally, but also internally: only a child has such strong feelings, emotions and excitement, a strong, boundless feeling of love that a person experiences "at that highest level of happiness, when he becomes completely kind and good and does not believe in the possibility of misfortune, evil and grief." "The expression on Natasha's face, ready for despair and delight, was a mirror image of her feelings" and helped the reader to penetrate the inner world of the main character.

The author masterfully portrayed Natasha's experiences. The following key scenes can be distinguished here. The picture of the ball begins with a description of Natasha's feelings in the carriage, when the Rostov family is going to the ball and Natasha for the first time imagines what she will see and experience. "What awaited her was so wonderful that she did not even believe that it would be: it was so inconsistent with the impression of cold, tightness and darkness of the carriage," the author's psychological comment is very expressive here. And the ball really ends with a feeling of immense happiness that overwhelms Natasha.

When the Rostovs arrived at the ball, "the host and hostess, who had been standing at the front door for half an hour and saying the same thing, also met the Rostovs in the same way. And two girls in white dresses, with the same roses in their black hair, sat down in the same way. But involuntarily the hostess fixed her gaze on thin Natasha and remembered, perhaps, all her golden, irrevocable girlish time and her first ball.

When they danced Polish and Natasha was not invited, it turned out that each of the men who would play an important role in Natasha's life in the future did not notice her: "Prince Andrei walked past them with some lady, obviously not recognizing them, the handsome Anatole looked at Natasha's face with the same look that one looks at the wall, Boris walked past twice and each time turned away. And when the "adjutant-manager" and the beautiful Helen danced the first round of the waltz, Natasha and I involuntarily worried that it was not she who was now dancing. Thanks to the skill of Tolstoy the writer, we see the falsity of secular society during the ball.

So, all three main characters of the novel are present at the ball: Andrei Bolkonsky, Pierre Bezukhov, Natasha Rostova. Bolkonsky and Bezukhov are characterized by Peronskaya, who reflects the views of secular society, and Natasha, through whom, in this case, Tolstoy expressed his attitude towards these characters. For high society, Pierre is a "pea jester", and Prince Andrei is a rude man who "does not know how to deal with ladies." At the same time, Natasha happily looks at the familiar face of Pierre and speaks of him as "very good." And in Prince Andrei, we see not only a reformer who "writes some projects with Speransky", but also a person with a big soul who managed to discern in the "trembling" Natasha a huge inner world, sharpness of feelings, inner strength. When Prince Andrei danced with Natasha "one of the merry cotillions before dinner," he reminded her of their meeting in Otradnoe. There is some symbolism in this. In Otradnoye, the first meeting between Prince Andrei and Natasha took place, a formal acquaintance, and at the ball - their inner rapprochement.

"I would be glad to rest and sit with you, I'm tired; but you see how they choose me, and I'm glad about it, and I'm happy, and I love everyone, and we understand all this," - and said a lot more Natasha's smile to Prince Andrei. It was after the first dance that Natasha was noticed, appreciated, and she was a success with men.

Throughout the novel, we meet Natasha in almost all life situations. Tolstoy gives us the opportunity to fully know the character of the main character. The episode of the first ball of Natasha Rostova is notable for the fact that we see the soul of the heroine in motion: from a moment of despair to the pinnacle of the highest happiness. In desperation, she closes herself and asks questions only to herself: "Is it really that no one will come up to me, really, I won't dance between the first ones, really all these men won't notice me?" In moments of the highest happiness, her soul is open to everyone: she is ready to give her love to Prince Andrei, she wants to help Pierre with all her heart, "to give him the surplus of her happiness", gives happy smiles to her father. Perhaps it is precisely for this boundless spiritual warmth that Tolstoy loves his heroine.

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METHODOLOGY FOR THE FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN THE LESSONS OF RUSSIAN LITERATURE IN SCHOOLS WITH A NON-RUSSIAN LANGUAGE OF INSTRUCTION

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Annotation

This article discusses the methodology of questions for the formation of communicative competence in the lessons of Russian literature in schools with a non-Russian language of instruction. The methods are based on the quality of conversation, class hour, communication games, extra-curricular activities. Methods are applied after lessons in non-Russian language schools. The purpose of the article is to highlight the problems of the methodology for the formation of communication among stakeholders and school students. After the lesson material, students need to master additional material to get acquainted with literary characters from the field of Russian literature, which is important for understanding problems and tasks when teaching Russian speech skills in schools with non-Russian language of instruction.

Keywords: Pedagogy, russian speech, spelling rules, extra-curricular activities, literary characters, russian literature, the problem of perception.

In the course of the educational process in schools with a non-Russian language of instruction, in the lessons of Russian literature, we conducted conversations with school students, class hours, communication games, and extracurricular activities. We discussed the issue of friendship with the hero of a literary work or film.

1. Who did you want to be friends with?

2. Why? What qualities attract in a hero?

(Students of schools with a non-Russian language of instruction want to be friends with strong personalities, preferably from Russian classics - PavkaKorchagin and EvgenyOnegin. They believe that this can be learned, that these heroes, being friends, can come to the rescue in difficult times. Children can watch who can give them this help from their friends).[1. p. 125]

3. And who helps you in life in difficult times?

4. How can television and literary heroes help?

(It is concluded that close people help in difficult times - mom, dad, friends, relatives. Fictional characters can help only by showing an example of strength or resourcefulness in getting out of a critical situation).

Depending on the goals set before the lesson, it was possible to create a friendly atmosphere in the class, the guys worked in a team, actively participated in competitions in pairs. Even those guys who do not show themselves in ordinary lessons, are silent, are not interested in anything, were active and did not refuse to participate in discussions. Students were able to collectively, solve the tasks. During the lesson, they developed thinking, attention, emotions, memory and speech, developed cognitive abilities. The students also learned a lot.[2. p. 228]

We experimenters also spent a class hour on the topic "The World of Human Relations". She took over the form of its holding from the television club of experts "What? Where? When?". Our class hour was held in the form of a quiz and was called "Can - can't?".

On the blackboard there is a drawing with the image of an owl - a symbol of wisdom. Multi-colored pieces of paper are attached to it, on the back of which the correct answers to the questions are written, and the questions themselves are attached around the owl in envelopes of the same colors. The questions are given in the form of a situation, which the guys, after thinking, should collectively answer. There are seven envelopes, they are arranged in the order of the rainbow color - a symbol of children's joy, happiness.[3. p. 25]

Students sit at tables in small groups, agree on who will be the team captain. In turn, the captains go to the board, take one of the envelopes and read the question-situation to the whole class. The guys collectively find the answer. The captains are the first to express their point of view, and then the rest of the guys add or correct. Envelopes contain tasks of this type:

1. Leaning on a stick, an old man walks. He stops to rest. And wanders again. The boys who watched him began to imitate his gait, hunched over, barely moving their legs - the guys laugh merrily.

What can you say about these boys?

2. The bus is crowded, everyone is coming home from work. Olya takes the vacant seat with a smile and looks at those who are standing.

How should Olya have acted?

3. One girl complained indignantly to her mother: "In the yard, the boy is so impolite - he calls me Tanya." "And what do you call him?" Mom asked. "I don't call him at all. I just shout to him: "Hey, you!" Tanya answered.[3. p. 29]

Do you think Tanya is right?

4. Two boys collided at the entrance door and could not disperse in any way. Which of them should give way if the boys are 8 and 11 years old. (Usually the one who is more polite is the first to give way.)

5. You knocked on the door. They opened it for you and you saw that you had the wrong address. How do you proceed?

After the guys express their opinion, conduct their examples, take a piece of paper with the answer, which is attached to the owl, and read the "opinion" of the Owl.

In one of the envelopes there were three questions at once - this meant a blitz tournament.

This form of holding diversified the traditional class hours and caused activity even among passive children. What we wanted to achieve.

We also held two educational activities in the class. Theme of the extracurricular activity: "Extracurricular activity on the topic: "Friendship is the main miracle."

Purpose of the Event:

- to form good relationships between children in the classroom,
- to develop aspirations to be tolerant in a society of people,
- to cultivate respect for classmates.

Equipment for the Event:

Proverbs on the board:

To have a friend - do not feel sorry for yourself;

Look for a friend, and if you find - take care;

Hold on to each other - do not be afraid of anything

Friend is known in trouble.

Whoever leaves a friend in trouble, he himself gets into trouble.

Album sheets and paints

At the beginning of the event, the song "Blue Carriage" was played. Then the children thought about what friendship is, how they imagine it, what definition they can give to the word "friendship". The children were given verses in advance, which they had to learn and recite at the event. All children are very well prepared. The children worked in pairs. They expressed to their neighbor about his successes and failures. Each student analyzed everything that his neighbor said.[4. p. 175]

Performing the following task, it was necessary to analyze the situation. And in the end, the children conclude that you need to be friends not so that he (friend) does something good for you, not because that it is profitable, but because this person is close to you, his interests, views, inner world are close. The children played the game "Magic Chair". Purpose: to develop interest in a person, to form positive personality traits; learn to see the good in people. One of the participants in the game is invited to the "magic chair": as soon as he sits down, "highlighted" and only all his virtues become apparent; those present talk about what their eyes see; name qualities (smart, kind, attentive); give behavioral characteristics (he always helps, you can turn to him with a request ...); talk about external virtues (beautiful hair). The children liked this game very much. They perked up and did not even take offense at the statements of the children.[5. p. 152]

We think that, depending on the goals set before the event, it was possible to show the value and necessity of friendship and clarify the children's ideas about what friendship is and what a true friend should be. The event contributed to the formation of a friendly class team. We managed to create a friendly atmosphere in the class.

And one more event that we held was an extra-curricular event "Clever and Clever".

Objectives: To learn to determine the lexical meaning of a word, depending on the context; correct lexical inaccuracies in statements of various types. To teach the correct grammatical design of sentences; Enrich and activate the vocabulary of students; Develop intonation expressiveness of speech, learn to distinguish between stylistic shades of words; Develop communication skills and the ability to formulate your thoughts; Cultivate an interest in reading and a love of books.

Equipment: recording, illustrations of characters from fairy tales, costumes, "fairy tale" objects (pea, walnut shell, blue balloon, shoe), cut phrases of A.S. Pushkin "The fairy tale is a lie, but there is a hint in it - a lesson for good fellows!"; poster with words; incentive medals "To the best storyteller", cap "Chief storyteller"

In general, I liked the work with the students, they willingly made contact, entered into discussions, and drew their own conclusions. In addition, the guys turned out to be creative personalities. In our opinion, it is necessary to carry out further work in the classroom in this direction (the formation of communication), this will help unite the class, develop a culture of communication and behavior among them. In general, the class is creative, so further work can be directed to the development of

creative potential in children. If in the future such work with children is carried out in the class, then the children will grow up cultured and will be able to communicate with both peers and adults.[6. p. 58]

To compare the formation of communicative competence in younger students, a repeated test was performed. The children were offered to re-diagnose the level of communication of children. The level of communication skills of children was determined using the test "Assessment of the level of sociability" by V.F. Ryakhovsky. Analysis of the diagnostic results showed that there were 3 more people with a high level of communication skills. A student whose level was below the average showed an average level. Such results allow us to draw a conclusion about the effectiveness of the developed activities for the formation of communicative competence. According to the results of repeated diagnostics, it can be assumed that the formation of communicative competence has grown [7. p. 51]

It is noticeable that the extracurricular activities carried out benefited the children. We believe that students in school need to prepare together more often and participate in extracurricular activities to improve their communication skills. Work should be carried out with younger students purposefully, giving them the opportunity to form a friendly and cohesive team.

This project led to the following conclusions:

1. A person improves his speech all his life, masters the riches of the language. Each age stage brings something new to his speech development. The most important steps in mastering speech fall on primary school age. Human speech is a kind of mirror of culture and education. For a younger student, competent speech is the key to successful learning and development. Fluency in speech contributes to full communication, the creation of a person's communicative comfort in society.
2. Analyzing the literature, I saw many points of view on the definition of the concept of "communicative competence", which have become more or less stable and generally recognized. Most authors note that communicative competence is not only the ability to understand others and generate one's own statements, speech behavior that is adequate to the goals, areas, situations of communication, it includes knowledge of basic speech concepts: styles, types of speech, structure of description, narrative, reasoning, ways of connecting sentences in the text, the ability to analyze the text.
3. A modern school should prepare a thinking and feeling person, who not only has knowledge, but also knows how to use this knowledge in life, who knows how to communicate and has an internal culture. The goal is for the student to be able to act and solve problems in all situations. Mastering communicative competence is a necessary condition for the formation of a socially active personality. Everyone needs to learn to speak clearly and grammatically correctly, to have a well-trained voice, to express their own thoughts in a free interpretation, to be able to express their emotions by various intonational means, to observe speech culture and develop the ability to communicate - everyone needs. Therefore, one of the most important tasks at the present stage of teaching students is the development of communication skills.
4. The use of various methods and techniques for the development of connected speech is an effective means of developing communication skills.

If the teacher carries out systematic work on the formation of communicative competencies in younger students, then the results of the development of coherent speech will increase [8. p. 71]

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THE PRINCIPLE OF VISIBILITY IN A MODERN SCHOOL

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Annatation

The article discusses the issues of improving the quality of education through the use of modern computer technologies. The use of computer programs provides a differentiated and individual approach to learning, since they provide for the possibility of providing training work of varying duration, depending on the assimilation of the method of action by specific students.

Keywords: individual approach, information, education, visual aids, skills formation.

The globalization of modern society requires highly qualified workers who quickly adapt to the flow of information. In his message to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev proposed to proclaim 2023 the Year of Human Care and Quality Education. The President stressed that it is necessary to continue reforms in the field of education.

This, in turn, poses serious challenges to the secondary school: improving the quality of education and upbringing of students, increasing the scientific and theoretical level of teaching, improving teaching methods and techniques, strengthening the material and technical base of schools, equipping the educational process with interactive learning tools [1].

More recently, the wordsmith had several tables, flashcards, filmstrips, educational recordings, etc. at his disposal. Today, the arsenal of visual aids has expanded significantly. Modern technologies came to the teacher's aid: projectors, interactive whiteboards, computers. The presence of a large fund of the above-mentioned training tools, which continue to grow rapidly today, raises the question of how to use these funds. What are the possibilities of visual aids for improving the educational process, how to organize a lesson using them, what are the effective methods of working with modern technologies?

The direct acquaintance of students with objects in nature or images of these objects was put forward by the outstanding teacher Jan Amos Komensky in the famous "golden rule" [2].

Visibility as one of the most important didactic principles is developed and implemented in the theory and practice of teaching the Russian language at all stages of the development of school education. The main way of its implementation is the use of visual aids in the educational process. Visual materials can be useful only if they are organically linked to the content of the lesson as a whole, with all its components and tasks. When starting to use visual aids, the teacher must realize for what purpose he is doing this, determine at what stage of the lesson to work with them, how to link this stage with other parts of the lesson. Visual aids help to solve such tasks as mobilizing students' mental activity; introducing novelty into the learning process; increasing interest in the lesson; increasing the possibility of involuntary memorization of material; expanding the volume of assimilated material; highlighting the main thing in the material and its systematization. Thus, visual aids are used at almost all stages of learning: at the stage of explaining new material (presenting information), at the stage of consolidating and forming skills (teaching students certain actions), at the stage of monitoring the assimilation of knowledge and the formation of skills (evaluating the results of students' work), at the

stage of systematization, repetition, generalization material (highlighting the main, most important in the studied material) [3].

Visual aids are divided into visual, sound, visual-auditory. Consider the means of visual visualization. Visual visual aids include so-called printed media (tables, demonstration cards, reproductions of paintings, handouts) and screen media (filmstrips, slides and slides, banners, presentations, videos).

Currently, the arsenal of visual aids is expanding and replenishing. So, computer technologies are used in Russian language lessons for educational purposes. Computer technology can be used at any stage of the lesson: when studying and summarizing the material. If we take spelling as an example, then working on a rule (or a block of rules) at the first stage involves studying or repeating the relevant material of a school textbook. After that, students with the help of a series of computer programs once again study the spelling rules, then train in the choice of spelling based on the algorithm embedded in the program, controlling their actions at all stages of applying the rule, including the last, final stage at which the choice of spelling is made. With the help of a computer, schoolchildren master spelling analysis, the scheme of which is presented by a computer, which allows us to judge the level of mastery of spelling theory by students, as well as the ability to apply this theory in practice.

Using a computer in Russian language lessons is not an end in itself. Its use makes it possible to effectively solve a number of didactic tasks: to intensify the educational process, optimize it, activate the cognitive activity of schoolchildren, arouse interest in academic work, increase their knowledge, achieve tangible results in improving skills and abilities.

Movies are also used to teach storytelling. With the help of a movie, you can clearly show students the compositional features of the narrative genre. For this purpose, such specific techniques are used as showing a series of main episodes of the filmed story at the end of the film (they are restored using a freeze frame); analysis of episodes related to the development of the action of the story; development of the plot at the beginning or ending of the story; analysis of the speaker's text, its addition and transformation; film music analysis, etc. Some films help prepare students for speaking. At the heart of such films is a sample of oral storytelling. At the heart of such films is a sample of oral storytelling. Work on the film will require students to perform a number of special tasks: follow the tone of the narrator's speech; determine how he conveys his feelings and his mood, how he carries himself; think about it why the story turned out to be interesting, why it is easy to listen to.

In order to solve all the problems due to the nature of educational films, it is necessary to follow the following methodological recommendations.

Thinking over the goals and objectives of using an educational film (or film fragment) in the lesson, the teacher must determine the stage at which the film will be shown, methods for correlating the work on the film with the content of the entire lesson. Particular attention should be paid to preparing students for the perception of the film: formulate the tasks of the work, orient the students to fix certain details when watching the film, talk about the creators, characters and actors (if any), etc. In other words, the preparatory work should help to ensure that from the very first minutes of watching the film, students are not distracted from solving the main task of this stage of the lesson. After watching a movie, it is useful to find out the general impression that it made on them: what they remember, what they liked, etc. This will allow you to determine which of the students was attentive when watching the film, which of them more fully realized its content. Consequently, further conversation with students will be more fruitful. In the course of performing special tasks aimed at

the knowledge of linguistic phenomena or the development of speech, the teacher leads students to the necessary conclusions. During a conversation with schoolchildren, it is useful to teach them to take notes that will later facilitate the completion of tasks related to watching a film: outlines of a plan or compositional scheme for a future statement, vocabulary that is new for students and necessary for future work, drafted fragments of text, etc.

Work on a film ends, as a rule, with the performance of independent tasks (at home or in class), determined by the content of the film and its purpose: the preparation of oral and written statements of various genres.

The use of computer programs provides a differentiated and individual approach to learning, since they provide for the possibility of providing training work of varying duration, depending on the assimilation of the method of action by specific students. The program provides for the use in the process of training work of different degrees of difficulty options that can be offered to students taking into account their capabilities.

Turning to cinema art in Russian language and literature lessons is a well-known type of work. But in the modern lesson, the use of video materials is finding more and more use. These are educational films, film adaptations of works of art, excerpts from animated films, video materials created by students themselves, excerpts from TV shows, etc.

Video materials can be used at various stages of the lesson and even at recess. Before the lesson, when students have already entered the classroom, videos help to arouse the interest of children, immerse them in the atmosphere of the future lesson. Creating such a film can be a preliminary task for students. The guys can edit a film based on a demonstration of paintings by famous artists accompanied by music corresponding to the era being studied.

At the initial stage of the lesson, video clips can be used to create a problem situation or predict a topic even in Russian lessons. For example, the study of new material on the spelling of the suffixes EC, IC can begin with a demonstration of an excerpt from the cartoon "In the land of unlearned lessons". The video clip makes the lesson vivid, memorable, activates the cognitive activity of students, teaches them to work with different sources of information. The use of film materials in literature lessons is especially relevant. It can be either an educational video or a film adaptation of a work of art. Educational videos allow us to reduce the time to get acquainted with the biography of the writer, to make this stage of the lesson, which is not always interesting to students, more visual.

In the XX century, many methodists argued that it was possible to turn to cinema and theatrical art only after studying a literary work, because otherwise the visual images created by actors and the director would suppress the activity of the reader's imagination. The traditional path for the methodology — from a verbal work to its cinema or theatrical interpretation - does not give the desired result today, since the main, first link falls out of the chain — reading. But it often happens among modern schoolchildren that interest in literature increases, and literary development proceeds more intensively with a specially organized interaction of reading and spectator activity.

There are certain methodological recommendations for the use of film adaptations of works of fiction in literature lessons. But it is always necessary to familiarize students with the means of cinematic expressiveness in advance. Any discussion of a movie should end with the creation of a problematic situation that motivates schoolchildren to turn to a literary source, therefore, reading activity should ultimately prevail.

Often the teacher has to make a choice: is it worth using video clips in the classroom at all, or is it better to ask students to watch the film in full beforehand, without violating the logic of the script. If, after all, the comparison of the film adaptation and the work in the lesson is appropriate, then how is it better to do it?

There are not so many techniques for submitting a film adaptation in the lesson, and each of them has its own methodological task.

You can also use other methods of working with the video sequence, for example: direct comparison of the video fragment and the text indicating the differences, possible reasons for the differences; search for answers to the questions raised in the fragment; discussion of the reasons for using certain cinematic techniques to reveal literary images (close-up, details, musical arrangement, etc.); location of video fragments in the logical order corresponding to the text, search for the missing fragment in the text; "voicing" of the scene (search for the corresponding video sequence of the monologue, dialogue).

In project and extracurricular activities, you can also turn to cinematography. The guys are happy to take part in the creation of booktrailers, promotional videos for the film adaptation, posters. Of particular interest is the implementation of small projects for lessons, for example, combining several fragments processed in the corresponding program to illustrate the compositional elements of the work, characterization of images, immersion in the era, etc. One way or another, the result of such work will be a return to the text and careful work with it. In addition to the problem of familiarization with reading, the use of film in literature lessons solves a whole range of other tasks: the formation of the media culture of students, fluency in computer technology, contributing to the successful socialization of personality in modern society; the development of logical thinking, imagination (the creative potential of children can be revealed here as much as possible); the development of oral and written speech. The educational impact is also great - the formation of spiritual immunity against the negative phenomena of society through the study of works of various types of art.

Computer support is possible when studying various topics of the school curriculum, primarily when studying punctuation.

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INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO THEORETICAL TRAINING AT THE LESSON OF PHYSICAL CULTURE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Annotation

In this article, to determine the level of theoretical training, a specially developed assessment questionnaire on the basics of the theory of physical education of high school students was used, in which a variety of answers to the questions posed is expressed.

Keywords: theories of physical culture, pedagogical experiment, homework, school age, exercise

The content of the theoretical part of physical culture classes is presented in sufficient detail in school curricula and methodological manuals. Over the past decade, there is clearly a lack of sound recommendations in the methodological literature on the most effective provision of information on the theory of physical culture to students. There is no sufficiently complete study of the issue of monitoring the level of theoretical preparedness of schoolchildren.

A modern school teacher of physical culture should be responsible for what information and ideas students will receive. Despite the progressive shifts that have recently taken place in physical education, teaching the basics of the theory of physical culture in a school educational institution remains one of the weak links in the school education system.

In order to identify the problem under study, a pedagogical experiment was conducted, in which the following methods were used: analysis and generalization of literary sources, documentary materials, survey method, pedagogical experiment, control tests, methods of mathematical statistics. (1)

The pedagogical experiment was carried out in secondary school No. 6 in Fergana. The experiment involved 60 schoolgirls of the middle age group, who were divided into one control and two experimental groups. Each group included 20 students of the 8th grade of a comprehensive school. Our choice of this age group is due to the fact that it is at this age that there is a special need to master the theoretical foundations of physical education.

The control and 1 experimental groups were engaged in the program of physical culture of the secondary school. The content of the classes included topics from the sections included in the educational minimum in the subject "Physical culture", the Sample program for this discipline at school and reflected in the textbook "Fundamentals of the theory of physical culture":

- psychological and pedagogical foundations of physical culture;
- socio-cultural foundations of physical culture;
- medical and biological foundations of physical culture;
- basic types of physical culture and sports activities.

Experimental work was carried out according to the program developed at the Department of Theory and Methods of Physical Culture in accordance with the content of the general school plan for physical culture.

Students in the control group received theoretical knowledge in the traditional way, i.e. during the lessons.

In the first experimental group, one physical education lesson was devoted to the basics of theory. The adoption of this decision to conduct theoretical classes in this way is due to our assumption that the information received during the whole lesson is absorbed faster and more firmly than when it is received by topic at the beginning of each physical education lesson immediately before practical classes. In the latter case, in our opinion, the integrity of the perception system is violated.

In the second main experimental group, the theory of physical culture was given to students as homework. We considered it expedient to experimentally test the hypothesis that the material is better absorbed during independent study, since students have more opportunities for its creative comprehension.

Testing was carried out in two stages: Initial - in mid-September; final - in mid-February 2020. The evaluation of the results was carried out according to the standards to determine the level of knowledge of the basics of the theory of physical culture of students - girls of the VIII grade, carried out by the methodological commission, which included leading specialists of the school education system.

For a more reliable analysis of the applied methodology, in order to study the influence of theoretical knowledge on the development of physical qualities, control tests were carried out to determine the level of development of motor abilities. For this purpose, the following exercises were used:

- 30 m run;
- shuttle run 3x10;
- 6-minute run;
- pull-ups on the low bar from hanging lying down

The results obtained during the pedagogical testing were processed according to the Student's t-test for parametric data and are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Groep	Wrong answers for tasks and sections				Sum points $\bar{x} \pm \sigma$	P
	Sociocultural foundations of FC	Psychological pedagogical FC basics	Medical biological FC basics	Basic Views physical education sports activities		
Control (n=20)	2,2	2,65	2,55	2,5	10,1±0,35	>0,01
	1,8	1,7	2,15	2,25	12,1±0,42	
Expert 1 (n=20)	2,2	2,3	2,6	2,4	10,5±0,43	<0,01
	0,45	1,0	0,95	0,85	16,7±0,56	
Expert 2 (n=20)	2,4	2,4	2,5	2,15	10,2±0,49	<0,01
	1,05	1,4	1,4	1,2	14,9±0,37	

The analysis of the obtained results shows that the average score in the initial testing in all three groups is approximately the same, while in the final testing in the 1 experimental group an unreliable increase in the result was revealed - 5.7%.

Thus, it is obvious that teaching students the basics of theory once in one lesson is more effective. At the same time, the development of the theoretical foundations of physical culture in the process of

homework has a better effect on increasing the theoretical level in comparison with students in the control group who study in the traditional way.

It became expedient to determine the negative impact on the development of physical qualities by the fact that one lesson per week was reserved for theoretical classes, reducing the time for physical training. The results of testing for the development of physical qualities showed that theoretical classes did not have a significant impact on the development of physical abilities. Summarized data of the initial and final testing separately for the two experimental and control groups are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Groep		Control tests											
		Run 30 m			shuttle run 3x10 m			6 minute run, p.			Pull-ups from hanging lying, times		
		x	σ	%	x	σ	%	x	σ	%	x	σ	%
Control (n=20)	До	5,48	0,27	8,5	9,4	0,19	8,15	1039,4	98,9	11,8	3,5	1,5	88,5
	После	4,9	0,19		8,8	0,2		1167,0	108,2		7,7	1,8	
Exp.1 (n=20)	До	5,4	0,29	4,0	9,38	0,21	8,12	1070,9	103,2	12,24	3,9	1,7	86,4
	После	5,18	0,34		8,5	0,34		1193,1	82,3		7,3	1,7	
Exp.2 (n=20)	До	5,43	0,24	8,7	9,35	0,17	8,17	1098,2	94,6	12,31	3,8	1,4	87,7
	После	4,96	0,3		8,7	0,2		1194,1	91,01		7,1	4,5	

A comparative analysis of the control results shows that in the initial testing, the data in different groups, in all types of tested exercises, are approximately the same.

Thus, it was found that in all three experimental groups, female students, using various forms of teaching the theory of physical culture, did not adversely affect the development of their level of physical fitness. At the same time, during the period of the pedagogical experiment in the 2nd experimental group, there were significant changes in the level of physical fitness, and the increase in the effectiveness of physical qualities was more than 14%.

Summing up the pedagogical research, it was found that:

1. In the practice of physical culture lessons in a general education school, insufficient attention is paid to teaching the basics of the theory of physical culture.
2. A comparative analysis of the results showed that the presentation of information on the theory of physical education during a separate lesson helps to increase the level of theoretical preparedness of schoolchildren.
3. Independent study by students of the theoretical foundations of physical culture is quite radically reflected in the level of theoretical training.
4. The process of teaching the basics of the theory of physical culture during one lesson does not affect the development of the physical abilities of girls studying in the 8th grade of the school education system.

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CLINICAL AND LABORATORY FEATURES OF NEPHROPATHY IN CHILDREN WITH DIABETES MELLITUS

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Annotation

Diabetes currently occupies a leading position in pediatric endocrinology with diseases, disorders and complications that can lead to a decrease in life expectancy. According to the World Health Organization, the incidence of diabetes in the world doubles every 10-15 years, and the life expectancy of patients is lower than among the general population. As a result of type 1 diabetes, the patient's ability to work and their life are impaired, which indicates that the disease is an important medical, social and economic problem in modern society. Materials and research methods. 50 patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus aged 6 to 16 years, 28 boys and 22 girls. The control group consisted of 20 patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus who did not have hyperuricemia, hyperuricosis, proteinuria, that is, normal urinalysis. ... Research results. The data obtained confirm that hyperuricemia, hyperuricosuria and urate nephropathy are common in children with diabetes. The onset of the disease is less pronounced, the course is relatively positive. However, if the diagnosis is not made at an early stage, that is, without dietary correction of purine metabolism, the process can become chronic (interstitial nephritis, DN, microbial inflammatory process of the kidneys, chronic renal failure can be observed). Conclusion: Given the type of disease, dysmetabolic changes are difficult to reverse, but we can conclude that dietary medico-time adjustments can be avoided in a timely manner.

Keywords: diabetes mellitus, nephropathy, children.

Relevance of the Topic

Diabetic nephropathy, one of the dreaded complications of type 1 diabetes, is now one of the main causes of death in children [4, 7]. DN mainly develops within 5-10 years after the onset of the disease, leading to a significant deterioration of the patient's quality of life, disability and, quite quickly, chronic renal failure (SBE). Every fourth to fifth of patients with type 1 QD die from SBE [4, 10]. Treatment of end-stage renal failure by extracorporeal methods (dialysis, kidney transplantation) requires a huge amount of money, amounting to several billion dollars every year, which raises kidney pathology in diabetes to the level of an important socio-economic problem [3, 5].

If children with diabetes develop symptoms of kidney disease, the first thing to consider is the possibility of developing diabetic nephropathy. In addition, such patients are not protected from dysmetabolic nephropathy with other genesis. According to observations, diabetic nephropathy can develop in children diagnosed with diabetes within 5 years (E. V. Melekhin, 2003). It is known that proteinuria observed in diabetes is not related to diabetic nephropathy in 10-30% of cases [4]. Metabolic nephropathy takes the main place among the non-infectious risk factors for kidney damage:

urate, oxalate, etc. [12]. According to scientists, urate nephropathy is a common option among dysmetabolic nephropathies, because carbohydrates with diabetic characteristics (obesity, MS, gout, atherosclerosis, arterial hypertension, insulin sensitivity) make up the whole range of pathological conditions associated with hyperuricemia (GU). There is a parallel between carbohydrate disorders and the level of manifestation of GU [11, 14, 1]. It was found that uric acid is structurally related to alloxan, a diabetogenic substance [19]. The etiological role of uric acid in the development of QD has been proven on the basis of experimental investigations: a single administration of SC to rats led to the development of uric acid diabetes. In this regard, timely initiation of treatment measures for dysmetabolism combined with urate dysmetabolism is of great medical, economic and social importance [6, 19].

The Purpose of the Work:

To study the clinical and laboratory characteristics of uricosuric nephropathy in patients with diabetes.

Case Study and Examination Materials:

50 patients with type 1 QD, 28 boys, 22 girls aged 6 to 16 years were taken. As a control group, 20 patients with type 1 QD and no hyperuricemia, hyperuricosuria, proteinuria, i.e., normal urinalysis, were taken. As a norm, 10 healthy children of the same age without aggravated family anamnesis (QD, metabolic syndrome) were taken.

The average duration of the disease is 3.24 ± 0.8 years, that is, the duration of the disease is definitely not enough for the development of diabetic nephropathy. The disease was variable in 6 children, with decompensation 2 times a year, and in the rest 1-2 times a year, with relatively stable decompensation. When arriving at the hospital, all patients were in the stage of decompensation of carbohydrate metabolism, the amount of glycosylated hemoglobin (Nb A 1s) was determined in 12 patients (24%), from 3.8 to 14.4%, the average was $8.0 \pm 3.57\%$. No ketosis was observed during special examination. According to the daily data of the glycemic profile, the average daily level of glycemia was from 3.2 to 14.1 mmol/l, the average value was 8.4 ± 2.4 mmol/l. According to the daily data of the glycemic profile, the average daily level of glycemia ranged from 2.5 to 28.1 mmol/l, with an average of 13.29 ± 4.8 mmol/l.

Examination Methods:

Clinical and laboratory characteristics of the examined patients are presented in Table 1. As can be seen in this table, there is no difference in age among the examined patients ($r > 0.05$). Clinical examination methods include: general examination of patients, objective examination of organs and systems by palpation, percussion (comparative, topographical), auscultation and measurement of arterial blood pressure by the Korotkov method.

Table 1. Clinical and laboratory characteristics of patients

Indicators	Duration of illness	
	up to 2 years	2-4 years
Age, year	11,9±2,1	12,1±2,2
TMI, kg/m ²	18,8±2,3	19,1±1,6
Glycemia, mmol/l	12,6±3,4	13,5±4,1
NvA 1s	9,8±2,5	11,8±3,7
Total cholesterol, mmol/l	4,7±1,1	4,49±0,9
Blood creatinine mmol/l	0,086±0,07	0,091±0,04
Average AQB mm.sm.us.	110,0±6,8	114,6±7,4
Diastolic AQB mm.sm.us.	62,2±6,8	68,4±8,4
Uric acid mmol/l	0,310±0,05	0,360±0,06
Insulin daily dose ED/milk	30,2 ±10,1	36,3±12,6
Urea mmol/l	5,7±4,1	36,3±12,6

Quantitative examination of proteinuria: application of Beuringer-Ingel Austrian company Nephur-type test strips. With the help of strip tests, in addition to determining the amount of proteins in urine, the following indicators were studied: reaction, specific gravity, leukocytes, bacteria, erythrocytes, glucose. Sulfosalicylic acid was used for qualitative and quantitative evaluation of proteinuria.

Partial kidney function in children with uricosuric nephropathy on the background of type 1 diabetes. According to the task, the patients were divided into 2 groups: 1 group (control) included patients with hyperuricemia, without hyperuricosuria, without pathological changes in urine, with 20 QD with a negative microalbuminuria test; Group II included 30 patients with hyperuricemia, hyperuricosuria and uricosuric nephropathy. The analysis of the functional state of the kidneys was carried out using the Roberg-Tareev test, the test of the functional reserve of the kidneys and the concentration function of the kidneys were carried out using the Zimnitsky test. Also, calciuria, tubular reabsorption indicators of phosphorus were used to evaluate the function of kidney tubules. (table 2). According to Table 2, glomerular filtration rate (FFT) in both groups is significantly increased ($r < 0.001$) and refers to glomeruli in a state of hyperfiltration ($FFT > 140 \text{ ml/min/1.73m}^2$). Water reabsorption tended to decrease, but was not statically reliable ($r < 0.005$), TRP was reliably decreased in both groups. Uric acid was $8.4 \pm 0.08 \text{ ml/min/1.73m}^2$ in patients of group I, 6.6% in group I, 10.3% in group II. Accordingly, the fractional clearance of uric acid in group I was $14.6 \pm 1.2 \text{ ml/min/ha}$ (normally $8.4\% \pm 0.4$, $r > 0.05$) and in group II up to $16.2 \pm 1.2\%$ ($r < 0.001$) increase was observed. These data indicate a better functional capacity of the kidneys in the excretion of uric acid from the body in the observed patients, which explains the almost 2-fold increase in the daily secretion of uric acid in uricosuric nephropathy ($r < 0.001$).

Table 2 Clearance and reabsorption of certain substances in diabetes mellitus complicated by uricosuric nephropathy (M±m)

Indicators	Healthy ones (n=10)	Group I (n=20)	Group II (n=30)
Creatinine clearance (ml/min/1.73m ²)	108,0±4,8	160,0±6,3 p<0,001	156,4±11,2 p<0,001
Water reabsorption (%)	98,2±0,7	96,1±1,1 p>0,05	96,6±1,2 p>0,05
Sa-clearance (ml/min/1.73m ²)	0,8±0,04	1,2±0,08 p<0,05	1,6±1,0 p<0,001
Uric acid clearance (ml/min/1.73m ²)	8,4±0,8	14,6±1,2 p>0,05	16,1±0,9 p<0,05
Phosphorus clearance (ml/min/1.73m ²)	10,4±0,8	16,0±0,4 p<0,05	18,1±2,0 p<0,001
Ammonia (mol/milk)	88,2±9,2	76,2±6,7 p<0,05	62,6±5,1 p<0,001
Titrateable acid (mol/milk)	56,5±4,1	34,6±2,6 p<0,05	28,0±4,5 p<0,001
Uric acid (mol/l)	46,6±2,4	36,2±2,7 p<0,001	31,4±2,5 p<0,001
Fractional clearance of uric acid (%)	3,4±0,25	4,6±0,5 p<0,05	6,5±0,6 p<0,001
	8,7±0,4	12,0±0,8 p>0,05	20,5±1,2 p<0,001

The concentration function of the kidneys is evaluated by the Zimnitsky test. A more accurate assessment of this function can be carried out by eating dry products. However, due to the possibility of developing dehydration and increased blood glucose in patients with QD, it was not possible to transfer. The average weight of the studied groups is presented in (table 3.2).

Table 3 Maximum specific gravity of urine according to the Zimnitsky test in type I QD

	Group I	Group II	p
Average index of maximum specific gravity	1028±3,8	1020±4,2	>0,05
Daily diuresis (ml/milk)	1324±134,0	1408±92,0	>0,05

According to Table 3, patients with uricosuric nephropathy tend to increase diurnal diuresis and decrease specific gravity, but both cases are not statistically significant (r>0.05). When the groups were compared with the main clinical-laboratory parameters, in patients with uricosuric nephropathy compared to the first group, the level of glycemia in the morning was reliably higher (9.3±0.2% and 6.3±0.1%, r<0.001), glycosylated hemoglobin (7,9±0.2 and 6.0±0.1%). Clear changes were detected in the chemical composition of blood and urine. In patients with urate nephropathy, diuresis is significantly reduced (r<0.001), which is more evident when abacterial and bacterial interstitial nephritis are added, accordingly, it was found that although the glomerular filtration rate at this stage of QD is high, the specific gravity of urine is relatively low (table 3.3).

Table 4 Characteristics of urine composition and partial kidney function in children with QD with hyperuricemia (M±m)

Group indicators	Healthy ones (N=16)	Group I (N=20)	Group II (N=30)
Creatinine clearance (ml/min/1.73)	108,6±4,8	160,0±6,3	156,4±12,3p<0,001
Water Reabsorption(%)	98,2±0,06	96,6±0,11 p>0,05	96,6±0,2p<0,05
Urates (mmol/milk)	3,16±0,38	5,6±0,5 p<0,001	6,5±0,6 p<0,001
Oxalates (mmol/milk)	0,36±0,04	0,57±0,05 p<0,05	0,74±0,06 p<0,001
Phosphorus clearance (ml/min/1.73m ²)	10,4±0,8	16,0 ±4,3	18±5,0 p<0,001
Calcium clearance (ml/min/1.73m ²)	0,82±0,04	1,6±0,8 p>0,05	2,1±1,3 p<0,001
Calcium (mg/milk)	31,3±3,5 p<0,05	74,6±2,2 p<0,05	76,8±1,2 p<0,05
Phosphorus (mg/milk)	478,7±9,1	575,4±7,0 p<0,05	610,0±54 p<0,001
Ammonia (mmol/milk)	56,5±8,3	36,0±4,6 p<0,05	22,0±4,5 p<0,001

According to Table 4, the daily excretion of urates in children with hyperuricemia and hyperuricosuria of the first type QD was 2.5-3 times higher than that of healthy children (5.6±0.5-6.5±0.6mmol/milk, in healthy children 3.16- 0.38 mmol/day; s<0.001), more than half of these patients have hyperoxaluria (0.57±0.005-0.74±0.06 mmol/day, 0.36-0.04 mmol/day in healthy children, r<0.001). Creatinine clearance is high (r<0.001, water reabsorption in renal tubules is not significantly changed (0.05), but tubular reabsorption of phosphorus is reliably reduced when compared with healthy children (r<0.001). A decrease in ammonia acidogenetic function of the kidneys is characterized by a decrease in ammonia excretion and titratable acids (r<0.001). Overpayment of nephrotoxic metabolites (urates, oxalates, calcium) was found in biological fluids, which may cause additional stress to all parts except for their nephrotoxic effect, and may be a factor accelerating the formation of dysmetabolic and later diabetic nephropathy. The obtained data confirm that QD is hyperuricemia, hyperuricosuria, and urate nephropathy are common in children. The onset of the disease is mild, and the course is relatively positive. However, if it is not diagnosed early, i.e., if purine metabolism is not corrected by diet and medication, the process may become chronic (interstitial nephritis, kidney (including microbial inflammatory process, oxidative stress, DN and membrnolysis as a result of chronic renal failure) can be observed.

Conclusion

As a result of the above investigations, it can be said that in nephropathies caused by diabetes, some substances include; increased clearance of calcium, phosphorus, ammonia, creatinine, decreased water reabsorption, increased urate and oxalate salts in urine. This, in turn, leads to an increase in the symptoms of the disease and an increase in the rate of the disease. Taking into account the type of disease, it is difficult to stop dysmetabolic changes, but we can conclude that it can be prevented by timely dietary and drug correction.

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GENERAL UNDERSTANDING OF MYSTICISM

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Annotation

This article discusses the philosophy of Sufism, which is widely interpreted in Eastern Muslim literature. At the same time, conclusions are drawn on the basis of some important sources on this issue. The most general concepts of Sufism are described. The meaning of the main terms is given.

Keywords: Sufism, basic concepts, themes of Sufism, image, plot.

Introduction

Sufism is primarily a teaching based on Islam. It is impossible to imagine and interpret Sufism without Islam, and our classic literature without Sufism and religious precepts. Sufism is, to put it bluntly, a higher level of Allahliness. Only a person who fully obeys the laws of Sharia and the rules of believing-Muslims can enter the history of Sufism. Sufism is the path of perfect perfection. "Odamiyning dunyoda bo'lmoqining sababi ikki niarsaga xojati bordur. Biri ulki, avvalgi dilni asbob (tahdil) halokatidin saqlagay va aning g'azosin (mevasin) hosil qilgay. Va yana biri badanni halok qiladurgan narsalardan saqlagay va aning g'azosini qilgay va dilni g'azosi. Haq taoloning ma'rifati va muhabbatidir. Charoki, har narsani g'azosi o'z ta'bining muqtizosidurkim, dil ma'rifatini taqozo qilur, badanini asramoq dil uchundirkim, badan foniydur, va dil boqiydur" ("There are two reasons why a person is in the world. One is to save the previous language from the destruction of the tool (tahdil) and produce its fruit (mawasin). And another one is to protect the body from things that destroy it and to do its revenge and to heal the heart. Truth is the enlightenment and love of the Almighty. Charoki, I am the saint of my own nature, who is responsible for everything, I require the enlightenment of the mind, it is for the mind to take care of the body, the body is mortal, and the heart is eternal"), this is what is said in "Kimyoi Saodat Turki". [1, 131].

A relatively complete description of Sufism is given in the pamphlet "Sufism and Sufism Literature". [2. 60].

Source Analysis

Sufism is a way to develop both purity of body and purity of heart and bring it to the rank of perfect humanity. This path has a complex course, certain psychophysiological exercises, and mathematical stages. According to the contemporary Iranian writer Ali Dashti, the leaven of Sufism, which is "a combination of asceticism and spirituality", is derived from the Holy Qur'an. And the beliefs of strange peoples, such as Buddhists, spiritualists, Zoroastrians, Christian and neo-Platonic Sufis, gave it color.[3, 16, 17].

Busakhl Tustari (died 283 Hijri) said that a Sufi is a person who is pure in religion and knowledgeable in thought. May he live in Allah's memory, away from people. In his eyes, dust and gold are equal. Sufism is little. It is to rest with Allah and escape from the people.

Abulhusayn Nuri (died 295 A.H.) says: Sufis are a people whose souls are free from the tyranny of humanity, free from calamity. And at the very beginning they are extremely Hakka, leaving everything else. They are neither kings nor slaves. Sufism is neither a style nor a science, but a necessity. If there was an image, it could be acquired through effort, if there was knowledge, it would be created through education. It is impossible to enter Allah's property either by art or knowledge.

A faithful Sufi is able to be at ease in the state of poverty, and in the state of self-pity to consider others superior. Junaid Baghdadi (died 297): Sufism says that Allah will kill you from yourself, and He will resurrect you. Sufi is a zamindar, and he will run over him for better or for worse. May the cloud overshadow everything and water everyone like rain.

Sufism is to stay away from sensual claims, to descend to the quality of spirituality, to give priority to the good, to follow the message to the ummah and to follow the prophet.

Among the Uzbek scholars, Oibek's services in explaining Sufism deserve attention. He writes, "According to the Sufis, the whole world - material existence is not real, this world is apparent. The real truth is Allah, whose body is absolute. The nature that surrounds us, the things in it and all kinds of events are nothing but a reflection of that body of the absolute. Allah has put his reflection in this world in order to look at his beloved, as if Allah is in love with him. In the world, he forgets Allah and melts in it.

This point of view, which is called pantheism and unity of existence, is one of the components of Sufism". Oybek correctly pointed out common ideas between Sufism and Neoplatonists: "The world that we perceive between the senses is not the real world. It is a reflection of the eternally existing and real world of ideas. Understanding things in this world is nothing more than remembering ideas.

Neoplatonists, on the other hand, describe the essence of things as ideas, and ideas as the thoughts of Allah. Neoplatonism promoted emanation - the idea that lower forms arise from higher forms. The Supreme Creator is Allah. As a result of its emanation, logos - the carrier of ideas and their space - appeared. From this, the spirit, the soul of the world, as a result of this activity, things appeared in the form of models in ideas".

Oybek shows the stages of Sufism as "Tariqat, Khidayat, Enlightenment, Truth". Literary scholar Ibrahim Haqqul writes that "Sufism focused on the path of spiritual perfection in four stages: 1. Shariat. 2. Sect. 3. Enlightenment. 4. Truth.

Sharia - preparatory stage. Religious and legal rules, moral and divine instructions from the "Quran" and Hadiths are carefully mastered in it. It was not allowed to convert to the Tariqat without fulfilling the requirements of Sharia. "Sharia - Law: Tariqat - Way".

A step is taken in the leadership of the sect:

The sect needs a political murshid,

The murshid needs a murid of faith.

(Ahmed Yassavi) [5, 21-32]

Under the leadership of the pir, the solik who has reached the stage of the tariqat (the path of the tariqat) must pass 6 statuses:

1. Repentance. 2. Wara'. 3. Poverty. 4. Patience. 5. Risk. 6. Reza.

In the stage of enlightenment, the closeness between man and Allah is the skill and wisdom of perfect acquisition, and those who have reached it are called the Wayfarer (righteous) Arif. After that comes the last stage - Truth. It consists of Fano, Tajalli and Tawheed positions. (Ibid., pp. 21-32)

These stages and statuses have their own descriptions. For example, Repentance is the end of the path of misery and the beginning of the right path. In this case, the tax sum is not to be free from bad vices, but to shudder at the carelessness of arrogance, to abandon useless actions, and to hate the corruption of the soul and the disobedience of the heart that lead a person astray.

Repentance - The time has come to ask for salvation from Hajj: the servant has left the subjection of the soul. In this place, the difference between the tariqat and the repentance in the Shari'ah can be felt. A person who enters the Tariq must be completely free from sins and bad deeds and disobedience of the heart.

Wara is piety, moderation, purification and tranquility.

Faqr is poverty, lack of need, that is, getting rid of the pleasures of this world, overcoming material need.

Patience is the patience of total maths.

Tawakkul - in this status, the taxpayer surrenders all his faith and discretion completely to his beloved. Ibrahim Haqqul said that avoiding questions, not giving room for suspicion, not asking for favors, not accepting gifts are the necessary conditions of this status. (Ibrahim Haqqul. Cited source, page 24)

Contentment is calmness, that is, the ability to face the world's troubles, sufferings, tribulations, joys and sorrows with a firm will.

When these statuses are over, the stage of enlightenment comes. In it, the science of the wayfarer thoroughly grasps the truth. He perfectly perceives closeness with Alloh, "he sees the reflection of the quality of Hajj in every place and in everything"³. The owner of such knowledge is called arif. [6, 24]

The last stage is true and consists of 3 statuses:

1. Decay. 2. Tajalli. 3. Monotheism (Tawahud).

Fano - in the words of Navoi, "Death", that is, the complete disappearance of the soul, only the remembrance of Alloh and the thought of Alloh remain in the heart.

Tajalli - the lover feels that all his actions are absorbed into the actions of the Truth. He perceives only divine attributes. And finally, the union of the human soul with the absolute being, with the divine soul, takes place in the state of monotheism. We use the mathematical stages of the path of the tax that entered the path of the sect towards Alloh from the definitions given by Bertels and Sultanmurad Olim: Repentance - in this case, the tax man enters the path of self-improvement on the basis of full compliance with the laws of Sharia.

2. Wara' (carelessness). In this case, the taxman makes a serious distinction between halal and haram and strictly adheres to abstinence.

3. Zuhd (abstinence, self-control, patience). In this case, one should be completely free from all the things that interfere with the way of Alloh and distract one's mind: various sins, good clothes, housing, food, family, and life worries.

4. Faqr - (poverty, poverty). In this case, the tax collector takes his poverty and realizes that he is recklessly poor before Alloh. In this regard, it is permissible to remember the hadith of our prophet "al-faqr faqri" (poverty is the pride).

5. Patience. When the taxman reaches this status, he endures any kind of punishment. He is indifferent to good and bad, that is, he does not get sad in bad days, he does not get carried away by good days and joys, he always reacts to events with great calmness.

6. Tawakkul (reliance on Alloh). In this case, the tax payer completely submits to the will of Alloh, that is, he only thinks about the moment he is breathing today, yesterday is gone, what will happen tomorrow and what he will do is up to Alloh. In short, "don't worry about the past or the future, rest is this moment, don't call other days rest."

7. Reza. (obedience, subjugation) - in this status, the tax is completely cut off from this world. Only Alloh can think.

In the process of going through the stages of this ritual, the tax falls into such a mental state that it feels a sense of closeness. This is called a case. It is as follows:

1. Qurb (proximity). Feeling a sense of direct proximity to Alloh.

2. Love (ishq). Feeling a fiery love for Alloh.

3. Danger (panic). The tax collector is afraid that he could not fulfill his duty before Alloh or that he committed a sin.

4. Rajo (hope). Hope for Alloh's grace and mercy.

5. Noise. (In this case, the tax is overflowing with pleasure.)

6. Uns (friendship). In this state, similar to love, tax feels a higher level of intimacy.

7. Itmonina (peace of mind, confidence). Rest in peace with Alloh's forgiving, watchful, loving kindness.

8. In observation. In this way, the tax collector not only feels close to Alloh, but as if he sees him.

9. Close(Yaqin) — (trust). Full awareness of the existence of the spiritual world, full confession.

After these cases comes Fano, which is the beginning of reality, that is, the tax collector feels that he is spiritually lost. The final destination - in Baga, the taxpayer separates from his identity and merges with the spirit of Alloh - achieves immortality. This is the highest case. It is the end of the tax purpose.

Conclusion

In the work of Alisher Navoi, Sufism ideas and symbols are very consistently developed. Especially, the ideas of divine love are more deeply reflected in the work "Mahbubul-kulub":

"Love is a shining star... the light of mankind's eye, and hence its wisdom: love is a precious jewel, and hence the jewel and the price of the crown of humanity."

Love is so stubborn that in front of him the king is equal to the king: he is so tyrannical that in his eyes both the dirty and the wicked are the same as the pure lover.

The hustle and bustle of the world's market and the bustle of the marketplace of all things in the world is because of love. Without it, human speech is like a lifeless body, human expressions are like flowers and grass without basil.[8.53]

So, Navoi connects Sufi meanings and ideas to each of his images and characters. Although the image of divine love is often exaggerated, it has caused the creation of many aphorisms, wise sayings, and philosophical conclusions. Nature, events in society, correctly evaluates the essence of things based on divine power. Such a strong, fixed belief has not changed throughout the life and work of the poet.

Revealing the content of Sufism is one of the most important and fundamental areas of literary science today. Navoi's creativity is an incomparable source of this field.

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ARTISTIC APPROACHES TO THE FIGURE OF AMIR TEMUR DURING THE RENAISSANCE

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Abstract

The article shows that the European countries' artistic approaches to the image of Amir Temur and the human qualities of Amir Temur were positively interpreted by European writers. The article emphasizes that the life of a great historical figure has attracted the attention of world scientists since the 15th - 16th centuries.

Keywords: historians, fantastic elements, historical facts, historians, chronicles, political scientists, humanist ideas.

By the 16th century, not only historians, but also many writers and playwrights addressed the life and work of Amir Temur in their works. The use of many fantastic elements in describing the life and activities of Amir Temur began in the 16th century. As a result, a number of chronicles about Amir Temur were created in Italy and Spain in the first half of the 16th century, and in Germany, France and England in the second half of the 16th century. In these works, based on the works of Italian historians, in addition to historical facts, various myths and fictions are widely used.

In Western Europe, where humanistic ideas are spreading more and more widely, there were many works aimed at positiveizing Sahibqiran in every way. For example, in the middle of the 15th century, the well-known Italian humanist Poggio Brachcolini wrote an ode to Amir Temur. Niccolò Machiavelli, a great political scientist who lived and worked in the late 15th - early 16th centuries, gave a high assessment to Amir Temur's work ("Shakhanshah").

Jean Du Bec's work entitled "History of the Great Emperor Amir Temur" published in 1594 is one of such works. We used the second edition of this work in our research.

The information given in Du Bec's work differs sharply from what Western Europeans knew about Amir Temur in the 15th - 16th centuries. In the preface to the work, the author states that he received this information from the Arab historian al-Hasan. He met Du Bec al-Hasan in Levante, Spain. Al-Hasan in the work is actually a fictitious person who serves to convey to the reader the thoughts of the author - Du Bec himself. Du Bec was the first in Western Europe to express the opinion that Amir Temur came from the family of "Tatar emperors" and noted that he was the son of the ruler of Zagatai (Chigatai). Also, according to Du Bec, Amir Temur was sympathetic to Christians and had a deistic worldview:

- Although he believed in one God, the creator of all things, he respected all religions, and often repeated that the power of God is seen in the diversity of nations, and nations have different beliefs in him. ...

Almost all prose works created during the Renaissance, including Du Bec's History of the Great Emperor Amir Temur, tell the story of Aksalla, a Genoese legendary figure who stood by Amir Temur in all his

campaigns. In Du Bec's work that we are analyzing, Aksalla is described as Sahibqiron's closest advisor and chief military commander:

- There was a Christian in his palace, and the ruler loved him very much; he was highly respected, his name was Aksalla, and he was a Genoese; he grew up in the palace from his youth; regardless of his religion, the ruler entrusted him with the biggest and most important jobs.

In particular, in the third chapter of the work entitled "Amir Temur's War against the Turkish Emperor Bayezid", it is narrated that Amir Temur receives a letter asking for help from the Emperor of Trabezond Paleologus. Sahibqiron, who is preparing to fight against the Turkish sultan, assigns Aksalla to bring additional troops from Movarounnahr:

- The ruler, who was gaining fame because of Aksalla, did not hesitate to send him to Chigatay, Aksalla had to collect an army from every settlement and return with them in the spring.

As in the works of Greek historians, in the works written under their influence in Western Europe in the 15th-16th centuries, Amir Temur's conquest of Egypt and China is mentioned. Du Bec's work "History of the Great Emperor Amir Temur" is not exempt from this. In particular, the letter of the Trabezond emperor Paleologus reached the hands of Amir Temur in Kambala, the capital of the Tatar kingdom, in the residence of his father-in-law and uncle, Buyuk Khan. After a long siege of Kambala, Amir Temur finally defeated the rebellion led by Kalibes, and then went to fight against the Ottoman Turks and was victorious.

The events of the work take place mainly in Samarkand, Kambala, Trabezond and Caesarea near Ankara. There are characters such as Amir Temur, Bayazid, his sons and his wife (the daughter of the Bulgarian king Lazar), Kalibes, Aksalla, the Pasha of Anatolia, as well as the prince of Charikan, Khianson, who fought side by side with Sahibkiran, and the prince of Tanay (Don). Aksalla, which does not have a historical prototype, can be a fantastic representation of the fact that Genoese served in the Sahibqiran palace.

Du Bec hardly mentions the sultan in the picture of the battle between Amir Temur and Bayazid. Only the defeat of his army, the escape of Bayazid and his sons, and their capture (the third chapter of the work) are described.

Amir Temur, on the other hand, is a positive and even ideal hero, a savior of Christians. He is a general, a noble and tolerant person. Amir Temur attaches great importance to the timely motivation of all soldiers in his army, and demands that they refrain from looting in captured cities and lands.

Du Bec's book gained great popularity in Western Europe. As early as 1597, it was translated into English. As a result, in 1603, English historian Richard Knoll's "General Turkish History" was published. The chapter dedicated to Bayazid in the work is completely based on Du Bec's book "History of the Great Emperor Amir Temur", and in some places it is copied verbatim from it. A small excerpt from Du Bec's work is included in the Byzantine chronicler Halcondil's work entitled "History of the Decline of the Greek (Byzantine) Empire" published in Paris in 1620. *Histoire du Grand Tamerlan d'apres les Memoires de l'Arabe Alhacent* (History of the Great Amir Timur based on the Memoirs of Arab al-Hasan) published in 1677 by the French historian Seigneur de Sainctyon, as the title suggests, it is nothing more than Du Bec's book "History of the Great Emperor Amir Temur". The work about Amir Temur, created by Jean Du Bec, became widely known throughout Europe in the 17th century. The artistic approach to the image of Amir Temur in Western Europe began with these works.

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CORRELATION RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN THE MAIN VALUE-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF COTTON GROWN IN DIFFERENT REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

On the basis of determining the degree of variability, correlative dependence and resistance to wilt of introgressive ridges in different soil and climate conditions, the ridges with high yield, quick ripening, fiber yield of 41.0-43%, quality indicators and high adaptability were selected. "S-6782" variety, which has a high index of valuable economic traits among their populations, was selected as a variety resistant to adverse factors of the external environment when new medium-fiber introgressive varieties were grown under the same conditions in different soil-climatic conditions of our republic.

Keywords: cotton, duration of vegetation period, adaptability, geographical long hybridization, introgressive forms, variety testing, correlation.

The analysis of the effectiveness of the selection work carried out in the selection of agricultural crops in many countries of the world shows that the selection methods used in this process should be adapted to the local soil-climate, weather and technological and socio-economic conditions of each country. Therefore, in the creation of new varieties of agricultural crops, evaluating the potential of genotypes in several geographical locations at the same time, identifying forms with the possibility of wide adaptability is one of the promising directions. At this point, it is of great scientific and practical importance to create productive and promising varieties based on introgressive ridges that are productive, have high quality indicators and economic efficiency, and are resistant to adverse environmental factors.

Correlation relationships between the length of the growing season and other valuable - economic: We determined the correlation coefficients between the length of the growing season and some valuable economic traits in ten rows of *Gossypium hirsutum* L. medium fiber cotton grown in three different regions of Uzbekistan.

It is known that for purpose-oriented selection processes, it is necessary to study the correlation between various characters. Thus, the researchers found a close relationship between yield and the number of bolls in cotton (from 0.84 to 0.91), an average positive correlation was observed between boll size and yield ($r = 0.32$ to 0.61). A moderate to weak positive correlation (from 0.28 to 0.39) was observed between productivity and seed weight, and a weak negative correlation was observed between productivity and fiber yield. A high degree of correlation was observed between yield and 1000 seed weight. Average positive correlation between pod size and plant height; weak positive correlations were noted between seed weight and fiber length. Seed weight

and fiber yield are generally negatively correlated [ibid]. By identifying forms that embody different interactions, researchers influence the recombination that occurs in hybrids.

During 2019-2020, a weak positive correlation was observed between the duration of the growing season and the weight of raw cotton in one bag ($r = +0.21 - +0.48$) (see Table 5.1). In 2018, a different level of correct correlation between the indicated characters was shown in the tested ridges, from 0.19 (in Tashkent region) to 0.94 (in Fergana region). Close correlation was also observed in Kashkadarya region $r = 0.54$. That is, as the length of the growth period increased, the pod weight increased. It should be noted that the breeder is interested in a negative correlation between speed and some character.

In most cases, the correlation between length of growing season and 1000 seed weight was absent ($r = -0.07 - +0.03$), or both inverse and positive were weak ($r = -0.21 - +0.28$). The groups tested in Fergana region in 2018 were an exception and showed a high correlation $r = 0.50$. A moderate to strong positive correlation was found between length of growing season and fiber yield in all regions during the three-year trial (0.28 to 0.60).

Table 1 Correlation between growing season length and major economic traits of cotton lines

Symbol	Territory	years	Growth period continue0073	1 bag weight	1000 seed weight	Fiber length	The comparison is strong	Microneur	Productivity	Productivity
Growth period	Tashkent	2018	0.19	0.20	0.56	-0.09	0.28	0.74	0.15	-0.75
		2019	0.38	0.28	0.36	-0.05	0.12	-0.12	0.39	-0.33
		2020	0.31	-0.17	0.48	0.24	0.15	-0.24	0.31	-0.46
Growth period	Fergana	2018	0.94	0.50	0.35	0.32	0.50	0.20	0.91	0.08
		2019	0.32	0.03	0.49	0.29	0.59	0.33	0.32	0.19
		2020	0.48	0.04	0.49	-0.10	0.33	-0.02	0.47	0.35
Growth period	Kashkadarya	2018	0.54	0.13	0.60	-0.15	0.39	0.54	0.38	-0.73
		2019	0.21	-0.07	0.28	-0.11	0.38	0.48	0.26	0.42
		2020	0.31	-0.21	0.40	0.35	0.22	-0.11	0.03	-0.07

A very weak correlation was observed between growth period duration and fiber length: from no correlation ($r = -0.05$, $r = -0.07$) to a weak positive correlation ($r = 0.35$). Very close correlations were observed between the speed and the specific tensile strength of the fiber (from 0.12 to 0.59). Correlation relationships between speed and fiber microneuri were shown differently in different test years - from weakly negative ($r = -0.24$), absence of correlation ($r = -0.02$), to strong positive ($r = 0.74$ in the tested ridge groups in Tashkent region in 2018). A high correlation was also found

between the duration of the growing season and the fiber micronaire in the ridge groups tested in Kashkadarya region in 2018 and 2019 ($r=0.48$ and $r=0.54$, respectively)

In most cases, a weak positive correlation was observed between the length of the growing season and productivity (from 0.15 to 0.38). We observed a strong correlation between them in the ridge groups of Fergana region in 2020 ($r = 0.54$) and 2018 ($r = 0.91$). In the experiments in Kashkadarya region in 2020, there was no correlation between these signs ($r = 0.03$).

A weak inverse relationship between the duration of the growing season and productivity was found in Tashkent and Kashkadarya regions in 2018 ($r= -0.75$ and $r = -0.73$, respectively). That is, fast-growing forms showed high productivity. In a three-year trial in Fergana region, it was observed that the correlation between the indicated signs was weak ($r = 0.19$ and $r = 0.35$) or non-existent ($r = 0.08$).

According to three-year experimental data, fiber yield, productivity, fiber tensile strength, cotton raw weight per boll are strongly related to increasing growing season length, unlike plant growing area. In our experiments, early ripening was closely related to productivity, which was also confirmed by the inverse relationship between these characters, i.e., the shorter the growing season in the ridges, the lower their productivity.

Correlation between fiber yield and other economic parameters:

We determined the phenotypic correlation between fiber yield and some economic traits in ten rows of *Gossypium hirsutum* medium fiber cotton grown in three different regions of Uzbekistan. According to the data in the table, in all the test years in different growing areas in the studied ridges, there was an average positive correlation between the fiber output and the length of the growing season, and the correlation coefficient ranged from 0.28 to 0.60.

That is, with the increase in the duration of the growth period, the fiber output also increases. In most cases, there was no correlation between the yield of fiber and the weight of raw cotton in one sack, except in Fergana region in 2020. and in Kashkadarya region in 2018. weak positive correlations were observed ($r=0.29$ and $r=0.23$, respectively).

In cotton ridges, a weak and high negative correlation was observed between fiber yield and 1000 seed weight (-0.02 to -0.54) in contrast to the growing area. It should be noted that in the third trial year, the relationship between these characteristics did not exist in Tashkent and Fergana regions, that is, high fiber yield was observed in both small-seeded and large-seeded forms (see Table 2).

Breeders have always been interested in creating cotton varieties that embody high fiber yield and quality. Studying the interrelationship between these characters determines the target direction in the search for forms with a positive correlation.

According to the table, in the first two years of experiments, weak and moderately negative correlations were found between fiber yield and length in ridges.

2-Table Correlation between fiber yield and key economic traits in cotton ridges

Symbol	Territory	Years	Growth period continues	1 bag weight	1000 seed weight	Fiber length	The comparison is strong	Microneur	Productivity	Productivity
Fiber output	Tashkent	2018	0.56	0.09	-0.16	-0.05	0.35	0.50	0.05	-0.33
		2019	0.36	-0.01	-0.45	-0.35	0.006	0.30	0.03	-0.07
		2020	0.47	0.05	-0.02	0.39	-0.14	-0.16	0.05	-0.01
Fiber output	Fergana	2018	0.35	0.09	-0.45	-0.26	0.04	0.57	-0.05	-0.09
		2019	0.49	-0.03	-0.54	-0.11	0.22	0.83	-0.09	-0.02
		2020	0.49	0.29	-0.02	0.03	-0.01	-0.20	0.33	0.49
Fiber output	Kashkadarya	2018	0.60	0.23	-0.32	-0.30	0.20	0.71	-0.02	-0.47
		2019	0.28	-0.03	-0.21	-0.34	0.10	0.46	-0.09	0.17
		2020	0.40	-0.005	-0.20	0.06	0.07	-0.20	0.24	0.30

The correlation coefficient ranged from -0.05 (in Tashkent region in 2018) to -0.35 (in the same place in 2019). In 2020, in all three regions, the correlation coefficient changed in the positive direction (from 0.03 to 0.39). Perhaps this is due to the influence of the choice of forms embodying high fiber yield and quality.

The specific tensile strength of the fiber was in most cases weakly correlated with the yield of the fiber or no correlation was present. Only in the Tashkent region, in the first year of the test, a weak positive correlation was found between these signs ($r=0.35$).

It is an indicator that describes the thinness and length of the microneuro-cotton fiber. For Grades I and II cotton, the appropriate range is 3.5 – 4.9 microns/inch. Below 3.5 is considered non-fibrous and has low cellulose content. If it is higher than 4.9, the fiber is considered excessively coarse. In addition, the breeder should be interested in the negative correlation between microneurism and some other characters.

According to the table, in the years 2018 and 2019, i.e., the first two years of the test, an average positive correlation was found between fiber output and microneuri in most cases, and the correlation coefficient ranged from 0.30 to 0.57. In Fergana and Kashkadarya regions, a strong correlation between these characteristics was found in different years ($r=0.83$ and $r=0.71$, respectively). As observed with fiber length, the correlation coefficient shifted in the third test year, only in a different, negative direction. 2020 a weak inverse correlation was found between these traits in all three regions (-0.20 to -0.16).

Fiber yield had little correlation with productivity. In the third year of testing, in two cases in Fergana and Kashkadarya regions, weak correct correlation was found ($r=0.33$ and $r=0.24$, respectively).

During the trial years, in most cases, the yield of the ridges did not depend on the fiber yield. That is, both ridges with high fiber output and low ones can be productive. 2018 In Tashkent and Kashkadarya regions, an average inverse correlation was found between fiber output and productivity ($r= -0.33$ and $r= -0.47$, respectively). In Fergana region, in 2020. these signs were mutually positively correlated $r=0.49$.

Thus, in the correlation analysis between the fiber yield and some valuable economic traits, it was found that there is a correct relationship between the fiber yield and the length of the growing season, according to the data of the three-year test in cotton lines of genetic origin. That is, with the increase in the duration of the growth period, the fiber output also increases. There was no significant correlation between fiber yield and bag weight of cotton in most cases. In the studied ridges, there was an inverse relationship between fiber yield and 1000 seed weight, different from the area of cultivation. A weak to moderately strong inverse relationship was observed between fiber yield and length. The specific tensile strength of the fiber had a weak or no correlation with the yield of the fiber. A moderately strong positive correlation was found between fiber output and microneuri in most cases. Fiber yield was not significantly related to cotton yield and productivity. It should be noted that as a result of selections made on a number of characters such as fiber yield and weight of 1000 seeds, fiber yield and length, fiber yield and micron, we managed to change the correlation in the required direction.

Conclusions

1. It was found that fiber yield, productivity, relative tensile strength of fiber, weight of raw cotton in one boll are strongly related to the increase in the length of the growing season. It has been shown that there is no correlation between early ripening and 1000 seed weight in most cases. A very weak correlation was found between cooking speed and fiber length. Correlations of different degrees and directions were noted between the duration of the growth period and fiber microneuria. A negative correlation between the length of the growing season and productivity was characteristic for the studied ridges.

2. A moderately strong positive correlation was found between fiber yield and length of growing season. Different degrees of inverse relationship between fiber yield and 1000 seed weight were observed in the studied cotton lines, depending on the area of cultivation. A weak to moderately strong inverse relationship was noted between fiber yield and length. The relative tensile strength of the fiber was weakly correlated with the yield of the fiber, or no correlation existed. A moderately strong positive correlation was found between fiber output and microneuri in most cases. The yield of fiber was not closely related to the weight of cotton raw material in one boll, cotton yield and productivity. As a result of selections made on a number of characters such as fiber yield and 1000 seed weight, fiber yield and length, fiber yield and micron, we managed to shift the correlation in the required direction.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF THE SPEECH CULTURE AND ITS ROLE IN THE MEDICAL PROFESSION

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ABSTRACT

This article serves to develop future medical staffs' communication with patients. The article includes various aspects of speech culture, including the history of speech culture, the style of speech, types of communication, and etc. The recommendations given in the article can be used to enrich the textbooks and manuals of medical higher education institutions.

Keywords. Physician culture, medical staff morale, professional speech culture, types of speech, speech etiquette, means of communication,

INTRODUCTION

Development of the professional speech culture of future doctors in medical universities is one of the important stages in the higher education system. In one of his speeches, the head of our country emphasized the need to include special courses such as "Medical staff morale", "Physician culture"[1]. The development of professional speech culture is primarily a process related to the implementation of measures aimed at increasing the efficiency of the health care system in our country, the introduction of new state standards into the system and, in accordance with them, improving the speech skills of future doctors.

The science of speech culture has been introduced in medical higher education institutions, and through this science, future doctors learn the art of communicating with patients and establishing professional relationships with them. Professional speech culture is inextricably linked with language culture. It is a field dealing with language rules, literary language and its norms. The culture of medical speech is very different from the art of public speaking. The goal of teaching this subject is not to train future doctors to be eloquent, but to help them to establish professional relationships between patients.

DISCUSSIONS

The doctrine of speech culture also has a long history. Although it was first formed as a doctrine in Rome and Athens, we can learn from sources that this art existed in India, Assyria, Babylon and Egypt before it was accepted as a doctrine. It is known that in those times, statesmen had to be aware of public speaking in order to be promoted to a high position [2]. We can see as an example the life of the Greek orator Demosthenes (384-322 BC) and Cicero (106-43 BC), who were able to create a unique school of speech and rhetoric in human society.

In Russia, attention to oratory developed in the 17th-18th centuries, that is, during the reign of Peter I. In that period, public speaking branched into 5 areas:

1. Eloquence among people in the above circle;

2. Military oratory;
3. Public speaking;
4. Religious speech;
5. Diplomatic speech[3].

It is known that in the history of Central Asian culture, the art of oratory has its own level and has been studied on the basis of sources since ancient times. We can find proof of our words through Mahmud Koshgari's work "Devonu lug'otit turk". This work describes the "rules of speech etiquette" [4].

Speaking about speech culture, we should mention the great Uzbek poet Alisher Navoi. The works of the great poet "Mahbubul-qulub", "Muhokamatul lug'atayn" and "Majolisun nafois" are dedicated not only to the study of the Uzbek language and its place and the culture of Uzbek speech, but also to the whole world. It is also focused on solving problems related to linguistics studied by linguists.

So, mankind's desire to speak effectively, correctly, fluently and beautifully, and the rules related to it, have their own past. The desire for eloquence, the rules and standards of the language have been improving according to the needs of the times. In order for future doctors to be able to successfully continue their professional activities, it is necessary to have professional speech culture. Because the correct and effective communication between the doctor and the patient serves to facilitate the treatment of the disease.

There are speech styles in linguistics, which are divided into 5 types:

1. Conversation style (free and informal speech).
2. Scientific style (discourse on science, technology).
3. Formal style (speech in which working papers, documents are conducted).
4. Artistic style (speech with artistic coloring).
5. Journalistic style (report, newspaper, broadcast speech).

Having analyzed the above speech styles, future doctors should know how to use the appropriate style based on the situation. Since ancient times, it has been believed that the word has great power, that is, with one word, it can heal a person, or on the contrary, it can cause the death of a healthy person. Therefore, doctors should pay attention to their speech culture in the process of professional activity.

The literature related to the development of professional speech culture in medicine, including professional speech standards, medical-linguistic literature, theoretical and practical information, professional activity in the field of medicine, analysis of communication between doctor and patient shows that this topic is not sufficiently covered in the field. is showing. The development of professional speech culture of students of medical higher education institutions is a set of interrelated components of the medical field and linguistics, and this connection serves to develop the skills of reading, writing and speaking related to the field in students. In addition, students are required to concentrate, act independently in acquiring professional and linguistic knowledge, actively participate in the pedagogical process and complete the necessary tasks.

Professional-linguistic competence is developed in the process of forming reading, writing, listening comprehension and speaking skills, as well as performing exercises and tasks related to the field and actively participating in questions and answers. In most cases, professional-linguistic-didactic competence in non-philological areas is developed through dialogue, conversation, question-and-answer, independent activity of students, use of scientific literature, and creation of short stories on the topic.

The practice of including the science of professional speech culture in the curriculum of medical universities in our country has shown that linguist pedagogues are aimed at developing the professional speech of medical students, forming the necessary culture in them, and establishing the relationship between future doctors and patients. It is the need of the hour to set goals and guide students towards these goals.

Within the scope of the science of speech culture, the teacher explains and teaches the methods of communication, communication and relationship between the doctor and the patient, and linguistically analyzes how to behave in different situations. However, from the point of view of language and speech, students have the right to decide what to do in a professional situation, how to speak and how to communicate with patients based on their own style. Therefore, the main task of the teacher is to teach the students the manners between the doctor and the patient and the methods of establishing speech communication in a professional situation, and the students develop their professional-linguodidactic competences through these methods.

The main goal of developing professional-linguodidactic competence is to improve communication between future doctors and patients. So, communication is understood as the establishment of speech communication between people, exchange of information, listening and understanding of the interlocutor. Professional-medical communication means psychological and social interaction between doctors and patients, receiving and giving information, providing therapeutic effect, and organizing a verbal response to the situation.

Unlike other fields, communication in the medical field is a very important tool, which doctors use correctly to solve medical problems, to successfully implement treatment processes, to organize a professional relationship between a doctor and a patient, and to help patients. It can be used as a socio-psychological solution in treatment. In addition, future doctors will be able to establish good communication with their colleagues and exchange information about the field by developing their professional-linguistic-didactic competencies.

It is known that the process of information exchange and its understanding is a communicative aspect of communication. There are the following types of means of communication used in the process of communication: oral (speech); non-verbal (mimicry, gestures, pantomime); extralinguistic (laughing, crying, pauses in speech, speed of speech); paralinguistic (voice range, timbre, voice quality) [5]. Australian scientist A. Piz believes that 50% of information is received through gestures and facial expressions; More than 30% of information is received through paralinguistic means; Less than 10% of information is understood through content. It should be noted that only information is transmitted through sentences and words, but through non-verbal means a relationship with the interlocutor is established.

Basically, the purpose of communication is different depending on the origin and content of the fields. For example, communication in the field of entrepreneurship is aimed at improving the organization, production, scientific, commercial and other goals of a certain subject. The goal of psychological communication is to understand the person, sympathize with him, and find a solution to his mental problems. In the communication between the doctor and the patient, the balance of business and psychological communication goals should be maintained, that is, it should be embodied in convincing the patient, establishing a reliable and warm relationship with him, and so on. At this point, it should be noted that in order to improve the patient's quality of life and successfully treat the disease, the doctor

must communicate with his relatives and exchange information. The doctor's communication with relatives can significantly contribute to the recovery of the patient from the disease.

In communication between the doctor and the relatives of the patient, the doctor is often expected to: inform about the patient's condition; hospitalization of the patient; answer questions in a vernacular language; listen to and respond to the opinions of loved ones; taking into account the patient's faith in life, his own thoughts and opinions; treat the patient and his relatives with respect; correct understanding and acceptance of their feelings and thoughts.

In many cases, we can face big differences in the communication between the doctor and the patient and his relatives. Doctors do not fully and adequately explain the disease, often use medical terms and terms, do not take into account the patient's family situation, problems and circumstances. On the contrary, they give brief information about the disease and rush to take treatment measures as soon as possible. Such a situation can cause uncomfortable and difficult situations for the patient and his relatives.

In most cases, the first question or indicator asked in questionnaires and sociological studies conducted by scientists is "the doctor's communication with the patient", and the second is "the doctor's attitude towards the patient and his relatives". In the remaining places, the doctor's work experience, patients' opinions about them, the doctor's personal qualities, and finally the doctor's education are asked. It can be seen that professional communication of a doctor is one of the most important aspects that he should master.

The professional linguistic and didactic competence of the doctor is manifested in the following: determining the presence of pathology and explaining it to the patient, studying the psychological state of the patient, calming him down, giving spiritual encouragement, comforting, communicating with the patient, obtaining the necessary information and giving, reducing the anxiety of the patient, instilling hope in him, eliminating misconceptions and perceptions about the disease and convincing him of goodness, hiding about the symptoms or consequences of a serious illness only for the benefit of the patient, or giving information only to his relatives .

CONCLUSION

It is known that the course of any disease depends not only on its causes and triggers, but also on the patient's body and mental state. Therefore, a qualified doctor should stabilize the patient's psychological peace and eliminate negative thoughts before treating the patient's illness. For example, it is necessary to give the necessary advice to patients who think a lot about the disease, or, on the contrary, to conduct appropriate explanatory work for patients who do not pay attention to their health. Some patients may be tempted to think about their illness, and in such cases, they may develop the illness themselves through self-hypnosis. Therefore, doctors are required to have an individual approach to each patient, study their psychology, and have the appropriate art of communication.

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MODERN TRENDS IN TEACHING READING TO B1 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article reports on the effectiveness of modern trends and strategies to improve B1 learners' reading skills. These days, teaching reading is taken into consideration in not only Uzbekistan but also, over the world. Because, reading is one of the skills that many students feel troubled while doing. It is also considered one of the most important skills. That's why, improvement in this field requires lots of studies. And our research studies what counts as an improvement in reading skills for B1 learners; examines theoretical and empirical issues in measuring improvements in reading skills.

Keywords: teaching reading, modern trends, B1 learners, Reading-writing relationship, Content-based reading, Task-based reading, Sustained-silent reading, Social reading

Introduction

Reading has always been considered one of the most important skills. However, have you ever wondered why this is so? The reason is that it is through reading that a person will be able to discover new ideas and concepts. It develops your communication skills and expands your knowledge and concepts around you. Reading is one of the most useful and practical skills for all learners while this is the most challenging one. That's why, lots of linguists dealt with this skill and how to conduct it for students effectively so far. According to Urquhart and Weirth (2009), reading is the process of acquiring and interpreting information from a written text; in other words, it is the process of receiving information and understanding it. Johnson (2008) states that reading is a complex activity that requires the use of language to create meaning from written words. Based on the definitions, the purpose of reading is to gain information, verify existing knowledge, enhance knowledge of the language being read, or to keep informed on fields in which we read. Reading plays an important role in language skills. It was explained above that reading is a complex process, and teaching reading should be started as early as possible.

Therefore, B1 students need to be taught how to accomplish reading tasks effectively. Firstly, who is B1 learner? B1 learner is the third level of English proficiency according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). In everyday speech, such a student can be called an "intermediate student". It is clear that B1 learners have proficiency in reading. Moreover, B1 learners are regarded as teenagers, namely who study at 10 and 11 grades in Uzbekistan schools. Teachers should be skillful and find best ways of teaching reading to these learners because of behaviors in their ages. Current days, the modern trends are widely used to improve the ways to teach reading to students who learn English as a foreign language. These trends are also important in teaching reading B1 learners. Because these learners can keep bored easily from traditional teaching methods. Teachers

should use these modern teaching trends in reading skill in order to encourage students to deal with reading tasks.

The purpose of this study is to present the benefits and importance of reading skill, as well as effectiveness of modern trends in teaching reading to students of 10-11 grades in Uzbek schools. The analysis of the questionnaires in the practical part of this article shows that by being exposed to modern teaching trends in reading students overcome their previous difficulties in understanding reading material.

Literature Review

Reading has an important role in all language skills. Therefore, a great many researchers gave their opinions on teaching reading.

According to Fahimsyah (2008), the basic steps to teach reading are to activate background knowledge, set purpose for reading, have students read for these purposes, and evaluate. With words of Gerlac, Ely, and Melnick, the teacher should use various techniques in teaching reading to make the students more understand about the material, and the teacher must be able to encourage their students to make reading as their habit and make them accustomed to reading. This, in due course, makes teachers of English as a foreign language apply a different set of methods and approaches until they find one which works the best for their students to solve problems they encounter in reading.

Different researchers have suggested numerous trends to improve reading comprehension and task completion based on reading passages. The modern teaching reading trends are as follows:

- a. Reading-writing relationship
- b. Content-based reading
- c. Task-based reading
- d. Sustained-silent reading
- e. Social reading

Reading-Writing Relationship.

This trend indicates that we read in order to put what we read into practice. Reading for writing is emphasized here because students tend to write from what they read. It is essential that developing knowledge of learned language requires the ability to read and write. The relationship between reading and writing has been studied from the same cognitive perspective and believers of the idea that reading influences writing claim that reading inspires and informs students' writing. It is to say that reading and writing were considered as separate acts before theories of causal relationships were studied. Goen and Gillotte-Tropp (2003) set six principles for teaching basic writing and reading together. The influence of reading on writing is often said to be a positive one, as learners get a number of benefits from reading a text, including new styles, new vocabulary and expressions, or even correcting their false ideas or grammar mistakes.

Content-Based Reading

According to this trend, we tend to integrate our prior knowledge of a topic with what we are reading right now. With words of Saint Augustine, the concept of content-based teaching refers to how teaching programs are organized around topics rather than linguistic topics. In this case, content was the core,

not grammar, function, or any other linguistic unit."It is the teaching of content or information in the language being learned with little or no direct or explicit effort to teach the language itself separately from the content being taught" Richards and Rodger stated (2009).

Task-Based Reading

A learner needs to do certain things with a reading text according to this trend. In this condition, teachers focus on doing some reading-based tasks instead of developing their students' reading abilities. It is believed that task-based reading increases students' ability to learn better when their attention is focused on the task instead of the language. Learners should focus on meaning and the activity should reflect real life; they can use any language they prefer. Ellis (2002) explains that TBLT relies on getting learners to perform tasks to help them develop knowledge and skills in a second language in a similar manner to their own language learning mechanisms.

Sustained-Silent Reading

This reading trend involves students and teachers reading free or silently for brief periods of time every day. Free reading or reading for pleasure is a trend that is gaining popularity these days. In other words, sustained silent reading is a form of school-based entertaining reading that allows students to select their own books and does not require testing for comprehension or book reports. According to Stephen Krashen, SSR has been shown to lead to gains in several literacy domains, including reading comprehension, vocabulary, writing skills, spelling, and knowledge of literature, science, and "practical knowledge".

Social Reading

This trend supports the idea of cooperative reading which is reading in a social context. It deals with students as members of a group when engaged in reading.

According to some researchers such as Chen, Cordon-Garcia, Alonso-Arevalo, Gomez-Diaz, Linder, social reading is a reader-centered mode of reading and focuses on the facilitation of readers' sharing and interaction encourages expressions of ideas and promotes collaborative survey. With the words of Hadwin, Jarvela, Miller, Chen, considering that social reading is a format of collaborative learning, it is necessary to connect the cognitive gaps among students and help them learn strategic control of their actions, thinking, and beliefs in the process of social interactions. In other words, social reading is a new reading style that puts emphasis on sharing, interaction, communication and social contact. As said by Wu, different from traditional paper-based reading, the rapid development of social reading has a great impact on readers' consumption of texts. Moreover, social reading puts more interest in social interaction during and after reading, encourages readers' self-generated content, and promotes the circulation and dissemination of information (Swann and Allington, 2009).

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated based on the theoretical basis and the aim of the study:

1. To what extent are modern trends in teaching reading effective in the development of reading skills of B1 learners?
2. How can the new trends in reading improve adults' interest in reading tasks at Uzbek state schools?

Methods

A total of thirty teachers from state schools in Tashkent participated in the research. Questionnaires were delivered to these English teachers. Three teachers of them got a MA degree and two teachers have almost an experience of 20 years in teaching. The other teachers got bachelor degree with experiences from 1 to 10 years. The descriptive method has been chosen to analyze the teachers' questionnaire. Sixteen questions were part of a larger study containing more other questions and statistical procedures to investigate the effectiveness of using reading modern trends. These questions were addressed to Reading techniques of teaching B1 learners.

Procedure

The teachers were asked to fill in the questionnaire about teaching reading using modern trends. The questionnaire contained two sections: Section one; general information, and section two; reading techniques. Most questions were open-ended questions when teachers are asked about their thoughts or explanations. Data were collected at the end of the second term before the holidays of New Year and after the teachers have finished checking the final exams of students. They were given enough time (a week) to answer the questionnaires, considering their responsibilities; some took more than a week to give them back, while others returned them in the same day.

Analyzing Results

For this research, we investigated the data collection from the questionnaire. Based on the results, we can reflect that modern trends in teaching reading to B1 learners are effective. Let's observe the answers of teachers who participated in the questionnaire.

Section1: general information

1. What is your full name?
2. How long have you been teaching?
3. Do you have a degree in IELTS, CEFR or others?
4. Do you have a degree in teaching (Bachelor\ Master\ Ph.D.)?

According to the questions above, the teachers gave full information about their personalities and teaching experiences.

5. Do you come across difficulties while teaching reading?

The aim of this question was to understand the difficulties of teachers in teaching reading. Almost all the teachers questioned face difficulties while teaching reading. They complained as follows:

- mother language interference,
- lack of reading practice,
- no desire to read;
- lack of interest and motivation,
- teachers' more attention to teaching grammar, vocabulary than reading

- pupils' irresponsibility,
- pupils are not patient while reading exercises;

6. Where do you see severe problems of your students in reading?

Especially, they have informed about students' problems like slow reading speed, not understanding text passages fully.

Section 2: teaching reading techniques

7. Do you aware of modern trends in teaching reading?(Reading-writing relationship, Content-based reading, Task-based reading, Sustained-silent reading, Social reading)

The purpose of this question was to know the teachers' awareness of the modern trends and innovative teaching styles in education. It is known from the answers that nearly all the teachers are familiar with these trends and they use them during the lessons.

8. Do you use the trends during reading lessons? Which one?

According to the teachers' answers, almost all the teachers use Content-based reading and Task-based reading trends more than other trends during the reading lessons. One of the teachers says, "Content-based reading works well to encourage my students to read because reading passage contains interesting content. For example, it can be about culture, geography, history of English-speaking countries or any topic in which students are interested. I use task-based reading as well to improve students' reading skills such as skimming, reading for gist, for details, summarizing, etc." Besides, another respondent state, "Reading - writing relationship, I try to make use of this trend while teaching reading intending to do focus not just for reading but also writing. I get students to read a piece of text and understand it and do rewriting on what they understand from it."

9. If students read a text in order to write about it, they remember it well. Do you agree? And do you use this method in your lessons?

Most teachers already use this method during the lessons. One of the young teachers replay as follows: "Sure! If students see the reading text as a source for their writing, they automatically try to remember it "word to word" mode". Also, one of the teachers who never use this method in the lesson support this idea, writing as following: "Absolutely agree. But I have never applied this method. Maybe in future, after some research about the principles of this method, I will implement it."

10. Do you encourage your students to read novels, short stories during the lesson? Do you think they like this type of reading

All the respondents gave positive answers. And their students are active during this type of reading. Nevertheless, they claim that this type of reading takes much time and they prefer students to read novels, short stories at home and they have discussions about them in the class in order to economize the time.

11. Students are fond of reading about social events and sharing their opinions on social websites like telegram, Instagram. Do you agree?

All the teachers state that their students are active in using social websites. Even if, some older teachers ask help from their students in order to how to use them, the students show them effortlessly.

12. If we lay the reading tasks on social websites (telegram, Instagram,...), students do the tasks eagerly. Do you agree? Why or why not?

Most teachers don't agree with this point. They don't prefer their students to use phones or other gadgets when doing their tasks. Few teachers agree with this method, supporting this opinion "I think

yes. One factor should be taken into consideration, one is spending their most time on social media because it is comfortable and engaging. So, this side of social media is used as a key to the problem that students stopped to read. However, they have no time for the traditional type of reading, give them that reading in the form of messaging in telegram or in Instagram, they will do, even unintentionally.” Similarly, another teacher points out “I agree with this viewpoint as the current generation is addicted to gadgets and social media. But it puts a huge responsibility on the teachers. What is more, not all of the students will complete this kind of task especially when it is an extended or long text/task. However, if it is given in small portions such as a telegram poll or Instagram quiz students will be more motivated. So, teachers should think about the form of delivery, i.e. how to organize reading via social networks.”

Conclusion and Recommendations

In this paper, we give emphasis to the role of modern trends in teaching reading. After analyzing the teachers’ questionnaires, we could come out with some recommendations concerning the need for integrating reading and writing, sometimes teaching reading in social media where students pass through different ideas. During these stages, the teacher’s role is important, directing them to the full meaning using reading comprehension strategies. Some teachers criticized their students as ‘lazy and irresponsible’ and whatever method they utilized to encourage them to do reading tasks did not work at all, while others insisted on the necessity to renew the curriculum and the practice of reading in their students. To improve the interest of students for reading, this is mainly due to instruction and the time devoted to reading. It is to say that both in-class and at-home readings help students become good readers.

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SOME DIFFICULTIES ON TEACHING WRITING FOR EFL STUDENTS

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Abstract:

Teaching writing has become difficult because of the challenges faced by the students in learning writing skills. Some of the challenges that are faced by the EFL students are lack of vocabulary, poor grammar, poor spelling, students' readiness and lack of exposure to books and reading materials.

Keywords: Writing skills, teaching and learning writing, challenges of writing.

Introduction

There are many consequences that could lead to major drawbacks in students' academic performance if they have a weak foundation in writing. Writing is not only vital in order to develop their academic performance, but also contributes to their social and emotional development. Moreover, in this competitive world, writing is also one of the skills that is necessary to excel. Their inability to write well, may affect their chances to secure a job in the future. Therefore, this issue needs to be tackled effectively. The challenges faced by the students have made it challenging for teachers to teach writing skills. The challenges that are faced by the teachers to teach writing skills are difficult to motivate their students, students of diverse levels, difficult materials and time constraints to teach the students. In order to improve a student's writing ability, more attention must be given by a teacher to teach writing such as giving guidance and feedback. Therefore, a teacher needs to be aware of the challenges faced by other English teachers in teaching writing skills and ESL students' challenges in learning to write.

Materials

Each student may face different challenges in learning writing. All the students are special and unique in their own ways. These challenges will somehow pull back the students from moving forward to produce a good piece of writing. The following paragraphs are about challenges faced by students in writing. Lack of vocabulary has caused the students to face challenges in acquiring writing skills. [1] Vocabulary is the fundamental element in constructing sentences which is the core of effective writing skills.[2] Students almost use spoken and written words every single day to communicate their ideas, beliefs and feelings with people around them. Good vocabulary repertoire can help students to speak or write to deliver their thoughts. Usage of electronic dictionary and more reading activities can help students with limited vocabulary.

Methods

Some EFL students are also having trouble with grammar. Grammar plays an important role in writing. Grammar provides information that helps the readers to understand its meaning. It is a structure that conveys the detailed meaning of the writer to the reader. Grammar also explains the forms and structure of words, called morphology and how they are arranged in sentences, called syntax. By having very limited knowledge in grammar, students will face anxiety to write sentences with correct grammar.

Results

Poor spelling is another cause of anxiety for students in learning writing skill. [3] Having good ability in spelling will lead to positive learning of writing skill. If the students are struggling with spellings, it will hold them back to move forward. The students have the habit to spell according to their pronunciation and this will lead to wrong spelling. [4] The students will either add or leave letters of the words. Last but not the least, lack of motivation is another challenge faced by the students. If the students are not motivated, they might not be interested to proceed with their learning process. Motivation is important in improving students' learning results.[5] Teachers could motivate the students by rewarding them with simple motivational phrases by saying "Good job!", "Good try!", "Keep it up" etc. Positive reward will make the students go further in their learning process. Teaching has always been the challenging part for teachers. Teaching English at primary level is naturally much more different from teaching in other levels of students such as secondary and tertiary levels. The challenge will somehow make the teachers' teaching ineffective. The following are the challenges faced by teachers. Nowadays, teachers are having a hard time in motivating the students. The younger generation has the perception that they can do whatever they please since much freedom has been given to them by their parents. When students choose to feel reluctant in learning, it is a sign of lack of motivation. [6]

Discussion

Having different levels of students in the classroom is another challenge faced by teachers to teach writing. In many elementary classrooms, students from different levels are placed in the same classroom. Different levels of students will result to difficulty to teachers in order to cater all of their levels simultaneously. [9] Different levels of writing ability will require the teachers to use different approaches. As a result, the teachers feel difficult to plan their lessons and prepare appropriate activities for the students. [7] Lack of students' interest is another challenge. Developing writing skills is always challenging, however, it is always an interesting task. Especially when it comes to writing, some students zone out. Students feel lack of interest in writing because they need to know many aspects in order to produce a good piece of work. The students need to know punctuations, grammar, vocabulary, spelling and sentence structure in order to write a good piece of writing.

Conclusion

As writing has been becoming the most challenging task among students and it takes lots of time to learn, I personally believe we can overcome this obstacles with working hard on our weak points. By understanding both the students' and teachers' challenges in learning and teaching writing skills, the teachers could choose the best possible approach to teach writing skills by giving feedback and guidance.

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MODERN APPROACHES AND INNOVATIONS IN STUDYING THE TOPIC OF ABDULLA ORIPOV'S POETRY

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Abstract:

The article contains information about modern approaches and innovations in the study of the subject "Poetry of Abdulla Oripov".

Keywords: Abdulla Oripov, Uzbek literature, innovative technologies, Uzbek classical music, modern approaches.

"Undoubtedly, confidence in our own strength and capabilities unites us on the noble goal of creating the foundations of the Third Renaissance, making us stronger and stronger. These aspirations are turning into great practical works, and the great people's movement is expanding more and more. Being in such a powerful line is a great happiness, a great honor."

One of those who stand in such a great position and serve as an example to others are teachers of mother tongue and literature, who have the proud title of teacher. They have a very important responsibility. First of all, it is his main task to get the brain of every writer and his work that is passed during the course of the lesson.

Uzbek literature is rich in excellent artistry with talented artists and spiritually mature individuals. The exemplary life and work of Abdulla Oripov, such a great national poet, state and public figure, Hero of Uzbekistan, the poetic monuments glorifying his destiny still attract the attention of readers.

By studying the instructive life of the poet, to develop the feelings of patriotism, philanthropy, philanthropy, independence, to protect mother nature, to develop independent thinking, expressive reading activities, and thereby to develop knowledge, skills and abilities. The main goal is to create *nikma*.

If the teacher learns information and innovative technologies correctly and applies them in practice, it is natural to have positive results. Currently, modern methods of teaching are widely used in the educational process. Application of modern teaching methods leads to high efficiency. When choosing educational methods, it is appropriate to choose based on the didactic task of each lesson.

Educational activity on the topic "Abdulla Oripov's life and work" includes "Material presentation", "Expressive reading", "Two-part diary", "Basket of ideas, concepts and names", "Role-playing game" or The main principle of achieving the goal is the "stage show" method, literary-musical composition views and teaching tools: projector, computer, slides, internet system, video projector.

"Material presentation" method

During the lesson, each small group presents prepared scientific and artistic information about the poet's work based on the previously assigned task. This method is one of the most tested and effective methods of the new pedagogical technology, which serves students' creativity and independent work ability, and teaches students to think independently.

Before starting the topic, students should study the work of Abdulla Oripov, memorize examples of his work, organize stage performances, find and perform songs composed to his poems, watch videos of the poet's activities from the Internet, as well as finding photos is the main task.

In the course of the lesson, each group strives to fulfill the assigned task diligently. Their poems, which decorate the pages of our literature, are read expressively in harmony with the sounds of music: "Uzbekistan", "The wind of my country", "Reservoir", "Ayol", "My first love", as well as on the basis of these great monuments The fact that the students sang their own songs and performed a role-playing game called "Uzbekistan - My Motherland" is evidence of the formation of independent work skills in them.

"Video method", i.e. viewing method. It is based on the reception of information on more visual overhead projectors, projectors, film cameras, educational televisions, as well as computers that display information. It is extremely appropriate to use the proverb "It is better to see once than to hear a thousand times". Video images such as "Birth", "Loneliness", "How much do I love Uzbekistan?", "Far from lies", performed by the poet himself, performed by People's Artist of Uzbekistan Y.Usmonova the poet's song "Take Me Away" will be performed.

The "two-part diary" method. It is a method that develops written speech and allows to connect the concepts of the studied topic with personal experience. The purpose of studying it is to arouse interest in the subject being studied, to develop written speech. In this case, students are invited to read a text prepared in advance. After making sure that everyone is familiar with the text, they are asked to divide the notebook into two with a vertical line. On the left side, the author is told to write what he likes or doesn't like about his ideas and opinions.

On the right side, the reader writes his own explanation of this idea, that is, he summarizes his understanding of the read text.

In the course of the lesson, the thoughts of the "Two-part diary" method given to the analysis of the poem "The wind of my country" will instill in the heart of the reader that the lyrical hero of the poet's poetry is a person who keeps pace with the times, is a patriot, and a creative person. The theme and idea of the poem are given in the 1st part of the diary, and a collection of poetic fragments or thoughts that reveal it in the 2nd part.

"Basket of ideas, concepts and names" method. During the lesson, the teacher activates the knowledge and experience of the students on the subject. By drawing a picture of a basket on the blackboard, students are invited to express their knowledge and understanding on the subject, and write down their thoughts on the basket. After that, the main concepts on the topic are told and compared with the information in the basket. Also, each group can perform this method with its members.

In particular, the poem "Listening to Munojot" was created under the influence of the "Munojot" tune, which has an important place in the history of Uzbek classical music and is a reflection of the pain and state of the soul that brings sadness to the human soul. In the process of describing, the information about the poet's passing over high artistic passages, his mastery of the art of using words and artistic images is told by the groups and written in the basket. These answers are summarized by the teacher, and the student's knowledge is evaluated for the best ideas.

"Role-playing" method. It is a method that shows various conditions of the life situation by students. Role-playing games differ from business games in the absence of evaluation. At the same time, in the

"Role-playing" method, learners who perform roles in the scenario developed by the teacher independently decide what tasks should be performed in a given situation.

Role-playing games also form interpersonal skills in learners. The fact that they performed a role play based on the work "My First Love", which was sung as a monument of our poetry, is a proof of the formation of independent work skills in them.

At the end of the lesson, students are given homework to find rare information about the poet's instructive life and learn its contents. Students' knowledge is evaluated based on their activity in the course of the lesson based on a five-point system.

Thus, students will acquire the following knowledge and skills in the process of mastering this subject:

- learn the essence of modern approaches and innovative technology and master their implementation;
- understands modern approaches, types of innovation, their place and importance in the educational process in the study of mother tongue and literature;
- modern approaches will learn the ways of using educational technologies in the educational process and the tasks of the teacher in this process.

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HISTORY OF ROBOTICS

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Annotation

This article contains information about the science of robotics, the history of robotics, information about the main classes of robotics.

Keywords: robotics, classroom, application, hybrid, technology, autonomous, experimental.

Robotics (Czech.- forced labor + ancient Greek: τέχνη — art;English: robotics) is a combined branch of Mechanical, Electrical and electronic engineering and computer science that deals with the construction, operation and use of robots, as well as their control, sensing and data processing.

Robotics is a science that, in addition to robots, studies the development and ways of using the latest technical integration of automated technical systems and production processes. Automated machines, in other words, robots can work instead of people in assembly processes in hazardous areas or factories. Robots can be very similar in appearance, behavior and perception to humans. Scientists are currently trying to make human-shaped robots look as human as possible.

Autonomous robots have been thought of since ancient times, but research in this regard began until the twentieth century. Since the fairytale period, robots have been predicted to one day perform human work, imitating human behavior. Today robotics is a rapidly developing field. As technology develops rapidly, robotics is also developing rapidly because Robotics is closely related to technology. With the development of technology, research and development are changing and developing, as a result of which the field of application of robots is also growing. Today robots are used in homes, businesses and the military field. Many robots are used in situations that cause direct damage to humans, such as neutralizing mines and bombs.

Although Robotics does not research and develop any robots, these robots must obey Isaac Asimov's three laws. He outlined the laws in the story "Horovod", which he wrote in 1942. These laws are written with the following opinion:

- 1.No robot can harm a person or prevent damage through inaction.
- 2.Without breaking the first law, the robot must obey all human commands.
- 3.If it does not contradict the first and Second Laws, the robot must ensure its own safety.

In the same Urin, we found it permissible to delve into the history of robotics. In 1942, the science fiction writer Isaac Asimov invented three laws of robotics. In 1948, Norbert Wiener developed the principles of cybernetics, which formed the basis of experimental robotics. Fully autonomous robots appeared only in the second half of the XX century. The first digitally controlled programmable robot was Unimate. It is designed to take and assemble the robot's hot iron parts from the smelting machine. Today, commercial and industrial robots are widespread. These robots do the job cheaper, more compact, and more efficiently than humans. Some of the jobs of robots used in this area are dirty, dangerous and boring for humans. Robots are widely used for assembly, assembly, delivery, land and space exploration, medical surgery, equipment, laboratory research and safety.

While there is debate about what exactly machines can be called robots, it is argued that a conventional robot must have the following qualities:

- Not natural, that is, made by a conscious being.
- Can observe the environment (does not have to observe through sight; another species can also have intuition).
- Can interact with the environment in an interactive way.
- Somehow smart, that is, able to make (independent or pre-programmed) decisions.
- Can program.
- Can move with rotation or parallel displacement axes.
- Able to perform agile manipulations.

In the melody, information is provided on the button of the main classes of robots .Today there are many types of robots that are used in different ways in different environments, although the purpose of Use and appearance are different, when it comes to structure, they all have three common areas:

1.Each robot consists of a mechanical base — a device, a frame. The type of frame varies depending on the purpose. For example, crawler tractors can be used if the robot moves on clay and sand.

Mechanically, the inventor's solution to a separate problem depends on the environment of the place where the robot moves. The Shape of the robot is directly related to its function.

2.Each robot consists of electrical components. These parts fully control robotic systems. For example, if we take a robot walking along chains, it will take strength to move these chains. This power comes as electricity, passes through the wires and is stored in the battery .

Gas-powered machines also require electricity for the gas utilization process. Therefore, cars such as gasoline cars have a battery. The electrical system is used to move the robot (engine), measure (electrical signals to determine the amount of heat, sound, location and energy) and for general use (the robot must send some energy to its motors and sensors). general basic operations).

All robots require some computer code. The same algorithm shows how the robot works. The person who writes the code writes how and when the robot decides and acts within the program. A robot moving along the same chain, thanks to its mechanical design and construction, makes mud perfect and does not move without a computer program, even if it receives the required amount of energy from its battery through wires; because the program tells the robot when and where to move. The program creates the basic value of the robot. If the mechanical and electrical parts of the robot are perfectly finished, but the written application is bad, the robot works in two ways, even if it does, it moves and works irregularly. There are three main types of algorithms: remote control, artificial intelligence, and hybrid. Remotely controlled robots have a number of commands. It executes commands only after receiving a signal from the remote control. In general, a person controls a robot located at a distance through the same device. Robots using artificial intelligence make their own decisions depending on the environment. In the robotic system, various reactions to environmental factors and objects are recorded. Artificial intelligence takes into account those reactions and affects environmental factors. Basically, artificial intelligence should be similar or similar to human thinking. And the hybrid is a combination of remote control and artificial intelligence.

In the summary urn, it should be said that we can also call a robot a machine that partially or fully performs the function of a person in conditions of danger to human life (strong radiation, high temperatures, etc.), in objects that are difficult for a person to navigate (under water, in space).

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**THE ISSUE OF WOMEN'S RIGHTS AND THEIR ROLE IN SOCIETY IN WORLD
LITERATURE**

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Annotation

This article talks about women's rights and their place in society, gender equality in world literature. The study of the image of a woman and her delicate psyche in world and Uzbek literary studies and related fields, as well as the opinions and discoveries given in the research works conducted in this regard, were discussed. In the works of modern Uzbek writers Zulfia Kuroilboy, Risolat Haydarova and Jamila Ergasheva, the image of a woman and her psyche are analyzed.

Keywords: World, literary studies, woman, image, psyche, plot, gender equality.

Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada jahon adabiyotida ayollar huquqlari va ularning jamiyatdagi o'рни, gender tenglik masalasi xususida so'z yuritiladi. Dunyo va o'zbek adabiyotshunosligi hamda unga aloqador sohalarda ayol obrazi va uning nozik ruhiyatini o'rganilganligi va bu borada olib borilgan tadqiqot ishlarida berilgan fikr-mulohazalar, kashfiyotlar haqida to'xtalib o'tilgan. Shuningdek, zamonaviy o'zbek adibalari Zulfiya Qurolboy qizi, Risolat Haydarova va Jamila Ergasheva asarlarida ayol obrazi, ruhiyati tasviri tahlilga tortilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Dunyo, adabiyotshunoslik, ayol, obraz, ruhiyat, syujet, gender tenglik.

When it comes to the issue of women's rights and their role in society in world literature, the rise of the topic of gender equality is also related to the protection of women's rights by intellectuals of society against the violation of women's rights for many years. In 1955, the American scientist John Maney introduced the term "gender" to science for the first time. After a while, this term became widespread. The main reason for this is that this concept was popularized by the supporters of feminism. The concept of "feminism" first appeared in the West. In the last 20th century, the Western woman was imagined only as a person who does household chores. This is also explained by the lack of protection of women's rights and their inactive participation in society. Not being able to get used to such a situation created the conditions for the emergence of feminism. Writers accept literature as a transparent mirror of society, and only works with an objective approach are sure of the longevity of a work of art. As an eternal theme of literature, women have a unique expression in the works of not only writers, but also writers, and such an approach in literary studies is called feminist criticism. Feminist criticism formally entered literary studies in the 1960s. But before this process, there were many centuries of works written about women's rights and their place in society, and writers who fought for women's freedom, and they laid the foundations of feminist criticism in the literal sense. In fact, the issue of equal rights of women and men has been the cause of intense debate since ancient

times. The sophist Antiphon, who lived in the 5th century BC, was the first to put forward the idea that all people were created equal by nature in his works. In his opinion, nature creates everyone equal: both men and women, but the laws that make people unequal are the result of mutual agreement between people (Anthology of human philosophy, 1969, 322). Philosophers recognized in their theories that men and women have equal rights. That is, Pythagoras, a great thinker and scientist, puts forward his opinion about equal rights of men and women in his philosophical views. Pythagoras' colleagues continued this idea. They emphasize that human life should be built on the basis of justice and a certain limit, that is, knowing and feeling one's place (Nikolaev N., 2017, 423). The idea of this content was developed by the Greek thinker Socrates in his philosophical teaching about the objective moral nature of laws. In particular, while recognizing the equality of human natural rights, he puts forward the idea that the polis should obey only logically correct and fair laws, and only in this case human freedom can be ensured. (Cassidy F.,1988, p.181).

In society, as soon as a girl child is born, she is at her father's will, she is involved in hard work even she is married before she reaches adulthood, and no one is interested in her wishes, which has led to the spiritual oppression of the representatives of this gender in life. This process caused the feeling of slavery and submissiveness in the female psyche to increase. As a result, it becomes clear that women look down on themselves again, and their feelings of self-love and respect begin to decline. Even in ancient India, a woman did not have any rights except to marry and give birth to children. He was considered to have an impure principle, weak character, and bad morals. Even in ancient Greece, women did not have any rights and freedoms. All their lives, they were forced to obey the man's orders and fulfill his wishes. A woman is at the disposal of a man for life, and life and death are entrusted to that man. That man offered his desire as a husband to the woman he wanted and took her under his control by force. All property was at the disposal of the man. Without his consent, a woman could not have any rights. Land is considered an absolute right in divorce proceedings. Only in some cases, the woman was able to express her desire for divorce. In such cases, unfair insults were poured on the woman (Orazaliyeva G.B., 2006, p. 147).

In ancient China, a woman was not considered a person, or even given a name. Women were called by number and treated accordingly. While boys were considered acceptable, girls were looked down upon. If a girl child was born in Chinese families, it was not considered a child for them. In China, girls were traded like commodities and sold at auctions, and as a result, whoever paid the highest price got the girl. They could not sit and eat with men, but they would fulfill all their wishes without hesitation. Women were disinherited when they got married. In the pre-Islamic period, women did not have any place or dignity among the people of the Arabian Peninsula. This situation started with the birth of a child. When a boy was born in the family, they rejoiced and were happy, but when a girl was born, mourning reigned in the family and they wanted to get rid of the child as soon as possible (Azimov A., 1991, p. 150).

In world literature, the fate of women in the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan is a main issue that is being studied with interest and is causing critical debate. Writers, such as Harriet Logan, Sunita Mehta, Nilufar Pazira, Deborah Rodriguez, Rosemary Skein, Marie Smith, and Zoya wrote on the topic of Afghan women. So, the place of women in society is related to the eternal themes of literature, which Khalid Hosseini has written with great skill in the novel "A Thousand Suns" (Hosseini Kh., 2007).

384). This work is a feminism-oriented novel published in 2007, which made Husayni's position recognized as a writer.

The fate of Maryam and Layla is seen as the main image of the plot of the work. The desire to write a work on the theme of Afghan women as a literary idea, which formed many years ago, arose when the author met beggar women in old clothes wrapped in chadors on the street corners with four to five or even six children each during his visit to Kabul in 2003. The writer is deeply moved by the situation of women in Afghanistan, and listening to their heartbreaking life stories, he admits that they have a stronger spirit, will and endurance than men. In the characters of Maryam and Aziza in the work, Hosseini describes the unhappy childhood of those who started their lives with the same "corrupt" status, while Maryam gives Aziza the happiness that she did not achieve, which also believes that bright days will come in Afghanistan, where children with the right to childhood will grow up. Khaled Hosseini's views on the fate of women in Afghanistan at all ages are illuminated through a feminist perspective in the novel "A Thousand Suns". The female characters representing three generations, Aziza - a young girl, Laila - a middle-aged woman, and Maryam - an older woman, describe the unhealthy environment prevailing in all the young people of Afghanistan. While looking forward to the future, the writer is saddened by the degrading treatment of women and calls on everyone to treat women with respect and dignity.

The sufferings of Pakistani women caused by the Taliban are described in the autobiographical novel of the Nobel laureate Malala Yousafzai entitled "I am Malala" (Yousafzai M., 2013. 288) by the criteria of impressiveness and truthfulness of literature. Every reader is especially shocked by the Taliban's nightly raids into Afghan homes, raping and killing women and girls. In such a difficult situation, every person who considers himself a patriot is forced to illegally cross the borders of foreign countries in order to save the honor of his daughter and wife, his pride, peace and well-being of his family. Most of them do not spend the night in the camps they meet on the roads. It turned out that the Taliban invaded such camps and carried out their nefarious intentions. The main reason for the writer's work, which shakes the whole world, innocent bloodshed and endless wars that serve the interests of some small groups, is the abandonment of education. They conclude that the only solution is to return to education. Therefore, he concludes that only the development trend will occur among the representatives of the generation where education and upbringing are put first.

Today, all over the world, the attention to women, the improvement of their legal, cultural and household standard of living, and the efforts aimed at establishing the education of girls in schools are developing at a rapid pace. It can be concluded from many cited examples that the laws that discriminated, humiliated and violated the pride of women, which arose in ancient times, continued for centuries, and even today in some countries, these norms is preserved. It is worth noting that a woman who is able to observe and reason may be able to give proper, reasonable and fair upbringing to her children. Literature can legitimately raise such problems and help to find a solution.

In Uzbek literature, the issue of women's rights has been in the center of attention for many years. The rise of the problem of the image of a woman in the novels of female writers in Uzbek literature: Zulfiya Kuroilboy qizi, Risolat Haydarova, Jamila Ergasheva became an indelible mental phenomenon. The image of a woman in literary novels is of great importance due to its vivid reflection of life, the fact of life, its naturalness and believability. One literary problem unites all three writers. They are completely different from other prose in that they bring the theme of female power to the fore. This

situation can be seen in their common views on suffering and pleasure, and in their literary and aesthetic heroes.

In this regard, Zulfia Kuroloy's works such as "Hard Life Paths", "Whirlwind of Difficulties", "A prisoner of dreams", Risolat Haydarova's "Javzo", Jamila Erasheva's "Woman on the Hill" were published as an expression of a woman's psyche and her feelings. Female artists who entered Uzbek literature also created images that show the character traits of a new woman in their works. In their novels and short stories, regardless of their creative direction, they embodied the new features of the female character that arose as a result of the issue of gender equality.

The novel "Hard Life Paths" written by Zulfia Kuroloy, a well-known Uzbek writer and author, describes the artistic interpretation of a woman's heart, desires, happiness, dreams, and their role in society and family. In fact, it is about the determination, hard work, family, love for children and the secrets of a woman's heart. Professor Umarali Normatov writes: "...Zulfia's series of stories, which were once despised by critics, and free from sociality that was not appreciated, created pure "songs of whims" through literary experiments, ... in terms of its artistic and spiritual impact, they are not inferior to mature works of a purely social direction" (Normatov U., 2010, web page). The heroes of the work interpret the events of life in a new way and promote concepts such as humanity, hard work, generosity, and honesty, which are typical in the views of people today.

Jamila Ergasheva is also a writer who is known for her stories, which are aimed at showing the modern man and his unique spiritual world in the image of interesting and extremely moving events. Writer's four short stories with a sharp plot, such as "Ajdarko'l" ("Ajdarkol), "Intiqom" ("Revenge"), "Tanazzul" ("Recession"), and "Yopiq derazalar" (Closed windows"), which capture the reader's attention, have been published. Again, the novel "Woman on the Hill" (screenplay "Fitna" (Conspiracy) entered the reader's world. In her works, the traces of goodness and evil in the human psyche and fate are reflected in sharp contrasts.

Risolat Haydarova's work "Javzo" is also an artistic interpretation of the psyche of the female image created in Uzbek novels and the analysis of the problem of poetic perfection of this image has been proven to be a special phenomenon in Uzbek prose. The landscape in "Javzo" is one of the important tools that reveal the idea of the work and the psyche of the characters in today's Uzbek prose. In the work, colorful female characters were created, such as Husnibonu, Gulnurbegim, Oğilbibi, and Opoqbegim, whose destinies were not similar to each other. The image of women in the work "Javzo" is one of the important factors that move the reality of any artistic work. In our opinion, the concept of the harmony of national values with the image of a woman in the works of the writer and the interpretation of the hero's psyche is also a part of this aesthetic category. In the work "Javza" there are active and colorful female characters such as Karakozbegim, Moghul Khanim, Khan Ayim, Khadichabegim, Opoqbegim, Ulugbibi, Gulnurbegim, Ganjina, Ogilbibi. By drawing their external portrait, the writer tries to enter their inner spiritual world, to describe the scenes of the female psyche. The character's mental state is revealed through images such as the face, eyes, height, complexion, clothing, and demeanor characteristic of the external portrait of the hero. Using external portrait details, such as "dark black hair", "uncurled eyebrows", "clear faces", in fact, these signs are an expression of positive feelings such as sophistication, beauty, and love. It can be said that in other historical works "Javzo" the depiction of the image and spirit of Roman women was not reflected in such a wide scope. There are beautiful lines about the dreams, sorrows, thoughts,

sufferings, anger and sorrows of the female race. Also, during the period of Timurids and Shaybani Khans, the lifestyle of women, their rights, their role in the family and society is skillfully written.

In short, a woman is the happiness and luck of the family, the successor of the next generation. It is true that the future of a country with happy women is bright. In the works of our writers Zulfiya Kuroloy, Risolat Haydarova, and Jamila Ergasheva, the lifestyle, dreams, goals, mentality, and aspirations of today's women are reflected. In each of her works, she skillfully expressed her pain, suffering, and joy. It seems that you cannot look indifferently at the reality that is happening around you and in your destiny. This is a great achievement of our talented writers. Promotion of these works, especially among young readers, becoming a discussion among them, and studying them will be an important source for understanding the psyche of women and their place in society.

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**THE FORMATION OF UZBEK NATIONAL VALUES AND THE
PROCESSES OF ITS RISE TO A NEW LEVEL IN SOCIETY**

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Annotation : This article provides detailed information about the transformational processes in the hierarchy of values and the promotion of values to a new level, as well as their specific characteristics. Opinions were also expressed about the place of Uzbek national values in the society and the factors affecting it.

Keywords: values, tradition, tradition, transformation, social life

Man always strives for perfection. As a result of this, he creates, develops, and further improves things that are very necessary for him. These created things are evaluated according to the fact that they serve to make the everyday life of mankind more prosperous, to improve the way of thinking, and to harmonize individual interests with the interests of society and the state. Due to such evaluation, the phenomenon that occurred can be recognized as a value. Of course, this is not a scientific definition of the phenomenon of value. However, value, in fact, as a product of a person's conscious activity, is a phenomenon that has a position that determines the extent to which it benefits mankind and makes his life easier. We often understand value as the value of a thing or event.

There is certainly some truth in this idea. However, it is necessary to recognize the event as value, which reflects its spiritual and cultural value, and not its material aspect in the literal sense of the word. To be more precise, true value is a phenomenon that serves the development of a person and society, the development of humanity. Value acquires its true form only when it shows the social importance of a person, when it helps to ensure the social and moral stability of society. In fact, today the world, its ideological landscape, moral way of thinking is changing at a very high speed and intensity. In the present conditions, the globalization processes of the world and the complexity of social institutions are changing the traditional values and moral criteria that have been formed for thousands of years. Under the influence of modern mass media and new information and communication technologies, traditional values in society are gradually being replaced by priorities based on individualism and personal freedom, pragmatism, commercial success, and cultural norms. As a result, "technocratic culture" is gaining strength in Uzbekistan today, as it is in the whole world.

Today Ignoring this factor in our spiritual-educational, educational-propaganda work, not "regulating" it can have certain negative consequences. We did not quote the word regulation for nothing. The fact is that now nobody in the world, in Uzbekistan, is happening in the world of information technologies not against events. Computer technologies, the Internet system have become an integral part of our social and cultural life. The priority level of technical principles is getting stronger. As a result, the scope of our youth's understanding of the world, the condition of meeting the need to increase one's knowledge potential is getting worse.

At the same time, as has been emphasized many times, we can see that such a situation is becoming more and more negative. So what does it look like? First of all, young people are becoming enslaved and dependent on the Internet system, their unique technocratic culture - recognizing only technical means, adapting to them without realizing it, ultimately creating dependence on the Internet and social networks. It is known that values are people's ability to accept certain situations, facts, norms in social existence from a certain point of view and to act in different life situations in accordance with this vision, that is, a comprehensive study of the population's system of perceptions of values is a way to comprehensively understand the essence of the socio-political reality of the current masses. opens.

As mentioned above, in the hierarchy of Uzbek national values, the issue of morality always occupies one of the most important places. At the same time, moral virtues themselves are a very complex system. Sometimes, in this system, protecting the motherland is recognized as a sacred feeling, and in some cases, mercy, gentleness, and in some cases, fairness, showing fortitude, etc., have an important place. In the hierarchy of values, as well as in the issue of a person's becoming worthy of society, the issue of reforms in his thinking has a special place.

Thinking is an important way to analyze the current situation and make unbiased conclusions about it. If a person, especially our youth, cannot analyze the events happening in the society and draw correct conclusions from them, this will have a negative effect on his ideas about the society. At the same time, there are factors that prevent some of our young people from realizing the novelty in their consciousness and thinking, which cannot be ignored. If we take a broader approach to the issue, we want to build a new society, New Uzbekistan. However, New Uzbekistan cannot be built with old thinking. As the great Allama Mahmud al-Zamakhshari said: "It is good to enter into good deeds earnestly, to give up the thought that I will do them later, and not to act hastily, but with thought and understanding.

"The transformation of the country into a democratic, open, civil society, the obedience of citizens to the constitution and existing legislation, and the degree of development of political culture among people determine the fate of national values.

Here, democratic values - civil society, openness of society, ideological values such as diversity, protection of human rights, personal freedom in the literal sense, and the rule of law undoubtedly have a worthy place in the development of national values. In the transition period, when the society enters a new stage of its development, the process of re-evaluation of national values also requires social activity of citizens. Social activity is a citizen's personal aspirations, life goals, efforts to make maximum use of one's capabilities in order to reach the level of maturity that should be achieved in the future.

Also, social activity is the ability of a person to harmonize his personal interests with the interests of the society, nation, and the Motherland in order to achieve his goal and to ensure its proportionality. Today, the society itself is interested in the social activity of citizens. Therefore, it was not for nothing that the head of the country expressed the following thoughts about it: "Among the society, there are many people who strive for innovation, people who deeply feel that reforms are a vital necessity and become conscious and active participants of changes. However, conservatives who are deeply rooted in the old and do not want anything new will remain. Such people do not openly oppose reforms and reforms. Maybe they will try to discredit him from inside or outside. There are several reasons why spirituality and enlightenment are becoming one of the most priority areas in today's hierarchy of Uzbek national values.

First, society recognizes that there are certain problems and shortcomings in the field of spirituality, enlightenment, and education. Secondly, the society of Uzbekistan believes that it is possible to solve problems in all areas of our country through spirituality and enlightenment, and its strong influence. Thirdly, there is a social sentiment related to the fact that our people are worried about the erosion of values that is happening in the world, and that it can have a negative impact on the development of our country. Such answers can be positively evaluated from the point of view of national development, thrift, spending earned material wealth in the way of human capital. Indeed, the issues of lavish weddings and excessive extravagance, which were once criticized by modern thinkers, have not yet been resolved.

At the same time, as we noted, the above answers may seem to reassure the community a little. At the same time, the development of our country into an open, democratic, social state and civil society is increasing the role of democratic values. In the hierarchy of values, factors such as social

activity, attention to the rule of law, openness, and healthy faith occupy a wider place among society members, indicating that Uzbekistan has entered a new era in its development.

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LINGUISTIC APPROACH TO THE DESCRIPTION OF LEXICAL UNITS EXPRESSING HUMAN SPIRITUAL STATE IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract

One of the top priorities in world linguistics is the linguistic approach to the study of linguistic units with national and cultural content. Another is the analysis of the national spirit of peoples reflected in world languages and the identification of ethno cultural features of linguistic expression in human relations. It should be mentioned that the main emphasis is on the psycholinguistic, linguocognitive, lingvoculturological, and sociolinguistic nature of language as well as how it functions in the lives of various peoples.

Keywords: ethno cultural features, lexical, phraseological, paremio logical and textual, linguistic essence, national-cultural features of the linguo cultural content of the concepts of the inner world of man.

Introduction

Priorities include the identification of ethno cultural elements of linguistic expression in human connections, analysis of the national spirit of peoples reflected in world languages, and linguistic approach to the study of linguistic units of national and cultural significance in world linguistics. It should be highlighted that the main emphasis is on the functional aspects of language, including its psycholinguistic, linguocognitive, lingvoculturological, and sociolinguistic aspects, in the lives of various peoples.

The scientific importance of the research findings is the resolution of conceptual and linguistic concept problems, and the potential application of the findings using the methods chosen for the scientific interpretation of linguistic material to further develop in other languages, linguocultural, and cognitive is explained by the fact that its ethical-semantic aspects have been thoroughly studied based on non-sister language materials.

The research has practical value in that it has led to the development of textbooks and manuals on lexicology, phraseology, sociolinguistics, translation theory and practice in higher education, comparison of the English and Uzbek languages, teaching specialized courses in linguocultural studies, text analysis, dissertations, master's theses, and the fact that the English and Uzbek languages can help future specialists to advance their theoretical and practical knowledge.

The meaning of the concept of "family" in the development of language and culture is defined, and the content of the conceptual sphere of relations in English and Uzbek is taken into consideration.

Linguistic interpretations of the concept of linguocultural features of human concepts in English and Uzbek are also discussed.

Language is a part of human nature and is essential for the growth of a person's cognitive abilities and the establishment of their worldview. Language's social and human nature is that it establishes the parameters for all cultural existence. Research should be done in a variety of approaches because the ratio of events in the "ethnos-culture-language" triangle is diverse and distinguished by the interdependence of the relationships expressed.

Language's social and human nature is that it establishes the parameters for all cultural existence. Research should be done in a variety of approaches because the ratio of events in the "ethnos-culture-language" triangle is diverse and distinguished by the interdependence of the relationships expressed. The research should first concentrate on the types and forms of speech actions that are unique to a given civilization, before concentrating on the study of their nature and purposes.

As it represents knowledge of the language, society, and culture, a concept is a unit in the fields of linguistics and culture in modern linguistics. Language-based concepts portray a culture and influence how people perceive the outside world. A unit of operational content, a unit of structured knowledge, or a quantum, is conceptual thinking. Concepts are ideal, impersonal units of meaning that one utilizes when thinking. In the form of specific units, or "quanta," they represent the information included in the learned knowledge, experience, and outcomes of human perception of real existence.

Method and Analysis

The notions of the inner world of man in the English and Uzbek languages are very different, as are the linguistic and cultural elements of the family roles. Consider how a bride in an Uzbek family compares to a daughter-in-law or bride in an English household. There are numerous rituals and traditions connected to the idea of the bride (bride greetings, the bride saw), and while many phrases with the word "bride" in them have long been used to refer to the bride's family obligations, only one logical phrase with the meaning "country" rather than "bride" can be found in English: "the bride of the sea"—Venice.

Family relationships between family members and relatives are another aspect of how the inner world of man is conceptualized in English and Uzbek from a language and cultural perspective. Examples of Uzbek phrases without English equivalents include *kuda-anda*, *kudalik*, *kuda-andachilik*, and others.

N.N. Boldirev contends that a notion in language can be expressed through a single word or phrase, a phrase logical unit, a sentence, or an entire text. The scientist divides the notion into many parts depending on the content and level of abstraction: a strong emotional image, imagination, scheme, concept, prototype, propositional structure, frame, script (script), gestalt, etc.

With the meanings of many words that are visual and external in character, a distinct emotional image is presented. Rethinking metaphorically: May and December, an elderly husband and a youthful wife. The father's child is like the father and is the father's own, which is a very distinct emotional image.

The mental image must include both an external and a set of emotional characters, unlike a clear emotional image. The newly coined Uzbek word "bride" not only conjures up images of young brides but also conveys traits like politeness, willingness for service, shyness, kindness, and other traits unique to young brides. It should be mentioned that only the Uzbek cultural framework allows for the

realization of this image. Check out this thinking phrase that was developed using the English phraseology "zoo Daddy" (a divorced father who has the right to meet his children on the weekends). The father in this portrait divorced his mother on the weekends. Changing metaphors: May and December are a young husband and a young wife. One specific emotional picture that comes to me is the father's child, who is like the father and is the father's own. The mental image must have a set of emotional characteristics in addition to an exterior one, unlike a clear emotional image. In addition to conjuring up a picture of a young bride, the newly popularized Uzbek word "bride" also conveys traits like as politeness, willingness for service, shyness, kindness, and other traits particular to young brides. It should be emphasized that this representation exclusively exists in Uzbek culture.

Let's look at the thinking phrase based on the English phraseology "zoo Daddy" (a divorced parent who is entitled to weekend visits with his children). The father in this portrait divorced his mother on the weekends. She takes her kids on strolls to the zoo, circus, and other locations.

As a result, both English and Uzbek cultures share linguistic and cultural characteristics of the conceptions of the inner world of man that are beneficial in the emotional arena. As a result, both English and Uzbek cultures have good emotional aspects to their respective linguistic and cultural representations of the inner world of man. The inner world of a man is thought to have good linguistic and cultural characteristics in both English and Uzbek. In Uzbek culture, these qualities include commitment and obligation, and in English society, they include love and affection. The terms "single mother," "illegal marriage," "illegal husband and wife," and "same-sex marriage" are among the new conceptions and models of family connections that have arisen in English but are not acceptable to Uzbek national culture. plus others.

Conclusion

The mental wholeness of the impression of the world landscape, which encompasses both language and cultural knowledge, imagination, and values, is the linguistic and cultural feature of the conceptions of the inner world of man in English and Uzbek. This concept's content is realized through the use of language. The language units in English and Uzbek reflect all issues, knowledge, attitudes, and values associated with the linguocultural characteristics of the notions of the inner world of man. As a result, this idea is founded on the lexical, phraseological, and textual levels of the language and can be realized in folklore discourses, folk songs, proverbs, and sayings that convey the knowledge of the populace. As a unit of the content of collective consciousness that is stored in the national memory of language owners in the form of linguistic expression, linguistic elements of the conceptions of the inner world of man in English and Uzbek are comprehended. A certain language community's national, cultural, social, psychological, youth, and everyday life experiences are directly tied to this idea. It possesses a number of advantageous, emotively assessing, and associative qualities. The multifaceted linguocultural aspects of the notions of the inner world of man in English and Uzbek relate to his outward and interior worlds and represent the respective languages' ethnic identities. The investigation led to the identification of linguistic and non-linguistic elements that affect the dynamics of development of language units that reflect family ties in English and Uzbek.

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THE STUDY OF THE TEACHINGS OF YAKUBI CHARKHI BY FOREIGN RESEARCHERS

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Annotation

In this article, information about the life and work of Yakubi Charkhi, as well as his place in the teachings of Sufism, is presented by mystics and scientists in different periods, and it is to justify his place in the history of philosophy that he is one of the roots of the Third Renaissance in New Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Yakubi Charkhi, Naqshbandiya, studies, treatises, philosophical analysis, Tafsir Yakubi Charkhi, series.

Yakubi Charkhi's scientific heritage has a great place in the continuation of the tradition of succession in Sufism philosophy. The fact that Yakubi Charkhi, one of the leaders of the Naqshbandi order, was a great Orif scholar is confirmed not only by the manuscripts collected by his students and children, but also by his treatises devoted to the research of various fields of science, especially the theoretical and practical problems of the Naqshbandi order.

Also, in foreign countries, in Germany, Turkey, Iran, Pakistan, Russia, Tajikistan, some researches on the life and scientific heritage of Yakubi Charkhi Azam have been carried out. These studies were used to one degree or another to illuminate the issues to be analyzed in the dissertation. But these studies were written from the perspective of the subjects and requirements of history, oriental studies, source studies, and they did not pay attention to the philosophical analysis of Ya'qubi Charkhi's mystical views.

Pakistani scientist Mohammad-Nazir Randja Yakubi was a fan of Charkhi's work. The scientist studied the works of the mystic "Sharhi Asma ul-husna", "Huroiyya", "Risolai abdoliya", "Risolai unsiya" and published the collection twice under the name "Rasoili Ya'qubi Charkhi". In the collection published in 2009, the researcher notes that he paid more attention to the treatises "Risolai abdoliya", "Risolai unsiya" and through these works he became a fan of mystic works. [1]

Iranian researcher Muhammad Amin Riyahi studied the Kubroviya and Naqshbandi sects and compared the "Tafsiri Ya'qubi Charkhi" of the mystic and the treatise "Mirsad al-Ibad" of the great representative of the Kubroviya sect, Najmuddin Razi. [2]

The life and scientific heritage of Yaqubi Charkhi have also been studied by Turkish scientists. Topbosh Osman Nuri "Sufism. From faith to charity"[3], he gave information about the concept of Sufism, its essence, sects, Naqshbandi teachings and its manifestations, and in the treatises of Yakubi Charkhi, he made a mystical analysis of the possibility of realizing God through faith, spiritual purity, and high moral qualities.

Turkish theologian Najdat Tosun "Golden people. In the book "The Golden Chain of the Naqshbandi Tariqa"[4], Yakubi Charkhi states that he is in the seventeenth generation of the "Zanjir al-Zahab", and mentions that he studied in the madrasas of Egypt, Herat and Bukhara, the social environment was bad during his stay in Herat, and he was in the house of Abdullah Ansari. For example, after the first

meeting of the mystic in Bukhara with Bahaiddin Naqshband, Dashti Kulakka gives information that he participated in the conversation of Maulana Tajiddin. According to the scientist, Yaqubi Charkhi saw in his dreams or visions that the Bukhara fortress was cracked, that light was radiating towards him from the holes in the walls of the fortress, that one end of the rays was at his head, and the other end was extended like a rope and connected to the Kaaba, that the knots on the threads of this light formed fruit trees at each node. , will see humans and creatures enjoying these fruits. After telling this dream to his teacher Bahaiddin Naqshband, he allowed Piri Yakubi Charkhi to guide the people.[5]

Hasan Kamil Yilmaz also published his "Golden Chain". The chain of succession of the sheikhs of the Naqshbandi sect" [6] gives detailed information that the full name of the mystic is Ya'qub ibn Usman ibn Mahmud ibn Muhammad ibn Mahmud al-Charkhi and that he was born in the family of a theologian in the village of Charkh near Ghazni, Khurasan (now a village in the Logar province of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan), and identified Yaqub Charkhi asserts that his position in the chain is in the eighteenth century after Muhammad Porso.

Hazini, a Turkish mystic, wrote a ten-verse poem about Yakubi Charkhi in his work "Javahirul-abror". In the poem, Bahaiddin Naqshband also writes about Charkhi's place in the Naqshbandi order, his death and his grave in Halgatu.[7]

Russian scientists have also conducted research on the scientific heritage of Yakubi Charkhi. Alexey Khismatullin dedicated to the life and scientific heritage of the mystic "Medieval drawing method. In the article entitled "In the example of the work of Yaqubi Charkhi" [8], he mentions that he studied theology in a village on the outskirts of Khurasan, and later on his travels in Herat, Egypt and Bukhara. Scholar Ya'qubi Charkhi mentions that he learned the dhikr of Khufiya from Piri Bahaiddin Naqshband in Bukhara and became a murid of Alauddin Attar. According to the researcher, the first copy of the work of the mystic "Risalai Abdoliya" was kept in Egypt until the century, and later Iranian and Pakistani scientists conducted research based on this source.

"Sufiism in Central Asia" in the international collection dedicated to the memory of Frittsa Mayer, Yaqubi Charkhi's work "Risolai abdaliyya" connects the origin of Khizr with Central Asia and provides information about his first kunya, Abul Abbas.[9] In particular, by analyzing the treatises of Khojagon-Naqshbandiya mystics, it was noted that along with the numerous works of Koshifi, Jami and Khoja Ahror, the treatises of Muhammad Porso and Yakubii Charkhi have a special place.

Alexander Knish in his book "Muslim mysticism" [10] spoke about the murids of Bahaiddin Naqshband, who was honored with the honor of being the son-in-law of Alauddin Attar (d. 802/1393), Khwaja Muhammad Porso (d. 882/1419) was the author of many works, He mentions that he created the literary heritage of the Naqshbandi order, and that Ya'qubi Charkhi (d. 851/1447) and Khoja Ubaydullah Ahror (d. 896/1490) played an important role in the spread of the order to the world.

Chechen scientist Eskarkhanov Gelani Lyomovich in his research entitled "Sufism in the North-Eastern Caucasus: emergence, ideology, practice" [11] showed that the teaching of Naqshbandi had a great influence on the development of socio-political and philosophical thinking in Central Asia, Iran, Turkey, India and Eastern Turkestan. , Muhammad Porso, Yaqubi Charkhi and Khoja Ahrori Vali's family, he emphasizes that it was widely spread as a result of the travels and migrations of his murids. Scientists from Tajikistan S. Makhmadullaev, Z. Nabotov, Yusuf Jolandan Mansur and others conducted research on the life and scientific heritage of Yakubi Charkhi. Researcher, Saidbek Makhmadullaev, in his article "Some moral views of Yakubi Charkhi" [12] paid special attention to issues such as the

human ethics of Yakubi Charkhi, a great representative of the Naqshbandi order, the means of attaining the purity of the soul, and getting rid of immorality. The researcher made good use of the mystic's treatises "Risolai Unsiya" and "Tafsiri Yakubi Charkhi".

Zayniddin Nabotov in the study "The human problem in Naqshbandiya teaching"[13] showed that the teaching of Naqshbandiya is widespread among the population to this day, in which Sufis such as Khoja Muhammad Porso, Maulana Yakubi Charkhi, Khoja Ahrori Vali, Fakhriddin Ali Safi, Abdurakhman Jami, promoted human qualities and spread universal values. focused on the important role of scientific heritage.

In Yusuf Jalondan Mansur's research on "Temuri period tombs in Movarounnahr and Khurasan: XIV-XV centuries" [14], Maulana Yakubi Charkhi's tomb is located in Halkati village on the outskirts of Dushanbe city. The researcher mentions that the mystic died on April 2, 1477. In particular, Ya'qubi gives information about Charkhi's work "Risalai abdoliya".

Ibrahimi Naqqosh's 456-page book "Risolahoi Piron va payravoni tariqati Naqshbandiya" [15] ("The treatises of the pirs and followers of the Naqshbandiya sect") has been published. The work contains the Tajik language translation of Mavlano Ya'qubi Charkhi's "Risolai unsiya". The researcher also published the pamphlet "Mawlano Ya'qubi Charkhi wa haft piri Naqshbandiya" ("Mawlano Ya'qubi Charkhi and the Seven Pirs of Naqshbandiya"). Pages 78-91 of this pamphlet are dedicated to Yaqubi Charkhi. Ibrahimi Naqqosh's 456-page book "Risolahoi Piron va payravoni tariqati Naqshbandiya" ("The treatises of the pirs and followers of the Naqshbandiya sect") has been published. The work contains the Tajik language translation of Mavlano Ya'qubi Charkhi's "Risolai unsiya". The researcher also published the pamphlet "Mawlano Ya'qubi Charkhi wa haft piri Naqshbandiya" ("Mawlano Ya'qubi Charkhi and the Seven Pirs of Naqshbandiya"). Pages 78-91 of this pamphlet are dedicated to Yaqubi Charkhi.

Jürgen Paul, Professor of the Center for the Study of Manuscripts at the University of Hamburg, Germany, in his 3-story dictionary[16], published in 2019, provides information about Yaqubi Charkhi's life, scientific heritage, and his meeting with Bahauddin Naqshband, mentor-student relationship. For example, in his monograph entitled "Khojagon-Naqshbandi doctrine and organizations after Bahauddin Naqshband", he focuses on the manifestations of Naqshbandi sect and gives information on the place of Yakubi Charkhi in the sect and his scientific heritage. It is mentioned that scholar Yakubi Charkhi learned the zikr from his teacher Bahauddin Naqshband and paid attention to his disciple Khwaja Ahrar Vali in this matter. According to Jürgen Paul, Yakubi Charkhi lived side by side with Alauddin for a couple of years until he went to the village of Halgatu near present-day Dushanbe and was buried there.

Summarizing the above points, we decided to devote our research work to the philosophical and social-political views of Yakubi Charkhi based on the research. We will analyze this problem on the basis of certain methodological principles, we will show that it has undergone transformation (re-change, re-creation) in the state of adaptation to the spirit of the times, and that this issue has not lost its relevance, but rather has increased interest in finding an answer. Therefore, the issue of Yaqubi Charkhi's philosophical and socio-political views from a historical-philosophical point of view was analyzed consistently by studying the studies of mystics and scientists from the Middle Ages to the present day, using the theological approach and philosophical comparativistic (i.e., comparative philosophy) methods.

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